

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF ARTS IN LANGUAGE AND LITERACY EDUCATION

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**DESIGNING A TRAINING FRAMEWORK FOR FILIPINO TEACHERS
USING COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING ACTIVITIES IN
TEACHING ORAL CONVERSATION FLUENCY
TO EFL CHINESE ADULT STUDENTS**

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03 June 2023

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Acceptance Page

This thesis titled: “**DESIGNING A TRAINING FRAMEWORK FOR FILIPINO TEACHERS USING COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING ORAL CONVERSATION FLUENCY TO EFL CHINESE ADULT STUDENTS,**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Education, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

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Biographical Sketch

Emmalyn G. Balon is an accomplished and dedicated educator with a strong background in language and literacy education. She began her teaching journey after graduating with honors as a Cum Laude in Secondary Education majoring in English from Holy Cross of Davao College in 2010. Since then, she has gained valuable experience in various educational settings, including teaching Kindergarten in Shanghai, China, and Vientiane, Laos.

Emmalyn is a renowned Online English Teacher-Mentor with a talent for engaging students from diverse backgrounds. Her exceptional teaching skills have earned her recognition as a featured teacher. Inspired by her love for language education, she founded LaoSpeak, an online language school, where she oversees a team of instructors delivering top-tier language education to Chinese and Laotian students.

Emmalyn's dedication to professional growth is evident through her extensive certifications, including Professional Licensed Teacher, TEFL, and TESOL. She has garnered recognition for her exceptional writing skills, achieving third place in a national essay writing competition held in Beijing. In addition to her teaching role, Emmalyn actively imparts her knowledge through co-training workshops focused on literature-based lesson planning and reading strategies.

Emmalyn's passion, dedication, and extensive experience make her a highly sought-after educator in language and literacy education. Through her commitment to empowering students and her continuous pursuit of excellence, she plays a pivotal role in shaping their language skills and enriching their lives.

Acknowledgment

I am incredibly grateful and would like to express my heartfelt appreciation to all those who have contributed to the completion of this thesis. It is with deep gratitude that I acknowledge the following individuals and institutions:

First and foremost, I extend my sincere thanks to God for His unwavering presence, guidance, and blessings throughout this entire journey. His divine wisdom, strength, and grace have been my constant source of inspiration and support.

To my cherished Balon family, thank you for your unconditional love, unwavering support, and belief in my abilities. Your encouragement, patience, and understanding have been my pillars of strength. I am forever grateful for the sacrifices you have made to ensure my success.

To my loving boyfriend, John Vincent D. Yee, thank you for standing by my side, providing unwavering support, and being a constant source of motivation and encouragement. Your belief in me has been instrumental in my perseverance and accomplishments.

I am deeply grateful to my advisor, Janette H. Malata-Silva, Ph.D., for her invaluable guidance, expertise, and mentorship throughout this research journey. Her commitment to my academic growth and their invaluable insights has significantly shaped the outcome of this thesis.

I am deeply grateful and extend my heartfelt appreciation to Andreas Carl M.D. Ph.D. and Bouavanh Pummaneevanh, my respected friends, for the endless cheer and unwavering support throughout this thesis journey. Your belief in my abilities has served as a constant motivation for me to push myself and strive for

greatness. I am truly thankful for your invaluable contributions and the positive impact you have had on my academic and personal growth.

I would also like to express my gratitude to the panel members for their time, expertise, and valuable inputs during the defense of this thesis. Their constructive criticism and thoughtful suggestions have immensely contributed to the refinement of this work.

I am indebted to the faculty of education at University of the Philippines – Open University, for providing a nurturing and supportive academic environment. Their commitment to excellence and dedication to shaping future educators have been integral to my growth and development.

My sincere appreciation goes to the participants of this study, whose willingness to share their time, experiences, and perspectives have enriched this research. Their invaluable contributions have formed the foundation of this thesis.

I am grateful to my friends and colleagues for their unwavering support, insightful discussions, and encouragement throughout this journey. Your friendship, camaraderie, and collaboration have made this experience more fulfilling and memorable.

To all those names may not be mentioned explicitly, I offer my sincerest apologies. Your support, whether big or small, has been deeply appreciated and cherished.

In conclusion, I express my deepest gratitude for the unwavering support, encouragement, and contributions. It is because of their presence in my life that I have been able to achieve this milestone. Thank you for believing in me and for being a part of this incredible journey.

Emmalyn Gomez Balon

Abstract

The online language education market in the Philippines has experienced significant growth, leading to an increased demand for qualified online English teachers. This study aimed to investigate the training needs of online English teachers in the country and develop an effective training program. A sequential explanatory research design was employed, involving 15 teachers who participated in a survey and seven of them who were interviewed. Data collection included web-based surveys and interviews, analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative techniques. The findings informed the development of a training program guided by instructional design models. The study addressed research questions related to TPACK levels, demographic variables, preferred pedagogical practices, and training content recommendations.

Results showed that most participants believed they had excellent TPACK skills, with Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) receiving the highest rating and Technological Knowledge (TK) the lowest. Educational attainment did not significantly affect TPACK levels, but education degree holders and experienced teachers generally had higher TPACK scores. Younger age groups and confident explorers of technology excelled in TPACK categories. Across all demographic factors, Technological Knowledge (TK) emerges as the most crucial area for all teachers. Teaching experience, personal characteristics, and professional development were identified as key factors in effective teaching.

The study also revealed insights into the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework, with participants valuing direct instruction, feedback, affective expression, and open communication. While triggering events and exploration

activities were effective for cognitive presence, reflection and resolution activities could be improved. The findings provide valuable insights for enhancing the training of online English teachers in the Philippines, ensuring they meet international standards and deliver effective instruction in the growing online language education market.

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Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background

The widespread use of English as the dominant language in business, science, and technology has resulted in a significant rise in the number of people trying to become proficient in it as a second language (ESL) or a foreign language (EFL). John Knagg in Bentley (2022) noted that the global population of individuals learning English is approximately 1.5 billion. Meanwhile, the exponential growth of the Internet and the extensive adoption of personal computers in domestic and academic settings have led to a consistent expansion of online language instruction (Felix, 2003; Hubbard & Levy, 2006; Stickler & Hauck, 2006; White, 2003). This advancement in technology across the globe has made language learning more accessible to learners through online education. The global market for online language learning is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of 13.1% from 2019 to 2025, reaching an estimated value of \$10.5 billion. The English language and individual learner segments dominate this industry. The Asia-Pacific region, particularly China, is expected to experience significant growth. China accounted for about 30% of the global market share in 2018, which is anticipated to continue (Smith, 2023; Meticulous Market Research Pvt. Ltd., 2019). The rapid growth of the online language learning market highlights the significance of foreign teachers possessing teaching certificates, as emphasized by the Chinese Ministry of Education (Xuejiao, 2019). In light of the prevailing circumstances, there is an urgent requirement for a considerable number of skilled educators who can teach English through online platforms.

There is a noticeable demand for Filipino individuals to engage in online English teaching in the Philippines. Notably, two prominent online language schools in the country have announced their plans to hire a substantial number of Filipino online language teachers, with one aiming to recruit 10,000 teachers and the other targeting 100,000 teachers (Business Mirror, 2020; Duran, 2019). These teachers are expected to deliver online lessons that enable students to develop fluent oral communication skills, primarily driven by the lack of speaking opportunities in students' home countries. Online language schools in the Philippines have identified specific qualifications for prospective teachers, including the ability to speak English with a neutral accent, possess a bachelor's degree, and adequate computer skills. Language teaching certificates and prior teaching experience have traditionally been seen as beneficial but optional for online language teachers. However, China's regulations now require online education platforms to disclose detailed information about their foreign teachers, including names, teaching credentials, and previous employment experience (Xuejiao, 2019; Ministry of Education PRC, 2019). As a result, these qualifications have become essential for teachers in the Chinese online education sector.

Language Teacher Education (LTE) programs for online English teachers are widely available online. A diverse array of programs with varying durations and content are available, ranging from brief 40-hour programs to more extensive programs covering 100 hours. There are available certificate programs for individuals interested in teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL) or teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL). Murray (2013) reported that a vast majority of online language teacher education (OLTE) courses discovered through a web search were offered by institutions in the United States. It is not unexpected that a

considerable proportion of teacher education programs are subject to or financially aided by English language educators who maintain prominent positions within their sphere (Snow et al., 2006). Even so, Brown (2012) advocates a departure from the conventional reliance on native-speaker paradigms and posits the incorporation of alternative forms of English, distinct from American and British English, in pedagogical resources intended to teach English as a second language (ESL) or foreign language. Concepts related to World Englishes (WE) and Global Englishes (GE) are already on board in a few teacher training programs like Cambridge ESOL Delta (Dewey, 2012, 2014, 2015; Dewey & Leung, 2010) and TESOL (Cameron & Galloway, 2019).

Nevertheless, it must be noted that the present situation concerning TESOL programs or online language teacher education indicates a notable deficiency in established standards. (Rodriguez, 2016). Also, Abras and Sunshine (2008) highlighted the inconsistency between recommended practices and the lack of uniform benchmarks in technology standards within teacher education, thereby identifying these areas as significant considerations within the field of Learning Technologies in Education (LTE). Besides the little headway made by these training programs into GE, a notable limitation has been acknowledged as the absence of a meticulously crafted and inclusive curriculum in teacher training for non-native English speakers (Bhowmik, 2015). In order to strengthen OLTE programs, a rising number of scholars have used the Community of Inquiry (CoI) structure.

Meanwhile, the instruction and mentoring of English as a foreign language are often carried out by individuals who need more qualifications and expertise as instructors (Henrichsen, 2010). In a study by Hubbard (2008), he discovered a

particular group of language educators who need more understanding and awareness concerning the function of technology in facilitating language instruction. According to Kessler's (2006) research, a significant proportion of educators acquire their expertise in Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) through informal means or self-directed study rather than formal training. TESOL program graduates from his study also expressed dissatisfaction with formal CALL preparation (Kessler, 2006).

Language instructors are "pivotal players" in the future of CALL since they are in charge of selecting the tools that will support their instruction and determining which CALL applications language learners will come across and how they will use them (Hubbard, 2008). In Mercado's (2013) study, it was found that gender, level of educational attainment, and eligibility as an online language educator are strong predictors of success in facilitating English language instruction in an online setting. Indeed, it is a disadvantage for language teachers who need to be adequately trained for CALL (Hubbard & Levy, 2006). The need for quality professional development for online English teachers is evident. Preparing faculty to teach online ripples positive impacts on learning effectiveness, faculty satisfaction (Moore, 2013), student satisfaction, and higher retention rate of faculty and potential students (Green et al., 2009).

Professional development programs have a significant role in enhancing teacher competencies (Sabbah et al., 2020). Age, experience, academic accomplishment, teaching ability, academic grades, and socioeconomic position are significant teaching predictors of competency (Debnath, 1971; Sharma, 1971). Bhattacharjee and Carri (2020) found that age, location, and gender are not associated with the teaching competency of secondary English instructors. In the

meantime, online English teachers may have encountered a distinct set of challenges whose required abilities differ from their offline counterparts (Hampel & Stickler, 2005) and for whom a teaching credential is optional (Dinu, 2020).

Although there are attempts to understand online language teacher's teaching competencies to guide training programs better (Berber-McNeill, 2015; Compton, 2009; Guichon, 2009; Hampel & Stickler, 2005; Jauregi et al., 2012; Rios, 2015; Sun, 2011,), most of these are situated in academic set-up. Respondents in these studies are also qualified to teach English in a conventional classroom. There is limited attention given to online language teachers' competencies and personal characteristics, and prior experiences that can specifically inform course developers on the training needs of each group and how to teach them.

The Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework has enormous promise for evaluating the skills and knowledge of online language teachers in practical settings. The dynamic interaction between three distinct knowledge domains, namely technology, pedagogy, and content, is at the heart of the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework. The significance of the regions where teaching and learning overlap is emphasized by TPACK. It also comes with a survey questionnaire which may be used to reveal OELTs' perception of their TPACK skills. This will eventually lead to identifying their training needs. However, various factors significantly impact how teachers perceive technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK), as Chai et al. (2011) posited. According to the body of research, there are differences between educators' Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) domains, with possible contributing factors including teaching experience, level of education, gender, and age (Erdogan & Sahin, 2010; Jang & Tsai, 2013; Lee & Tsai, 2010; Luik et al., 2018).

Thus, looking into these factors that may contribute to developing their TPACK skills is also significant. Researchers are urged to consider demographic characteristics throughout the design and development phase of training programs intended to improve teachers' Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK), as Mailizar et al. (2021) suggested. The implementation of such programs is likely to be more successful as a result of this strategy.

Professional development programs are undeniably vital for online language teachers to be competent and ready in their field. It is crucial first to understand the particular requirements and unique circumstances under which educators function to promote significant instructional improvement within the educational community (Gaible & Burns, 2005). It has been argued by Wanzare and Ward (2000) that modern staff development approaches should enable educators to engage in active involvement within programs crafted to address their on-the-job training.

Research Questions and Objectives

This study aims to deliver a training framework that can be relevant and effective by identifying their training needs and pedagogical preferences. In order to attain this goal, the study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the TPACK level of online English language teachers (OELTs)?
2. Is there a relationship between OELT's demographic variables and their TPACK level?
3. What are the pedagogical practices in their language teacher education training that online English language teachers find effective?
4. Based on their TPACK level and CoI preferences, what training content and pedagogical guidelines should be provided to teachers?

Significance of the Study

The study intended to address the training needs of online English teachers by proposing training content that considers the level of TPACK skills among online English language teachers. Also, this study provides guidelines on how the proposed content should be delivered by identifying the pedagogical practices that these teachers believe to be effective in their language teacher education training. Thus, the findings of this study are expected to guide the creation of a unique training course to cater to the requirements of online English teachers working in the Philippines.

Primarily, this work could benefit online language schools that strive to improve the quality of their online education by honing their teachers' competence. The findings of this study hold considerable implications for online language schools operating within and outside the Philippines, particularly those targeting Chinese EFL learners. Given that Chinese students constitute the largest market share in the online language education industry (Zhang, 2019), online language schools must consider the stringent regulations set by the Chinese Ministry of Education (China MOE, 2018). Consequently, the findings of this study provide a timely opportunity for these institutions to reevaluate and adapt their training programs accordingly.

Secondly, current and future online language teachers could learn practical tips and practices that could be used as self-development tools in improving their online language teaching competencies.

Also, this could bring new light to academic institutions that offer teacher education. It could provide new insights on what and how to equip 21st-century language educators whose career opportunity is wider than conventional classroom set-up.

Moreover, this study contributes to the body of the literature by acknowledging the voices of online language teachers regardless of their teaching qualifications and status. Shelley et al. (2006) observed that tutors and other supporting staff in online education frequently fail to get their contributions acknowledged or even enquired about by superiors or researchers, creating an impression for educators that their opinions are unsolicited and disregarded. A discussion made by Stickler and Emke specified that 'the part-time language teacher is almost invisible: marginalized in the profession, under-researched in studies, and under-represented in the literature' (Hampel & Stickler, 2015, p.36). The claim above suggests that the qualifications of part-time language teachers in European academic settings are comparable to those of full-time online English teachers in the Philippines.

Finally, the results of this study support the advice of the English Language Teaching (ELT) community to create educational plans that go beyond standard English and take into account the particularities of the context in which they are implemented. In training pre-service and in-service English teachers, Snow et al. (2006) stressed that "...the immediate context of language teaching and the socio-cultural factors..." (p. 274) should be essential criteria while devising teacher training programs for English-as-a-lingua-franca settings. Thus, the product of this paper is to deliver a training program that includes Filipino online English teachers' demographics, values, attitudes, beliefs, and context.

Scope and Delimitations

This study is limited by (a) the geographic location, nationality, and teaching contexts of the respondents; (b) sample selection; and (c) the mode of online instruction. This study employed a sequential explanatory method that was carried out over 16 weeks.

First, this study is restricted to Filipino online English teachers residing in the Philippines. Also, these teachers should have offered a one-to-one 25-minute English teaching service to EFL Chinese adult students who aim to acquire conversational fluency. They should have conducted classes that do any or one of the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach activities (e.g., role-playing, filling in missing information, pair discussions, opinion-sharing, and discussion-leading questions).

Second, the study sample is drawn exclusively from those who meet the selection as mentioned above criteria. Finally, the modality of online teaching that the respondents utilize must be via audio or video-synchronous computer-mediated communication (SCMC). Classes must have been conducted either on Zoom, Skype, or a company-based customized platform. Text-based SCMC is excluded from this study.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This study examines the need of Filipino teachers to teach the English language through online conferencing. It aims to devise a training program that considers their sociocultural factors and actual training needs based on their Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) level. Along with the TPACK framework, Community of Inquiry is also utilized to provide an online teacher education program that these teachers find effective.

This literature review includes the following sections: (a) online education, (b) online language teaching, (c) online teachers, (d) online teachers' education, (e) language teacher's education, (f) online language teacher's teaching competency, (g) teaching speaking and SCMC, (h) communicative competence, (i) communicative language teaching and task-based language teaching, (j) communicative language teaching activities, (k) roles of teachers and students in CLT classrooms, (k) Chinese as EFL learners, (l) educational technology framework and standards, (m) TPACK framework, (n) TPACK and EFL teaching, (o) Community of Inquiry, and (p) instructional design models.

Online Education

With the significant advancement of technology, online education has not only become a trend or an alternative in the field of education. It has become a new form of classroom setting that requires adaptation and innovation of traditional practices in teaching. The introduction of personal computers has significantly aided the development and acceptance of online education. The vast global dissemination of

conceptual ideas and the incorporation of various technical instruments to enhance communication and provide educational access to broad and diverse audiences describe this style of academic instruction (Collins, 2002). According to Passmore (2009), online education ought to provide pertinent and genuine knowledge delivery mechanisms while ensuring high-quality instruction. Salmon (2011) contends that activities found in online learning are characterized by high levels of purposefulness and are guided by clear goals, outcomes, and directions.

Meanwhile, the field of second language acquisition (SLA) research has increasingly focused on computer-mediated communication (CMC) as a means to enhance language learning. Computer-mediated communication (CMC) is "communication that takes place between human beings via the instrumentality of computers" (Herring, 1996, p. 1). This can come in two forms, asynchronous and synchronous. An asynchronous CMC (ACMC) does not happen in real-time. Synchronous communication among participants is not mandatory, as messages can be saved on a server (IGI Global, n.d). Examples of this form are text messaging, email, blog posts, and discussion forums.

On the other hand, synchronous computer-mediated communication (SCMC) provides an environment that closely resembles real-time interactions. All parties are engaged in the communication simultaneously; however, they are all in different locations. For this study, SCMC is the form the participants utilize for their job as online language educators.

Apart from convenience, SCMC has brought good benefits to language learners. It has been found that using video conferencing as a type of synchronous computer-mediated communication (SCMC) enables conversations between native and non-native speakers, thereby improving learners' communication skills.

According to Jauregui et al. (2012), the phenomena above also encourage novice learners' propensity for L2 acquisition and the ease with which they can become proficient in a second language (L2).

Online Language Teaching

Online language learning via video conferencing has become popular among English language students in Asia. The demand for online English tutoring is particularly high in nations like South Korea, Japan, Russia, and China (Zhang, 2019). The Philippines provides teaching services to the countries above.

As a former online English instructor, I would compare this type of online language instruction to an "after-school English tutorial class," except it takes place online using audio or video-conferencing platforms like Skype, Zoom, or company-specific software. The following are some common practices in a synchronous online language teaching environment. As observed, online teaching practices include the following: (a) an online language teacher engages with students one-on-one and/or occasionally in small groups (usually up to four); (b) lessons and performance comments are tailored to each student's needs; (c) course materials are readily prepared and designed by the online education company; (d) student's assessment is informal; (e) teachers are booked depending on student's preference; and (f) teacher's performance is evaluated by students after a session is conducted. Outside the synchronous online language teaching, teachers may either seek technical assistance, disputing student complaints, or have a coaching session with the company's quality assurance team. To perform at his/her best is crucial to an online language teacher's reputation as their reputation builds the company's credibility that can increase the number of enrollees.

Online language companies should note that success in the marketplace is correlated to the quality of education they provide (Abel, 2005). Significant areas that have strong connections to quality in online learning are the ability of faculty to adapt to teaching in the online environment (Fish & Wickersham, 2009), professional advancement opportunities for online instruction, as well as the level of satisfaction expressed by instructors in regard to online teaching (Allen & Seaman, 2013; Bolliger et al., 2014; Cole et al., 2010; Koepke & O'Brien, 2012; Moore, 2013; Storandt et al., 2012).

Online Teachers

To maintain the caliber of education in a setting that fully integrates the environment, it is imperative for educators to be adequately prepared and consistently informed about the requirements of the system. The scholarly findings of Davis and Rose (2007) and Wood (2005) show that the idea that people who are excellent at traditional face-to-face education are innately capable of smoothly shifting to and efficiently instructing in alternative mediums is a myth. In 2007, the Professional Development for Virtual Schooling and Online Learning report by the North American Council of Online Learning (NACOL) identified typical fallacies pertaining to virtual educators. Three of these common misconceptions are:

- A teacher who holds a standard teaching license already possesses the skills required to instruct students in an online learning environment.
- A teacher with advanced training and experience in a traditional classroom setting is well-suited to instruct a top-notch online course that has been created or bought in advance.

- A recently certified teacher who has experienced virtual learning in their pre-service programs will be equipped with the skills and knowledge required to deliver effective online instruction.

According to Johnson (2008), it was found that a number of instructors engaged in teaching online courses lacked formal training in the area of online instruction. The instructors acknowledged their deficiency in effectively imparting instructional content. This predicament is also shared in second language teaching. In addition to the prevalence of individuals lacking formal training in English as a Second Language instruction, research conducted by Hubbard (2008) has indicated a concerning trend of language teachers completing their education without adequate exposure to the utilization of technology for pedagogical purposes. Furthermore, Hampel and Stickler (2015) cite findings from the 2008 Developing Online Teaching Skills (DOTS) project survey conducted by Germain-Rutherford and Ernest (2010), which indicate that among the surveyed educators who reported receiving little to no training in utilizing information and communication technology (ICT) for pedagogical purposes, a significant proportion (30%) relied on self-directed learning. Kessler's (2006) research posits that teachers' attainment of computer-assisted language learning (CALL) proficiency is primarily derived through informal and self-directed avenues, in contrast to formal instructional approaches. According to his statement, there is a prevailing sense of discontent among TESOL program alumni regarding their formal training in Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL).

In Mercado's (2013) study with 73 Filipino online teachers teaching English to Koreans, he found out that teachers possessing expertise in technology, effective

communication, online pedagogy, and content knowledge are efficient in the delivery of online English courses. The success of online English education is found to be significantly associated with the gender, highest level of education attained, and eligibility status of the instructors.

On the other hand, lack of preparation may make it difficult for educators working in the online learning environment to meet the diverse needs of their students. (Bush et al., 2010). Teachers who do not have enough experience make learning bad for learners as teachers struggle to learn about the online environment and understand the best strategies for teaching curriculum particularly to adult learners (Gilmore & Warren, 2007).

Considering the duties and responsibilities of eight stakeholders at various levels in distance education (Compton, 2009), the functions of online teachers may vary in quantity but are unquestionably burdensome. Online teachers, as a final stakeholder in distance education (DE), humanize the learning environment. According to Harms et al. (2006) and Moore and Kearsley (2011), the establishment of a sense of co-presence within the virtual classroom leads to a reduction in the perceived distance of the learning environment. Online teachers perform a variety of tasks in the online learning environment, such as facilitating, encouraging active involvement and high levels of interaction, giving feedback, and adopting the role of other stakeholders.

Online Teachers' Education

Undoubtedly, a substantial education for online teachers is a must. It is vital that online faculty are prepared and knowledgeable because they are expected to

demonstrate more teaching competencies and attitudes that are developed through preparation and effort (Bawane & Spector, 2009; Wlodkowski, 2008).

The term "teacher education" typically refers to efforts or programs that prepare future teachers at the undergraduate or graduate levels within higher education institutions, with a concentration on a particular set of potential teaching professionals. It is important to mention that educators who are currently employed as teachers, also known as practicing or in-service teachers participate in additional educational opportunities to improve their knowledge and skills. These undertakings aim to expand their knowledge and skill sets, as well as to acquire novel knowledge and skills relevant in disparate educational contexts (Dawley & Rice, 2010).

Reports on online teacher training are developing over the years. According to Pape (2007), it is rare for classroom teachers to have received pre-service training in online teaching. Additionally, opportunities for the development of such skills are scarce, even throughout the duration of their employment. Conversely, a comprehensive survey conducted by Going Virtual in 2010, as referenced in Dawley and Rice's work (2010), which was answered by 830 respondents across 40 US states, contradicts previous reports. Throughout the study, online educators were solicited for information pertaining to the characteristics and substance of the benefit they had obtained from professional development, as well as the specific areas in which they expressed the requirement for continued professional development. It is noteworthy to mention that educators predominantly cited persistent training programs and workshops as the primary forms of professional advancement. This affirmation was confirmed by 94% of respondents who reported receiving such training through their respective academic institutions or affiliated organizations. However, 25% of new online teachers reported that they received no training.

Whereas Zweig and Stafford's (2016) study on four online learning programs in the Midwest, indicated that 63%-88% received training while teaching online rather than prior to teaching online.

Moreover, online teachers expressed their training preferences in the studies of Dawley and Rice (2010) and Zweig and Stafford (2016). Various suggestions have been put forward to enhance the professional growth of online instructors. These include the implementation of a fully online facilitated professional development (Dawley & Rice, 2010), the provision of a personalized professional development experience (Zweig & Stafford, 2016), and the adoption of an unstructured approach to professional development to better address the primary challenges encountered in an online teaching environment (Zweig & Stafford, 2016).

The iNACOL's Professional Development for Virtual Schooling and Online Learning (2007) advocates for the recognition and accommodation of diverse preferences. The guide underscores the requirement for professional development to be customized to suit diverse considerations like individual necessities, job functions, cultural origins, as well as contextual intricacies. Moreover, the aforementioned guide proposes the incorporation of virtual educational programs into pre-service and professional growth endeavors.

Moreover, the Southern Regional Education Board (SREB) in 2009 proposed the usage of diverse modalities for professional development of online teachers, inclusive of mentorship, observation of exemplary online teaching models, and practical exposure to technology tools. These guidelines aim to enhance the quality of online education through an effective and diversified approach to teacher training. SREB has additionally advised on the recommended areas of practice that ought to be incorporated in professional development. This paper presents three essential

domains within instructional technology: academic, content knowledge, skills, and temperament, and online teaching and learning methodology management, knowledge, skills, and delivery. The National Education Association (NEA) (n.d.) has proposed that effective training programs are essential for online educators, particularly in the domains of (1) proficient communication practices, involving appropriate and prompt feedback provision; (2) guided discussions; (3) the facilitation of teamwork and creation of multimedia-based projects; (3) modification of curriculum and instructional materials; and, (4) the effective deployment of online resources to support optimal instructional outcomes.

Cohan (2011) has demonstrated that singular instances of training or professional development workshops do not yield significant effectiveness. According to Iskander's (2009) results, different faculty members have different technical needs in relation to their educational methods. The current discourse in professional development suggests that virtual or hybrid training courses should exhibit novelty and practicality, while also considering contextual factors (Iskander, 2009). Additionally, such initiatives should facilitate opportunities for educators to apply, rehearse, and assimilate newly acquired knowledge (Rothwell, 2010; Seidel, 2010).

Collaboration is a notable keyword along with successful professional development for online teachers. The notion of communities is commonly recognized as a distinguishing feature of successful professional advancement, regardless of whether such programs are executed in a physical locality (Little, 2003; Louis & Marks, 1998; McLaughlin & Talbert, 2001) or virtually (Barab et al, 2004; Koch & Fusco, 2004). Vaughan and Garrison (2006) put "collegial network" as fundamental in a community-based approach to faculty training and development. It

is imperative that the design of the intervention program provides opportunities for faculty members to actively engage in communication, interaction, and collaborative endeavors. (Harrington-Mackin, 2008). Incorporating faculty feedback into professional development is crucial, particularly for online or hybrid programs, in order to improve faculty instructional practices (Sisk-Hilton, 2015).

Language Teacher's Education

Programs that address the education of P-12 ESL instructors must adhere to a set of requirements that have been created by the TESOL International Association. The above-mentioned directives were formally approved in 2001; changes were made in 2005 and 2010, with the latter being the most recent revision (TESOL International Association, 2010). Other existing standards from TESOL International Association are for the ESL/EFL teachers of adults. The program indicated above is similar to what is designed for English as Second Language teachers in the primary through twelfth grade levels. However, it is delivered through a series of guidelines that teachers should follow when facilitating education. The framework developed by the TESOL International Association in 2008 consists of eight different categories that include all of the requirements for efficient language education. Planning, teaching, evaluating, taking identity and context into account, testing language proficiency, choosing the right learning materials, and adhering to professionalism are some of these domains.

The TESOL Organization's certification effort is currently the main way to advance one's professional development in the field of online English as a Second Language (ESL) instruction (TESOL, 2008). Both face-to-face and online courses are available in the Philippines for TESOL and undergraduate or graduate Language

Teacher Education (LTE) degrees. Based on Murray's (2013) study, many online language teachers, including Filipino participants, prefer an LTE course delivered online due to its convenience and flexibility.

Conceding to Murray's (2013) data, it is also important to acknowledge England's (2012) warning that effective online teacher educators' skills and knowledge are somewhat different from those required from conventional face-to-face TESOL teachers. Rodriguez (2016) posits that a dearth of criteria presently prevails for programs pertaining to Online Language Teacher Education (OLTE) or Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL). Given these considerations, it is conceivable that the TESOL program or training provided to online language instructors may not entirely align with the specific requirements of educators operating within an electronic learning environment.

Online Language Teacher's Teaching Competency

As English language teachers, they should know how to (1) use the target language, (2) educate culturally sensitively, and (3) behave in a target culture (Pasternak & Bailey, 2014). It has also been emphasized that possessing native-level fluency in the English language and being competent in its use are not inherently correlated. To be eligible to teach, any English native speaker must have substantial professional training in addition to being proficient in English.

Many models and frameworks have been developed that specify the necessary skills online teachers must possess. These works also aim to inform and refine online teacher training programs. The Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework, as articulated by Koehler and Mishra (2009), is a widespread framework. This theoretical framework highlights the significance of

technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge in effectively incorporating technology into teaching. In brief, this framework asserts that teachers must possess a comprehensive understanding of these three knowledge domains in order to successfully integrate technology into their instructional practices. (Koehler & Mishra, 2009). Another study is from Albrahim (2020) who reviewed and analyzed literature in order to determine the skills and competencies needed by instructors to effectively teach in an online learning environment. Extensive scholarly research has been done on the categories of pedagogy, technology, design, content, management/institutional, and social/communicative abilities in modern academic discourse. Also, Albrahim (2020) listed the online teaching skills as task or performance statements belonging to each of the categories. In accordance with Guichon's (2009) findings, there are three primary competencies which are associated with the provision of synchronous online teaching. These competencies are categorized as socio-affective, pedagogical, and multi-media regulation and are purported to be integrated with technical aspects of online teaching, rather than functioning as distinct or separate entities (p. 170).

The pedagogy of teaching language online necessitates a distinctive skill set that diverges from that of teaching face-to-face classroom language courses or instructing other subjects in an online context, as language serves as both the means and the substance of teaching (Borg, 2006). Moreover, it is imperative to acknowledge that online language education, by its very nature, imposes critical cognitive and emotional demands on learners. This notion is articulated by Hurd (2008), who underscores the significant affective challenges that often accompany online language acquisition.

Hampel and Stickler (2005) have put forth a theoretical framework, which they

refer to as the "pyramid model," that encompasses seven essential competencies necessary for effective language teaching in an online synchronous setting. Their foundation is grounded in the expertise they have acquired in this realm, including their experience in online tutor training. The model highlights competencies that span from fundamental skill sets to those of a higher order nature. The acquisition of fundamental ICT proficiency, proficiency in particular technical and software competencies, as well as an understanding of the limitations and potential of these skills, must be augmented by more advanced abilities. These might include: online socialization that enables the fostering of communicative competence, creativity, and the capacity for individuals to make informed decisions in their selection of communication choices. According to the source, the acquisition of online language teaching abilities ought to progress hierarchically, with fundamental proficiencies forming a broad foundation upon which to develop one's individual and personalized techniques, ultimately culminating in a pinnacle of mastery.

Additionally, studies by Kozlova and Priven (2015) and Morales (2015) showed that proficiency in computer-assisted language learning (CALL) was learned through a spiral and iterative process. The development of online pedagogical expertise can be conceptualized as a spiral process, according to Kozlova and Priven (2015), in which the abilities first learned during the pre-teaching phase are then improved upon and reevaluated during the teaching stage. A natural progression from a broad capacity to formulate a task to more particular abilities, such as providing information and organizing cooperation, occurred as a result of teacher training being implemented in an actual situation.

Compton (2009) asserts that the paradigm created by Hampel and Stickler falls short of providing recommendations for how well-prepared an online language

tutor should be for teaching responsibilities. Compton (2009) developed a different framework for online language teaching skills that is divided into three categories: technology in online language teaching, online language teaching pedagogy, and online language teaching assessment. The categories are logically grouped on a proficiency continuum with three distinct tiers, namely novice, proficient, and expert, removing the uncertainty surrounding a teacher's readiness to instruct.

On the other hand, Berber-McNeill (2015) attempted to operationalize and quantify the participants' online language teaching skills while they were instructing a class online by combining Hampel and Stickler's (2005) and Compton's (2009) framework competencies. Three graduate students who were Spanish lecturers at a big public institution took part in it. Insights into what factors contribute to the formation of these online language teaching skills and how to maintain their continuing development were provided by Berber-McNeill's (2015) case study.

Although Hampel and Stickler's (2005) and Compton's (2009) frameworks are found to be relevant for online English teacher's teaching competencies, two important points are not fulfilled. Both frameworks have not mentioned online language teacher's content mastery, but rather on technological and pedagogical aspects. Secondly, the creativity or expert aspect of the aforementioned frameworks could be ambiguous to translate into performance statements. According to Sun's (2011) research, the existing frameworks were deemed deficient in their specificity with regard to their practicality for implementation in the daily practices of online language educators. A novice online teacher could discover little guidance in their plans. The solutions to the questions of what to do and how to do it, or what not to do, remain unknown. Thus, the TPACK framework, which is more comprehensive, will be utilized for this study. To add, Albrahim's (2020) online teaching performance

tasks will be included in the survey due to its specificity. Nevertheless, these teaching skills will be categorized under TPACK constructs where they seem to be fit.

Teaching Speaking and SCMC

Speaking is one of the more challenging responsibilities in the teaching and learning of languages since it requires intense practice and a strong commitment to reach high proficiency. Johnson (1997) claims that speech can be thought of as a combinatorial talent that requires carrying out several tasks at once. To improve a learner's speaking competence, teachers must find efficient ways of helping language learners. Fluency and accuracy in language usage are two objectives of speaking. Speaking has been cited as one of the most difficult abilities for educators to convey (Scott & Yterberg, 1990) and is a vital part of the learning and teaching of second languages (Cahyono & Mukminatien, 2011).

According to Nunan (2004), speaking refers to the process of creating language expressions systematically in order to effectively communicate meaning. Speaking also involves prosodic features such as pronunciation, intonation and stress patterns that can be taxing for non-native speakers. For Nunan (1989), the functions of speaking refer to as: monologue or dialogue. In the domain of spoken discourse, a monologue is distinguished by an uninterrupted and continuous delivery of oral expression, whereas dialogue refers to active participation in a verbal exchange with interlocutors. Bygate (1997) views the skill in two categories: production skills and interaction skills. Production skills are used to change the oral production with the aid of facilitation tools such formulaic phrases, simplified structures, fillers, and hesitation or compensating techniques. A key component of

interaction skills is being able to explain what you mean to say in a way that the listener can easily understand. For this study, online language teachers and students engage in speaking as a dialogue and as interaction skills.

Numerous studies have demonstrated that SCMC is effective in giving students speaking experience. Additionally, SCMC is a potential method for those who are hesitant in face-to-face interactions, assisting them in developing greater speaking confidence (Wallace, 1999; Carvevale, 2003, as mentioned in Okuyama, 2005, p. 4).

Learners could practice conversational skills they would need in the real world, which are challenging to imitate using conventional chatting tools, through audio/video conferencing (Yanguas & Flores, 2014).

Moreover, Yamagata-Lynch (2014) stats that the use of synchronous online sessions for the entire class as well as properly planned small group meetings may improve the students' sense of community among their peers and their instructor and enable their meaningful participation in course-related activities. According to the author, these synchronous communication tools encourage students to engage actively in the learning objectives by fostering natural conversations among themselves. When learners are engaged, the interaction of messages is concurrent (Stockwell, 2007). This exchanged message provides an opportunity for learners to develop "fluency" for their speaking skills (Murray, 2008).

A study conducted by Hamano-Bunce (2011) said that the employment of SCMC holds significant potential in facilitating oral discourse, promoting comprehensible input through interactional modification, offering corrective feedback, encouraging pushed output, and fostering collaborative dialogue amongst college students within the United Arab Emirates. Pioneering in audio SCMC studies in

CALL, Jepson (2005) aimed to investigate the reparative actions made by English as a Second Language (ESL) learners in the context of communication through audio synchronous computer-mediated communication (SCMC) and textual chat within an online private institution for English language learning. The findings indicate that there was a greater occurrence of negotiation for meaning in discussions that utilized audio-mediated synchronous computer-mediated communication (SCMC), in comparison to those that relied on text-based chat. Nevertheless, video conferencing has been promoted by numerous scholars as a useful method for encouraging student connection, according to Levy and Stockwell (2006) in Jung (2016).

Skype software has been evident in some research in relation to language teaching. Academic research centered on Skype encompasses a multitude of linguistic modalities, including but not limited to Spanish (Volle, 2005; Lee, 2008), Italian (Tudini, 2003), and French (Lamy, 2004; Hauck, 2007). The prevalence of the English language has been widely observed in several Asian countries, including Taiwan as reported by Lee (2008), Japan as studied by Tsukamoto et al. (2009), Malaysia as described by Maclean (2008), and Vietnam as analyzed by Hong (2006). The study entails online audio or video conferencing consisting of interactions between students and language instructors, as well as between students and individuals who are native speakers. The findings obtained from these research endeavors indicate a discernible trend wherein students readily seek to enhance their command over oral language skills through the utilization of the aforementioned application (Lamy, 2004).

In connection, Kopf (2012) examined video SCMC exchanges amongst German secondary school students in New Zealand. He came to the conclusion that the use of video conferencing enhanced students' capacity for interpersonal

connection. Furthermore, the research by Vurdien (2019) shows that EFL students in the experimental group (n=18) who engaged in communicative tasks with their partners via Zoom video conferencing outperformed the control group (n=12) who carried out the same tasks in face-to-face classrooms.

Communicative Competence

The students can conduct good communication if they have sufficient competency in communication. Some experts call this competency as communicative competence. Dell Hymes first established the idea of communicative competency in 1966. The author defines communicative competence as a person's latent linguistic knowledge and their ability to use it effectively in communication contexts. Oral, written, and nonverbal methods of communication are all acceptable ways to demonstrate this competency. Oral fluency is one of the key elements of communicative ability. For this paper, online language teachers help their students improve their oral fluency through conversational tasks.

Oral fluency is a particular quality that indicates proficient speaking talent. It is evidenced by a learner's capacity to converse with ease, without superfluous hesitations, and with speech prosody, syntax, and vocabulary range comparable to that of a native speaker (Polyakov & Tormyshova, 2014). Such a feat requires performance that is well above average. According to Chambers (1997), fluency is therefore viewed as a performance indicator in the assessment of non-native language learners' oral skills and acts as a gauge of their progress in language learning. Effective communication is said to require speech that is understandable, making it a key component of communication.

Several studies offered their suggestions on how to improve communicative competence. According to Al Alami's (2014) empirically-based investigation, incorporating literature into instruction may serve as an efficacious approach to enhancing the communicative aptitude of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners. Buitrago Campo's (2016) mixed-method action research investigation highlights the task-based learning approach as a potential means of enhancing students' English communicative competence. Agbatogun (2013) conducted a quasi-experimental investigation that revealed the potential for enhanced communicative competence among ESL learners through the utilization of clickers within a classroom setting. Furthermore, Pillar's (2011) examination showcases a correlation between video implementation and effective instruction regarding receptive and productive language skills. To evaluate communicative competence among students, Pillar suggests the integration of an evaluative assessment.

Some researchers focused on specific activities that can develop learner's communicative competence. The study conducted by Ampatuan and Jose (2016) presents a qualitative analysis proposing role-play as an effective communicative tool to support the acquisition of students' communicative competence. Bang's (2003) mixed-methods investigation revealed that incorporating drama activities can foster an interactive learning environment, facilitating the natural use of the target language by students. Furthermore, the qualitative phenomenological study conducted by Catoto and San Jose (2016) has indicated that the implementation of class reporting can serve as a valuable approach to augment students' communicative competence, self-assurance, and interpersonal abilities. According to the mixed-methods study conducted by Gómez Palacio (2010), there exists a range of efficacious strategies that can foster the improvement of ESL students'

communicative competence. These methods include but are not limited to independent reading, storytelling, role-playing, information gap activities, and peer tutoring. The aforementioned tasks exhibit a close correlation with Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Instruction based on Tasks.

Communicative Language Teaching and Task-Based Language Teaching

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) have garnered significant adoption in the Asia-Pacific region, with numerous Asian countries firmly advocating the use of CLT and TBLT approaches in their curricula and English language education policies. CLT approach advocates for the utilization of communication or interaction as the primary means and ultimate objective in the acquisition of a second or foreign language. The purpose of this effort is to improve students' language skills through activities that encourage interpersonal cooperation, such as group or pair work, as well as role-plays and dramatizations that mimic real-world situations and locations. Additionally, it's crucial that the teacher uses the target language with fluency and appropriateness while offering a variety of materials and assignments that help with real-world scenarios (Celce-Murcia, 2001).

In employing CLT, a wide array of methods and techniques are possible. There exists a certain degree of consensus regarding the attributes requisite to warrant the designation of "CLT." Wesche and Skehan (2002) contend that the following holds true:

- Activities necessitate recurrent interactions among learners or other interlocutors to disseminate information and resolve issues.

- Use of genuine non-pedagogic literary works and communication exercises interconnected with actual real-world scenarios, frequently highlighting connections across written and spoken modalities and channels.
- Approaches that are learner-centered which acknowledges the learners' personal backgrounds, language requirements, and objectives while generally providing the learners with opportunities to exercise creativity and participate in instructional choices.

Doughty and Long (as cited in Brandl, 2008) listed some principles to serve as a guideline for implementing CLT practices. The first principle is the use of tasks as an organization principle. This is where TBLT converges with CLT. Some proponents of TBLT assert that it represents a logical extension of the CLT movement that was prevalent during the 1980s. However, the definition of TBLT remains somewhat unsettled, as noted by Littlewood (2007).

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) is a pedagogical approach that centers around communicative and interactive tasks, mandating learners to engage in meaningful communication and interaction (Nunan, 2004; Bygate, Skehan, & Swain, 2013). Task-based instruction prioritizes the significance of language meaning over its form. The present approach posits language as a vital instrument for students, enabling them to effectively engage with their surroundings through communicative means. The foremost objective is the attainment of communicative competence, which refers to the aptitude for employing language proficiently.

There are obvious parallels between CLT and TBLT. Both instructions employ a needs-based approach to content selection, place an emphasis on learning a language through interaction, incorporate real texts into the learning scenario, and

give learners opportunities to concentrate on both the language and the learning process.

Communicative Language Teaching Activities

According to the definition presented by Richards and Lockhart (1994), an activity denotes a purposeful task that has been deliberately chosen with the intention of attaining a specific educational objective. A communicative task is an essential part of curriculum preparation, implementation, and assessment (Nunan, 1991). Task-based language teaching (TBLT) selects syllabus content and instructional processes based on two main considerations: the communicative tasks that students are expected to perform beyond the classroom and the theoretical and empirical knowledge about the social and psycholinguistic factors that support language acquisition. Language should be taught through usage and communication, according to CLT. Since this is the case, communicative exercises ought to give students additional chances to "develop links with meaning that will later enable [them] to use this language for communicative purposes" (Littlewood, 1981, p. 8). These exercises are meant to improve the pupils' communication skills.

Littlewood (1981) asserts that communicative activities play a significant role in the educational domain by serving a variety of pedagogical goals, such as but not limited to providing comprehensive, task-based practice, boosting students' motivation, facilitating organic learning, and cultivating a welcoming learning environment.

Littlewood (1981) divides CLT into two categories. Figure 1 shows pre- and post-communicative activities.

- Pre-communicative activities help learners produce acceptable language for later communication. A communicative exercise could be used as the lesson's opening activity. This contains exercises and question-and-answer sessions.
- Post-communicative activities provide 'whole-task practice' to improve motivation, allow natural learning, and create context. Various social interaction activities, such as facilitated role-playing and dialogue sessions, simulated exercises, discussion forums, and facilitated debates, can aid in the development of communication skills.

Figure 1

Kinds of Communicative Language Teaching by Littlewood (1981)

Richards (2005) posits that proponents of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) have put forth three distinct genres of practice. These practices possess mechanical, semantic, and communicative practices. The discipline of mechanical practice entails the execution of tasks without deducing the underlying theoretical concepts. Semantic practice necessitates that students engage in

purposeful decision-making. The practice of communication entails the application of language within a genuine setting, wherein genuine and significant information exchange takes place.

Additionally, Pica et al. (1993) recognized a number of activities, such as opinion-exchange, jigsaw, information-gap, problem-solving, and decision-making tasks. They contend that tasks in which each interlocutor possesses a portion of the knowledge that must be exchanged in order to achieve a good conclusion are the most effective for promoting interaction and negotiation amongst language learners. In addition, Richards (2005) listed examples of other activity types that have been used in CLT.

- Task-completion activities require students to employ language resources to finish tasks like games, puzzles, and map-reading.
- Information-gathering activities require student to use their linguistic resources to collect information like student-conducted surveys and interview.
- Opinion-sharing activities include activities that let students compare values, opinions, or beliefs.
- Information-transfer activities are wherein students take information and represent it in a variety of ways. For instance, after reading directions on how to get from point A to point B, they might draw a map outlining the steps, or after reading information on a subject, they might portray it as a graph.
- Reasoning-gap activities enable students to learn new information from the given information. Creating a teacher's schedule, for instance, based on the class schedules that are provided.
- Role plays are tasks that allow students to improvise scenes or conversations using the material provided.

According to Paulston and Bruder (1976), role play should be spontaneous and imaginative rather than scripted, allowing learners to enhance their communication skills in simulated real-life situations. Sullivan (2000) explored the role of playfulness as a mediator in communicative language education and suggested that play serves as a means to transition learners into their zone of proximal development. In this context, learners engage in oral narrative activities that foster a playful atmosphere, enabling them to connect and communicate with teachers and peers. Through these activities, learners practice negotiating meaning and collaboratively generate knowledge.

Role of Teachers and Students in CLT Classrooms

In communicative language teaching classrooms, learners are expected to be an active participant. They must do exercises, use real resources, and also take after the teacher's communicative conduct to learn how to appropriately speak and connect with other peers. Thus, they become negotiators. Breen and Candlin (1980) noted that the role of joint negotiator in classroom procedures and activities is closely linked to the role of mediator between the self, the learning process, and the object of learning. This suggests that students should contribute actively in order to foster an interdependent learning style and receive the benefits of the learning process.

Breen and Candlin (1980) summarized the two roles of the teacher within CLT. The essential role is to empower the communication handle between all individuals inside the classroom, and between these individuals and the diverse works out and compositions. The second role is to act as a free part of the learning-teaching group. The latter part is closely related to the objectives of the essential part and develops from it.

Richards and Rodgers (2014) recognized three fundamental parts attributed to the instructor within the CLT framework. The instructor is perceived as a need analyst, a counselor and a group process manager. Need analyst must determine and respond to language needs. . As a counselor and facilitator, the instructor must utilize affirmation and input to communicate effectively. Finally, as a group manager, the instructor keeps an eye on, directs, and counsels the learners, but never steps in to fill in blanks or correct errors; this is done later, when the emphasis is on correctness.

Chinese as EFL Learners

China is one of the largest populations of English learners. Statista (2018) projected that China's online language education users would approach 30 million by 2019. Fundamentally, Chinese students studying English in China are regarded as English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners. They learn the English language in a non-English speaking country. According to Cowan et al. (1979), as cited in Boyle (2000), Chinese EFL see English as a vital tool that can help them access modern scientific and technological advancements and, secondarily, as a means of fostering trade and understanding with nations where English is a major language..In China, there is already a transition from memorization-driven teaching to communication-driven teaching (Ang, 2021). In this move, learners are expected to use and engage their language skills in interaction activities. It should be acknowledged that various factors exert an influence on the oral communication abilities of adult EFL learners.The ability of adult EFL learners to communicate effectively may be impeded by various factors, including their age, auditory medium, societal and cultural influences, and emotional disposition, as noted by Shumin (2002).

Furthermore, in order to be proficient in speaking, EFL students need to acquire grammatical competence, discourse competence, sociolinguistic competence, and strategic competence.

According to Shumin (2002), thorough analysis of the factors, conditions, and components underlying speaking proficiency is essential for effective EFL instruction. By providing ample language input, engaging in speech-promotion activities, and carefully considering the learner's context, teachers can support gradual improvement in English speaking proficiency.

Educational Technology Framework and Standards

Harris (2021) compiled a comprehensive list and summary of 16 globally developed frameworks and standards for educational technology, including the Learning Technology, ISTE Standards, UNESCO ICT Competency Framework for Teachers (UNESCO ICT-CFT), Common Sense Media K-12 Digital Citizenship Curriculum Scope and Sequence, Australian Curriculum ICT Capability, TPACK Framework, RAT Model, and the 4 Shifts Protocol. These frameworks and standards offer diverse perspectives on educational technology integration, digital citizenship, teacher competencies, curriculum development, and transformative practices in teaching and learning. They reflect the evolving nature of educational technology and cater to various educational contexts and needs.

Of all the standards and frameworks from Harris (2021), the UNESCO ICT-CFT and TPACK frameworks were considered for this study since both frameworks specify competencies to which teachers should ponder in their teaching along with the use of technology. In accordance with the UNESCO framework on Information and Communication Technology Competency Standards for Teachers (ICT-CFT)

(n.d), a total of 18 ICT competencies encompass the desired skillset that teachers should possess. Moreover, these competencies can be further classified into 64 distinct objectives. However, several parts of the framework lean more toward governmental or national interests in education than toward the skills of the instructors. For that reason, the researcher decided to withdraw from the said framework.

Looking closely at TPACK, an extended framework from Shulman's (1986) model of Pedagogical Content Knowledge, similar approaches were also encountered. These approaches share some similarities with the TPACK framework; yet Spector et. al (2014) highlighted its significant departures from that of Mishra and Koehler's (2006) TPACK. Listed below are the alternative approaches.

1. ICT-Related Pedagogical Content Knowledge (ICT-Related PCK)
2. Knowledge of Educational Technology
3. Technological Content Knowledge
4. Electronic Pedagogical Content Knowledge (ePCK)
5. Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge-Web (TPCK-W)

Alternative approaches built on Shulman's (1986) model, such as the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework, all agree that educators need to be knowledgeable in order to connect and transform content and pedagogy when new technologies emerge. As opposed to the TPACK framework, most of these approaches have not conceptualized technology as a separate area of knowledge. In TPACK, each knowledge is taken individually but also the interaction of these bodies of knowledge is considered with equal importance. Knowing the fact that technology advancement is accelerating, Mishra and Koehler (2006) forewarned that it would be problematic if technology would be solely treated as a separate

knowledge. Because of this, the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework has given teachers a sense of autonomy and transformed how they are perceived, especially in light of the quickly developing technology (Koehler & Mishra, 2008; Mishra, Koehler, & Kereluik, 2009). To be a great teacher, we must combine our topic knowledge with our understanding of how to teach. We must learn how to integrate technology into our content and pedagogy in order to establish a successful learning environment, especially as the emphasis on technology develops (McGrawHill, n.d.). Utilizing Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) as a theoretical framework for assessing teaching knowledge has the potential to yield consequential implications for the development of training and professional growth opportunities for both novice and experienced educators (Schmidt, et al., 2009).

TPACK framework is the most suitable for this study for several reasons. Firstly, it accommodates the diverse expertise levels of online English language educators, providing a clear framework for integrating content and pedagogical knowledge. Unlike other frameworks, TPACK is not limited to specific technologies or contexts, making it applicable even in non-academic settings like the chosen locale functioning as a Business Processing Outsource (BPO) industry. Lastly, the potential of the TPACK framework to inform the design of effective teacher education and professional development programs is highly valuable for end project of this study.

The TPACK survey measures teachers' understanding and integration of TPACK components, providing insights for training and professional development opportunities for educators (Schmidt et al., 2009). Nevertheless, the TPACK survey has been customized and adapted by researchers to suit their specific research

goals and contextual requirements. Few examples are of Schmidt et al. (2009), Niess et al. (2010), Archambault et al. (2012), and Gao et al. (2012).

In contrast to Mishra and Koehler (2008), Schmidt's TPACK study emphasizes instructors' assessments of their own TPACK in connection to certain subject areas. It tries to evaluate how educators use technology in the context of particular subject areas and instructional techniques. The survey asks open-ended and Likert-scale questions about teachers' knowledge of and opinions on pedagogy, technology, and content integration.

The TPACK study conducted by Mishra and Koehler, on the other hand, focuses more comprehensively on the preparation and growth of pre-service teachers for the incorporation of technology across several subject areas. Without putting a lot of emphasis on particular curriculum areas, it evaluates their self-perceived TPACK competencies and confidence in using technology in teaching and learning.

In this particular study, Schmidt et al.'s (2009) TPACK survey was chosen. Schmidt's TPACK survey emphasizes the interplay between knowledge domains and teachers' perceptions of their own TPACK within specific subject areas and instructional practices, contributing to a deeper understanding of technology integration in teaching (Schmidt et al., 2009).

TPACK Framework

The Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework is a pedagogical approach aimed at supporting educators in assimilating technology into their classroom delivery. To effectively implement this approach, educators must possess a comprehensive understanding of the content to be taught, the appropriate

pedagogical strategies to be employed, and a clear awareness of the available technological resources. Mishra and Koehler (2006) introduced the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework, which encompasses seven distinct categories of knowledge relevant to the effective integration of technology into educational practices. These categories are: Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), Content Knowledge (CK), Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK), Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK), Technological Content Knowledge (TCK), and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK). The efficacy of the TPACK framework has been demonstrated in providing apt guidance to educators with respect to integrating the domains of content, pedagogical strategies, and technological knowledge (Niess, 2008). Figure 2 shows the TPACK framework.

Figure 2

TPACK Framework

Technological Knowledge (TK) encompasses the comprehension and utilization of computer software and hardware, as well as presentation equipment, such as presentation documents, and other technologies, specifically within educational settings. The concept of technological knowledge (TK) encompasses the capacity to acclimate and assimilate novel technological innovations. The preservation of this capability necessitates consideration in light of ongoing advancements and technological evolutions (Agustini et al., 2019). Examples are the ability to troubleshoot, install, update software; understand the function of different software and hardware.

The acquisition of Content Knowledge (CK) fosters a deeper level of comprehension and expertise within distinct academic domains or areas of study. CK exhibits variations at distinct levels, as exemplified by variances in Primary and Secondary Schools. It is anticipated that an educator possesses a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter in order to effectively instruct and educate. The concept of conceptual knowledge (CK) bears significance as it serves to establish the distinctive cognitive frameworks inherent to particular fields of inquiry across various investigations (Agustini et al., 2019). As an example for this study, teachers are expected to master different conversational topics such as favorites, weather, choices, current events and so on; and teachers should have good knowledge on language forms such as English language grammar.

Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) refers to the holistic objective of acquiring knowledge that is tailored to the act of teaching. In order to successfully manage and organize teaching and learning activities to attain expected learning objectives, it is essential for educators to cultivate a range of requisite competencies. This corpus of knowledge encompasses a comprehensive understanding of the affordances and

challenges that are inherent in online classrooms, the critical role that student motivation plays therein, as well as effective methodologies of learning assessment. It is to be noted that this list is not exhaustive. Agustini et al. (2019) assert that pedagogical knowledge (PK) encompasses a breadth of teaching methodologies, as well as the ability to effectively design and structure classroom activities in a manner that promotes optimal conditions for student learning and knowledge acquisition.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK), a term that refers to the assertion made by Shulman (1986), states that effective teaching involves more than just a distinct understanding of pedagogy and content (Rosyid, 2016; Goradia, 2018). PCK acknowledges that various pedagogical approaches are more suitable for specific content areas. PCK is more than just being a content expert or knowing general pedagogical standards; it is an awareness of the reciprocal influences between content and pedagogy. Examples of this include having the knowledge of what questions to ask, when to ask them, and how to ask them in the context of an activity that involves exchanging opinions.

Technological Content Knowledge (TCK) pertains to the knowledge that arises from the bidirectional relationship between technology and content (Agustini et al., 2019). The development of technology has had a huge impact on our knowledge and has introduced innovative notions in the area of material presentation that were previously impossible. Example activities are using Google maps to discuss direction or travel plans; creating an interactive board game for discussion-leading questions in an online setting.

Technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK) emphasizes how closely pedagogy and technology are related. The acquisition of this knowledge permits an understanding of which technical instruments are appropriate for achieving

educational goals, so empowering educators to choose the equipment that is most practical in accordance with a particular pedagogical style. Technology enables unique teaching strategies that are easily deployed in schools, claim Agustini et al. (2019). Examples are using online graphics and video clips to increase learning motivation, using online translators to aid language barrier and incorporating sound effects during the session to increase learner's interest.

The term "technological pedagogical content knowledge" (TPACK) refers to the synthesis and integration of knowledge from a number of disciplines, including technological knowledge, content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, technological content knowledge, and technological pedagogical knowledge. Its main objective is to investigate how technology might be used appropriately and successfully to assist pedagogical goals in particular circumstances, with the long-term objective of promoting effective teaching and learning. Every element of the knowledge domain defines a demand and the importance of these characteristics in the pedagogical setting. However, successful teaching involves more than just each component. Teachers with Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) combine technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge to design student learning (Agustini et al, 2019). To cite an example, it is a teacher who is able to use an auxiliary camera and extra software in presenting a customized interactive board game in teaching greetings (How are you?) in an online set-up; using Tic-Tac-Toe to increase interest in teaching conversational starter topics through PowerPoint and manipulating it in an online set-up.

The Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework serves as a theoretical concept utilized by both researchers and educators to assess the preparedness of prospective and practicing teachers in terms of effectively

integrating technology into their teaching practices. TPACK has an impact on teachers because of the interaction of technology, pedagogy, and underlying content. As a result, teachers have tremendous challenges in terms of changing technology, pedagogy, topic matter, and the modern classroom environment. Curriculum development should involve more teachers. (Ay et al, 2016; Cetin & Erdogan, 2018;Chai, et.al, 2011; Lestari, 2015; Puspitarini & Sunaryo, 2013; Rosyid, 2016; Savec, 2017;)

The TPACK framework is a useful theory and concept for educators and researchers in measuring the readiness of teachers to teach effectively with technology. The TPACK survey has the potential to produce outcomes with significant implications for the provision of instructional training and professional growth opportunities for educators across all levels of experience.

TPACK and English as Foreign Language Teaching

Undeniably, TPACK studies are widely available. Some of these focused on assessing the teacher's understanding of TPACK while some were on the assessment of the teacher's TPACK. Examining teacher's TPACK is also evident in various disciplines especially in Math (Erdogan & Sahin, 2010; Jang & Tsai, 2013; Mutlouglu,2012), Science (Jang &Tsai, 2013; Mai & Hamzah, 2016), and Computer Education (Karaca, 2015). However, there are few on language teaching; and it is rare to find studies related to online language teaching.

Tai and Chuang (2012) posited a conceptual framework entitled the "TPACK-in-Action model", designed to facilitate the integration of technology into language classrooms among proficient English instructors in Taiwan. They created a workshop on computer-assisted language learning to build the TPACK competency of in-

service English instructors in five steps: modeling, analysis, demonstration, application, and reflection. Through this curriculum, English teachers who are currently in the classroom learn how to use technology while making pedagogical choices. Additionally, they worked out how to apply the knowledge they gained in the workshop to their classroom instruction.

At a Turkish university's Department of Foreign Language Education, which provided a four-year undergraduate program in English Language Teacher Education, Koçolu (2009) performed a study on 27 aspiring EFL teachers. The goal was to examine technical pedagogical subject understanding from the perspective of Turkish preservice EFL instructors. The study's findings showed that preservice teachers' TPACK may be improved and practiced with the help of computer-assisted language learning courses.

Through design-based research, Ansyari (2012) created a professional development curriculum for technology integration. Twelve English professors took part. The results showed that all participants had positive experiences with the TPACK professional development workshops; however, it was determined that there was room for growth in terms of time, technical exploration, and student involvement. Kurt et al. (2013) created a 12-week TPACK development program to assess the TPACK development of 22 Turkish preservice English teachers in Turkey. During this time, the pre-service teachers were introduced to the TPACK framework, and they built technical resources, participated in collaborative technology discovery, developed lessons that integrated technology, and taught in a real classroom environment. The study's conclusions show that pre-service English teachers' TK, TCK, TPK, and TPACK scores increased statistically significantly from the start to the finish.

In terms of technology and pedagogical content competence, 596 teachers who delivered their instruction online were studied by Archambault and Crippen (2009). The study's findings indicated that while participants knew a lot about educational subject, they lacked confidence when a technological element was introduced.

In their study, Lee and Tsai (2010) explored the perspectives of preservice teachers with regard to TPACK when utilizing web-based technology, and identified that experienced teachers exhibited reduced self-assurance in relation to technology. In their study, Koh and Sing (2011) directed their attention towards investigating the perspectives held by pre-service teachers with regards to their age, gender, and seven key components of TPACK. The findings indicated that the elements of TPACK exerted a notable influence on the TPACK perceptions of pre-service educators. Conversely, variables of a demographic nature, specifically age and gender, were not observed to hold a statistically significant impact on the aforementioned phenomenon. Furthermore, within the TPACK framework, it has been determined that the TPK and TCK factors serve as key determinants in shaping TPACK.

Previous research indicates that numerous factors are involved in the development of one's technological pedagogical content knowledge. Several authors have underscored the significance of gender with regard to TPACK. After conducting an examination of Koh et al.'s research in 2011, it was observed that gender had a significant impact on the extent of an individual's technological pedagogical content knowledge. The researcher drew an inference that the male population exhibits a superior level of TPACK in comparison to their female counterparts. Juhdi and Hamid (2010) discovered that the integration of technology in teaching and learning

was executed more proficiently by male educators as compared to their female counterparts. Furthermore, male educators exhibited a greater level of proficiency in all aspects of TPACK in comparison to their female counterparts.

Another element that affects TPACK is teaching experience. Both Juhdi and Hamid (2010) and Theerawajjanapa (2011) studies noted that teachers had more confidence integrating technology into their topic content as they gained more teaching. This shows similar results from the study of Adulyasas (2017). Other variables influencing TPACK were intrapersonal variables as self-efficacy, outcome expectation, and interest (Wisdom & Creswell, 2013), as well as fundamental computer knowledge, school support, and availability of computers in schools (Stewart, et al., 2013).

Community of Inquiry

To clearly and properly deliver support for online English teachers, Community of Inquiry is also adapted. There are a growing number of scholars who have used the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework aiming to improve the OLTE instruction. This is proven true in Gonzalez et al. 's (2015) studies as they reviewed databases containing related concepts to CoI and language learning, CoI and EFL/ESL, cognitive, social, teaching presences, and English teaching learning.

Shields (2012) posited that the Community of Inquiry (CoI) construct was initially introduced by early pragmatist scholars including Charles Sanders Peirce, John Dewey, and Jane Addams. The CoI is primarily represented by a team of people who have committed to working together to address a shared problem, challenge, or concern using a method akin to scientific inquiry. According to Dumitru (2012), the primary asset of this community lies in its capacity for knowledge

generation.

The framework known as the Community of Inquiry was developed by Garrison et al. (2001) in their scholarly work. It has been widely used in studies about successful online learning environments (Swan & Ice, 2010). It considers the sense of presence through teaching, social and cognitive components for a “successful higher educational experience” in a computer mediated environment (Garrison, et al., 2001, p. 87).

According to Anderson, Rourke, Garrison, and Archer (2001), teaching presence encompasses the design, facilitation, and direction of cognitive and social processes aimed at achieving meaningful and educationally valuable learning outcomes. Teaching presence consists of three essential elements, as identified by Akyol and Garrison (2008) and Anderson et al. (2001). The first element is instructional design and organization, which involves establishing the curriculum, setting time constraints, and structuring the learning environment to support effective instruction and learning. The second element is facilitating discourse, which entails guiding and moderating discussions among learners, identifying points of agreement or disagreement, promoting collaboration, and fostering critical thinking and reflection. The goal is to facilitate meaningful interactions and promote deeper understanding among learners. The third element is direct instruction, which involves activities such as posing questions, providing explanations, giving feedback, and ensuring learners' comprehension and engagement. Instructors actively guide and support learners' cognitive processes through direct instruction. Together, these three elements of teaching presence play a crucial role in creating an effective and engaging online learning environment where instructors assume a central role in designing, facilitating, and directing the learning process.

According to Garrison et al. (2001), learners have the ability to construct and validate meaning through continuous reflection and discourse within a critical community of inquiry. This process is known as cognitive presence. Garrison and Arbaugh (2007) further describe cognitive presence as consisting of four levels. The first level is the triggering event, which involves the initial identification of issues or problems that require further inquiry. The second level is exploration, where learners collaboratively investigate the identified issues through critical discourse and examination. The third level is integration, which involves the construction of meaning and the synthesis of ideas and perspectives. Garrison et al. (2000, 2001) suggest that the later phase of cognitive presence exhibits a higher cognitive level compared to the earlier phase. This progression reflects the deepening of understanding and the development of critical thinking skills as learners engage in sustained inquiry and reflection.

Social presence, one of the key elements, refers to an online learner's ability to engage socially and emotionally with other participants and perceive them as authentic individuals within a community of inquiry (Garrison et al., 2000). Social presence can be further broken down into three elements, as identified by Rourke et al. (2001). The first element is affectiveness, which involves learners expressing both common and unique emotions within the online learning environment. The second element is open communication, which entails responding to others and their contributions in a meaningful and interactive manner. The third element is group cohesion, which involves group members developing and sustaining a sense of commitment and belonging to the learning community.

The Col model promotes collaborative active learning, instructor presence for content curation and facilitating social and cognitive presence, participation in peer

supervision and professional learning networks, and the development of metacognition and self-reflection. It is described as a learning group dedicated to active knowledge building and the gradual development of disciplinary discourse community language and skills. (Shea & Bidjerano, 2010).

The Community of Inquiry and Quality Matters instruments were used in a study by Swan et al. (2014) to enhance completely online courses in a Teacher Leadership program. The Col framework was utilized to enhance learning, and the QM framework was used to assess course design. Since each instrument measures a distinct component and has the potential to improve learning outcomes, they discovered that utilizing both instruments together actually enhances learning.

A notable study is conducted by Shin (2008) which made use of the Col framework to redesign her online courses. Over 60 English teaching experts from 29 different countries in North Africa, the Middle East, Central Asia, and Southeast Asia participated in the study to find out what makes an effective online learning environment. In order to compare two implementations of the identical online teacher training course in 2004 and 2005, this qualitative study used a concurrent layered approach. The following are some recommendations for OLTE instructors from Shin's (2008) conclusion.

- Using problem-solving methodology in the discussion forum to encourage members to contribute concepts that can lead them to an application (the resolution phase in the Practical Inquiry model)
- Using starter-wrapper strategy to put the students in command of the debate while remaining available as the instructor to assist them as needed. Internet accessibility must be taken into account for this assignment.

- Being aware of cultural differences by employing a pedagogy that is culturally inclusive
- Being adaptable because children might experience issues with internet connectivity

Chen (2012) also adopted the Community of Inquiry framework as a tool in order to study practices at the University of Southern California's online TESOL teacher education program. The study looked at how instructors and students perceived the pros and cons of an online TESOL teacher preparation program as well as the traits of successful participants. Despite the difficulties they experienced with technological problems, the program's results showed that students and instructors are usually delighted with it.

A recent study from Rodriguez (2016) explored students and instructors' perceptions of effective pedagogical practices in OLTE courses. She adopted Col survey as the main instrument to connect best practices in online environments and desirable instruction for SLTE. The study included participation from 125 students and 18 instructors from non-credit certificate programs, professional development initiatives, and post-secondary credit courses in Online Teacher Education (OLTE). Notably, educational institutions in the United States offered the majority of these programs. The findings of the study suggested that currently adopted pedagogical practices are perceived favorably. Nonetheless, the use of online communication as a means to facilitate social interaction is perceived to be lacking in effectiveness. Additionally, the research's utilization of surveys and interviews revealed opportunities for enhancing instructional methodologies.

The synergy between TPACK and Col is not a novelty since this has taken shape in few literatures (Bath & Bourke, 2011, Hokanson et al, 2015; Otrell-Cass,

2015). Since this paper aims to provide a training program for online English teachers, TPACK aspects will be utilized as its content; whereas, CoI will be used as a basis for designing learning strategies and learning activities that would promote higher levels of learning for their TPACK knowledge. This is to better tailor a course that is well-suited to their needs, context, and beliefs.

Perhaps, the employment of CoI in determining the effective practices specially tailored for online English teachers may increase teacher's participation. Kennedy (2015) conducted a study which found that online teachers expressed a willingness to engage in both formal and informal professional development activities. However, the study also revealed that their actual participation rates in these development opportunities were lower for both types of programs. This affirms Simpson's (2012) claim that the "fundamental weakness" of distance education is the dropout rate (p.6) as it is 10%-20% higher than in face-to-face courses (Herbert, 2006). Recent studies have attempted to comprehend the causes, solutions, and contributing elements of the declining student retention rate in online courses (Bawa, 2016; Christensen & Spackman, 2017; Willging & Johnson, 2009).

Nevertheless, research indicates that faculty workloads and personal commitments are the main reasons why participation in development programs suffers (Brooks, 2010; Cook et al., 2009). However, Kennedy's (2015) research indicates otherwise. Some of the respondents in her study called for 'more training and support [to] be offered for adjunct online faculty and that part-time faculty ought to be included in course development decision-making' (p.74). Also, the results in her study indicated that on average, female online faculty found informal and formal professional development more useful compared to males, and they participated more in informal professional development. Online instructors may have preferences

on the design and content of a course, which may influence their assessment of a course's usefulness.

Instructional Design Models

The end goal for this study is to design a training course for online English teachers. The training course's content and delivery must be structured so that students can efficiently store and retain information.

For this goal to be realized, it is essential that an instructional design model is observed. Instructional design is the process used in creating instructional materials that are effective and meaningful to learners (Athuraliya, 2021). Instructional designers have two primary functions:(1) to analyze learning needs and (2) to systematically develop improved learning experiences (May, 2018).

Instructional design models enable designers to visualize the training need and break down the process of designing training material into a series of actions (CommLab India Bloggers, 2016). Models provide guidelines to ensure that training addresses the learning objectives and meets the desired expectations. Various instructional design models have been proposed in the literature (Kurt, 2015). With an array of models available, it is a challenge to pick the right one. Yet, a good designer should be able to move from one to the other to ensure that a specific need is met (Mahler, n.d. as cited in Burnham, 2019). Furthermore, Allen (Allen, & Sites, 2012) stated that today's finest model is one that is effective for an organization. Hence, an instructional designer is not only knowledgeable on each model but also sensitive to the challenges and affordances each model could bring to its clients and/or company.

In this study, the selected approach for adoption consists of the ADDIE Model,

encompassing Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation, as well as the SAM (Successive Approximation Model). ADDIE and SAM are tools for eLearning content development as they influence teaching styles as well.

ADDIE is an acronym for Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate. ADDIE comprises five stages, and the results of each phase are used as input for the subsequent stage (May, 2018). The five phases of the ADDIE model provide a dynamic, flexible roadmap for designing training and performance tools. The identification of the learner's existing knowledge and abilities, the learning environment, and the instructional goals and objectives all occur during the analysis phase. Discussions also include delivery options, learning restrictions, and audience characteristics. The design process takes into account learning objectives, assessment instruments, activities, content, subject matter analysis, lesson planning, and media selection. It should be methodical and accurate. All components of the instructional design plan must be meticulously carried out with a strong emphasis on attention to detail in order to guarantee the best results. During the development phase, the developers construct and put together the content assets that were created during the design phase. The project is reviewed, and any comments received is taken into consideration during the revision process that follows. Programmers work on the creation and/or fusion of different technologies. The ADDIE model's evaluation step includes a number of tests designed to assess domain-specific, criterion-referenced items and give users the chance to offer comments. Every stage of a process includes formative evaluation, whereas summative evaluation evaluations are specific to the project's domains (ADDIE Model, 2022).

Although ADDIE is a widely accepted model and the archetype of current

instructional designs, it is criticized as being rigid and too linear in nature (Burnham, 2019). As a direct response to the inadequacy of the ADDIE model, Michael Allen (2012) developed the Successive Approximation Model (SAM). It is a streamlined version of the ADDIE Model with the goal of gathering data and producing usable models early in the process. For the production of courses, this model uses a recursive rather than a linear procedure (Successive Approximation Model, n.d.). It is the most commonly used instructional design methodology for rapid development. (ELM Learning, 2020). SAM is divided into three phases namely, Preparation, Iterative Design and Iterative Development. The Preparation phase starts with gathering all project information and background; the content and scope of this phase will vary widely depending on the project or course. The "Savvy Start" emphasizes brainstorming, drawing, and prototyping, as well as involving as many interested people as possible as you produce the material: coworkers, mentors, and, if you're lucky, students. The Iterative Design phase involves designing and prototyping the material so that interested parties can evaluate it. The final prototype is fully developed and put into use throughout the iterative development stage. Following its initial use, it can be reviewed and may be necessary to repeat the process from beginning to end.

Both models have their own strengths and weaknesses. ADDIE model is beneficial because it is methodical. Since it has been around for many years, there are guidelines on what to include in each step as accounted by other practitioners. This will profoundly help novice instructional developers, including the researcher of this study. Nevertheless, SAM's iterative and collaborative aspects are helpful points to consider in designing a training course for online English teachers whose opinions are much valued.

To begin designing, identifying the gaps in knowledge, skills and other pertinent background information related to the context is a fundamental key in analyzing learning needs and developing learning materials. Conducting needs analysis, or needs assessment, has been used in the language teaching field to further develop course materials, learning activities, tests, etc. Recent literature has highlighted the significance of conducting needs analysis in English for Academic Purposes, English for Business Purposes, and English for Specific Purposes. Scholars including Boshier and Smalkoski (2002), Brown et al. (2007), Cowling (2007), Edwards (2000), and Jasso-Aguilar (2005) have made notable contributions to this area of research.

The process of needs analysis (NA) involves methodical gathering and examination of both subjective and objective data. This is done in order to establish and verify sound curriculum objectives that effectively meet the language learning needs of students, while considering contextual factors such as institutional influences on the learning and teaching environment (Brown, 1995). According to certain studies (Boshier & Smalkowski, 2002; Chaudron et al., 2005), curriculum development is the optimum place to apply a requirements analysis.

Recognizing and acknowledging the requirements of learners is an influential instrument of facilitation, which has the potential to establish a collaborative relationship between instructors and students at the initiation of any educational endeavor (Minderhuot, n.d.). A learner's needs are the gap between his or her desired outcomes from the learning experience and his or her existing level of knowledge, competence, and motivation (Noessel, 2003). Through needs analysis, learners, teachers and course developers can be informed on the existing gaps between learner's level of knowledge and competency and the learning program,

which the learner would take.

An article from Moeni (2008) reported that needs is a missing part in teacher training programs. He stated that training programs are deemed to be highly efficient and impactful when they are built upon a comprehensive examination of the needs and requirements of the educators. When there is a distinction between various groups of instructors in teacher training programs, teachers are more likely to participate in and follow additional professional development programs with higher excitement and interest. It concluded that “professional development strategies of the future should be sensitive to teachers’ needs as professionals and to related solutions supported by ICT” (Moeni, 2008, p. 8).

A nation-wide survey conducted by Yan (2005) among teachers of English at tertiary level revealed an urgent development need among university teachers of English in China. The study discovered a disparity between the real requirements for effective classroom instruction and the perceived needs for development among teachers using needs analysis. Yan (2005) also believed that a lack of pedagogical content knowledge and language learning theory components in their teacher education curriculum may have well contributed to the discrepancy between teachers beliefs and their classroom performance.

Nugraha et.al’s (2018) study discussed the value of needs analysis in the e-learning of Indonesian as a Second or Foreign Language. Through the utilization of NA, those responsible for developing the curriculum were able to acquire pertinent information regarding various aspects of the learning process including the linguistic backgrounds of the learners, their preferred learning styles, their receptivity to particular teaching strategies, as well as their individual motivations for participating in the e-learning language program. Additionally, the degree of the learners’

commitment to the program was also assessed using this methodology. Through the utilization of NA, it was determined that an issue existed with the development of the curriculum for the e-learning program, as a result of the non-categorized competency profile and the imprecise level placement. The study also highlighted the importance of the NA process in e-learning program development as it helps in designing the planning, implementation and assessment of the learning program.

Both Richards and Hino (1983) and Kusumoto (2008) conducted needs analysis to identify necessary training for foreign teachers teaching English and Japanese homeroom teachers respectively. The aforementioned studies have produced important information about the evolution of teacher-training programs in Japan, making them useful for the improvement of curriculum developers and educators.

The importance and value of a needs analysis in language and language training programs is widely evident in TESOL literature. However, related studies on needs analysis and teacher's training programs are addressed to the benefits of offline teachers. The analysis of needs of online teachers and their rapidly evolving contemporary context is a wide-open ground to explore.

Summary of the Related Literature and Studies

Online education is a dynamic learning environment that appeals to both language learners and researchers. Its convenience and effectiveness have attracted language learners to undertake. Researchers are also interested in investigating the effectiveness, affordances, obstacles, and a variety of other aspects in online education due to its rapid advancement in the field, particularly in second language instruction.

On the other hand, the teacher's role, which is vital in any form of education, is becoming more crucial as they step into online learning contexts. Researchers have emphasized the significance of professional development to prepare online teachers. Although teacher education has long been accessible, researchers have continued to explore and understand the dynamics of online learning and teaching through acclimatization. Their efforts have contributed significant recommendations and guidelines in tailoring training programs for online teachers. Nevertheless, there are still reports of online language educators who are struggling in their teaching environment. Reasons could be inadequacy of training programs and lack of standards in OLTE courses.

Researchers in the field of CALL have also supported in designing training programs for online language teachers. TPACK is a widely utilized framework in measuring teacher's performance in integrating technology in teaching. Another outstanding effort was the identification of necessary skills that online language teachers must possess. With the proposed online language teaching skill frameworks of Hampel and Stickler (2005) and Compton (2009), there are researchers (Sun, 2011; Berber-McNeill, 2011) who employed these in their own studies in an effort to understand the issues and development of these proposed teaching skills, and also how to sustain the growth of these competencies. Yet, it must be recognized that the participants in these studies had formal language teacher education, teaching experiences and, eligibility to teach in a conventional set-up before they transitioned to online teaching.

In addition, CALL researchers have employed Col in order to gather information from its direct users (i.e. instructors and learners) on the effective pedagogical practices in OLTE course hoping to emphasize the strengths and

revamp weak teaching practices for the future training programs. However, most of these studies are implemented in North American education institutions. There is still a great deal to be done with the help of CoI in determining teaching practices that the in-service online teachers in the Philippines find effective. This is mainly because the quality of courses or the learning materials offered to these teachers might not have been assessed yet.

Conducting needs analysis, or needs assessment, has been used in the language teaching field to further develop course materials, learning activities, tests, etc. As needs analysis was used to identify teacher's needs, researchers were able to inform course developers on the necessary training needed by the teachers and the factors that should be considered by the training facilitators. However, these studies were addressed for conventional teachers. It is scarce to find studies that look into the needs of online teachers, particularly the online language educators.

Online English education in the Philippines is one of the flourishing industries that provide decent livelihood to many Filipinos. This magnetizes many citizens in the country to apply despite their ineligibility as teachers. Nevertheless, institutions have supported them through free training. Due to the inaccessibility and confidentiality of the nature of these training, there is no data how these trainings are developed, and whether these address the teacher's actual needs.

Hence, this study would like to unravel their training needs based on their TPACK level. This will also acknowledge online language teacher's previous study and work experiences, training expectations and recommendations. Outlining training contents relevant and supportive to the actual needs of online language teachers will be done guided by the TPACK and instruments of this study. Additionally, engaging teaching approaches preferred by online English educators will be leveraged to meet their

training needs using Col. Finally, ADDIE and SAM instructional designs would lend us an idea on how to organize the content and delivery of the training program effectively. All of these would enable the study to design a training program that is real, meaningful and effectual for online English teachers.

Figure 3
Conceptual Framework

The presented conceptual framework focuses on the development of a training program tailored for online English language teachers. This program is designed to address the specific needs and requirements of these teachers, taking into consideration their demographic profiles and communicative teaching roles and activities. The framework recognizes the influence of online English language teachers' responses to their Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) level, their preferences for pedagogical practices based on the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework, and their recommendations for improving their TPACK skills. By integrating these key factors, the conceptual framework serves as a roadmap for the development of a comprehensive and effective training program for online English language teachers. The conceptual framework places significant emphasis on addressing the specific needs, preferences, and recommendations of the online English language teachers. This focus is crucial to ensure the successful integration of technology and the improvement of their instructional practices within the online teaching environment. By considering and addressing these key aspects,

the framework aims to facilitate effective technology integration and support the continuous professional growth of the online English language teachers.

Definition of Terms

Online Language Teaching – teaching English language to speakers of other languages such as Korean, Chinese, Japanese, Russian through a synchronous computer-mediated communication form such as video- or audio-conferencing virtual class

Online Teacher Education – courses offered that are conducted online specifically for individuals pursuing education career

In-service Language Teacher Education – any courses, may it be as preparatory or professional development course, offered to the practicing online English teachers

Online English Teachers – the Filipino citizens, who are currently teaching English language online to speakers of other languages such as Koreans, Japanese, Chinese, and Russians

TPACK - an acronym for Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge, which is a technology integration framework that identifies three types of knowledge (technology, pedagogy and content) that educators need to combine for successful educational technology integration.

CoI - an acronym for Community of Inquiry that describes how learning occurs to a group of individuals

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the outline of research methods that were observed in the study. It details the participants or the requirements for inclusion in the study. Also, the project design process is summarized in tables to give an overview of the steps and reasons why some instructional design phases were omitted. Additionally, a description of the data collection tool and the steps taken to complete this study are provided. There is also a discussion on the methods used to analyze the data. Finally, the researcher declares to observe the research ethics for this study.

Research Design

To address the research questions, a sequential explanatory mixed methods approach was employed, involving a systematic progression from the collection and analysis of quantitative data to the subsequent collection and analysis of qualitative data. The qualitative results helped enrich the collected quantitative data of this study.

In the process of designing a training program, it is imperative to take into account the needs of the target population. However, attaining a substantial number of participants was challenging. In that case, integrating qualitative data with the quantitative survey can prove advantageous. Despite the restricted participant count, qualitative data has the potential to furnish extensive and meticulous insights from individual perspectives, facilitating a comprehensive grasp of the intricacies inherent in the research topic. By combining quantitative and qualitative methodologies, the study can benefit from the statistical rigor and generalizability of quantitative data and the profound understanding and contextual insights provided by qualitative data.

This comprehensive approach helps overcome the limitations of small sample size, leading to a more thorough understanding of the research phenomenon and ultimately supporting the development of an effective training program. Also, it is essential to use various methods to explore more data sources to carry out an in-depth study in the CALL field (Zhou, 2018).

The survey was conducted to gather quantitative data, enabling a statistical analysis of online English language teachers' TPACK level. After that, open-ended questions and follow-up online interviews were done to gather the qualitative data. This was done to aid in the understanding and explanation of the results drawn from the quantitative data. Open-ended interview questions were prepared based on the findings of the quantitative analysis, most especially on the unusual and intriguing figures. The quantitative results gathered from the TPACK Likert survey were used as the basis for the training program's content; also, quantitative data gathered from the Col Likert survey were used as the mechanism for how the course will be delivered. In addition, the qualitative data obtained from the interviews were used to explain why the proposed contents and delivery were indicated. As prescribed by the instructional design model for this study, the data collected was analyzed in order to carry out and support the subsequent phases accordingly.

A summary is presented in Table 1.

Table 1*Summary of Research Design*

Research Question	Data Input	Instrument	Analysis
1. What is the TPACK level of online English language teachers?	Quantitative (Appendix 5 & 6)	Adapted TPACK survey and Albrahim's online teaching task (Appendix 1)	Descriptive statistics
2. Is there a relationship between OLT demographic variables and their TPACK level?	Quantitative (Appendix 4, 5 & 6)	Demographics and TPACK survey(Appendix 1)	Descriptive Statistics
	Qualitative (Appendix 9 &12)	Open-ended Questions (Appendix 1) Interview (Appendix 11)	Coding Analysis (Appendix 10)
3. What are the pedagogical practices in their language teacher education training that online English teachers find effective?	Quantitative (Appendix 7 & 8)	Adapted Col survey (Appendix 1)	Descriptive statistics
	Qualitative (Appendix 9 &12)	Open-ended Questions (Appendix 1) Interview (Appendix 11)	Coding Analysis (Appendix 10)
4. Based on their TPACK level and Col preferences, what training content and pedagogical guidelines should be provided to teachers?		All gathered quantitative and qualitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coding Analysis • Needs Analysis • Instructional Design Road Map

Table 2*Steps in Designing the Training Program*

Instructional Design	Phase	Task
ADDIE	Analyze	The researcher as the instructional designer gathered the pertinent data and analyzed them to determine the instructional needs, environment, opportunities and constraints.
ADDIE	Design	The instructional designer wrote the learning objectives and determined the instructional strategies that will be used to achieve those objectives. A simple outline or prototype was created.
SAM	Iterative Design	Before proceeding to ADDIE's third step, the created prototype was shared to a focus group wherein they examined and further designed the prototype. A snowball sampling was done to create the focus group which includes four online English teachers. Together with the focus group, the instructional designer modified the design according to the discussion made.
ADDIE	Develop	The instructional designer revised, reviewed and finalized the content of the training course as its Alpha version.
SAM	Iterative Development	Instead of implementing it right away as advised in ADDIE, the final output was rolled out to the focus group as the first evaluators of the course. Their feedback was adapted for the revised course material, Beta version.

The study followed the steps outlined in Table 2, integrating elements from the ADDIE and SAM processes while excluding specific steps. The comparison of the preparation phase in SAM and ADDIE's first phase highlighted similarities in their data analysis and brainstorming approaches. However, ADDIE's initial phase was favored due to its emphasis on establishing a solid foundation for the project. The comprehensive analysis conducted during this phase is essential for ensuring project success and alignment with the desired outcomes. In addition, the implementation and evaluation phases of the ADDIE model were not included due to several challenges. The researcher acknowledged that implementing the proposed training program was beyond the scope of the study, which led to the exclusion of the evaluation phase. Furthermore, time constraints significantly limited the application of these phases within the study's framework. These factors were carefully considered to maintain the research's focus and feasibility within the available time and resources.

Research Locale

The study was limited to the Philippines as it has become a rapidly rising online language education market source. The Philippines has been providing virtual language sessions to students in nearby nations like South Korea, China, and Japan, and even as far away as Russia. Upon this writing, there are more than 20 online teaching platforms in the Philippines offering decent online teaching careers for Filipinos regardless of their eligibility (Philippine Online ESL Jobs, n.d.). Since February 2020, specific platforms have experienced a significant increase in demand and usage (Reuters, 2020).

Online language teaching, one of the flourishing online jobs in the Philippines, has attracted many Filipinos to pursue a career. Its competitive salary and less rigid teaching qualification requirements have welcomed many individuals to apply despite the lack of teaching knowledge. However, the growing demand for catering to international students has left no option for online teaching companies to hire and train unprepared teachers continuously. Also, the call to disclose online teachers' qualifications and professional backgrounds (Xuejiao, 2019) has put growing pressure on some online language schools – pushing them to provide better training for their teachers.

Hence, the Philippines was deemed a suitable research locale for this study as it has a sizeable online teacher population who are all encouraged to participate in their company's training.

Participants

The study specifically targeted practicing online English teachers who met the following criteria: (1) teaching adult Chinese EFL learners to enhance conversation fluency, (2) conducting online classes through video- or audio-conferencing, (3) utilizing communicative language teaching activities, and (4) residing in the Philippines, establishing these criteria aimed to ensure that the participants shared a common teaching service and professional experience. Also, setting criteria helps to create a homogeneous sample, allowing for more meaningful comparisons and analyses of the data collected (Creswell, 2014; Johnson, 2014).

Initially, attempts were made to contact online English language schools for participant recruitment, but their lack of response led to adopting of a snowball sampling method. The researcher utilized the immediate network of colleagues and

acquaintances associated with online English language schools to recruit participants, leveraging social networks to identify individuals who met the study criteria. This approach ensured a focused and efficient recruitment process, targeting participants with the relevant qualifications and experiences. It also facilitated trust and rapport-building, increasing the willingness of referred individuals to participate and providing valuable insights. A verification process was implemented in the survey to filter out participants who did not meet the study criteria, ensuring the validity of the collected data. Despite the limitations of a restricted timeframe, the study gathered responses from a cohort of 15 online English teachers who satisfied the study criteria and actively participated in the survey. However, only a subset of 7 teachers (46.67%) expressed their willingness to partake in the subsequent phase, which involved interviews. Nonetheless, their voluntary involvement proved instrumental in providing valuable contributions to the study's findings.

While the sample size may be small, it is essential to note that results from a small sample are considered more valid when the population is homogeneous, as heterogeneity can impact the interpretability and validity of the findings (Canadian Audit and Accountability Foundation, n.d.). Homogeneous composition in focus groups is essential for effective group interaction and dynamics (Grønkjær et al., 2011). Common demographic attributes, cultural backgrounds, and relevant experiences among group members foster a sense of familiarity and safety, even among initially unfamiliar individuals (Grønkjær et al., 2011; Sim, 1998).

Instruments

A. Survey Questionnaire

The survey questionnaire employed in this study included various types of questions, such as verification, demographics, CLT teaching activities, adapted TPACK survey, adapted Col survey, and open-ended questions on participants' personal TPACK skills development and opinions on training online English language teachers. The survey was administered using the Google Forms platform, chosen for its ability to reach a geographically dispersed population of online English teachers. Additionally, it provides streamlined data management and analysis and facilitates swift response and immediate communication with participants (Adelia, 2021). The survey remained accessible for two weeks to accommodate the limited time frame of the study. The survey questionnaire can be found in Appendix 1. The survey questionnaire consisted of five sections.

1. Verification

Verification is critical in survey research to enhance the collected data's accuracy, reliability, and credibility. By verifying participants' qualifications or characteristics at the outset of the survey, researchers can effectively filter out individuals who do not meet the defined criteria, reducing the potential for biased or irrelevant data (Fowler, 2013). The implementation of a verification process serves to confirm the authenticity of respondents and their responses, ensuring that the data aligns with the research objectives and accurately represents the intended population. This verification mechanism strengthens the validity and trustworthiness of the research findings.

2. Demographics

Demographic information is crucial in educational research, providing valuable insights into participants' characteristics and backgrounds (Creswell, 2014). Age, gender, ethnicity, educational background, and socioeconomic status can help identify patterns, trends, and potential educational experiences and outcomes disparities. Demographic data are valuable in educational research due to the significant differences that often exist among different groups on essential issues (Alreck & Settle, 1995).

Demographic information, including age, gender, and contact details, is commonly collected in educational research. This study's demographic section also included questions about participants' employment, educational background, and technological skill level. The inclusion of participants' current ESL company affiliation served to validate their eligibility as representatives of targeted online English language schools. Gathering this information ensured that participants met specific criteria for the study, contributing relevant experience and insights from their work within the online English language school context. Participants' educational backgrounds also helped provide context for their perspectives, experiences, and expertise in the subject matter. Assessing participants' technological skill level is valuable for effectively understanding their ability to use technology tools and resources in instructional practices. This knowledge informed the development of targeted interventions and support strategies to enhance participants'

technological competence and promote the successful integration of technology in their teaching practices. The participants' technological proficiency was assessed and classified into three distinct levels: enthusiastic beginner, reluctant user, comfortable user, and confident explorer. These categories are derived from previous research studies that employed the TPACK survey to assess participants' technological competence in educational contexts. However, the specific definitions and interpretations of these terms were not clearly delineated in previous research. As a result, for the purpose of this study, the participants themselves provided input on two technological proficiency categories. Furthermore, participants were allowed to voluntarily supply their email addresses, indicating their willingness to engage in future interview sessions. By gathering these demographic details, the study established a comprehensive understanding of the participant's backgrounds and qualifications, enhancing the academic rigor and contextual relevance of the research findings.

3. Adapted TPACK Survey

The TPACK survey utilized in this study was adapted from Schmidt et al. (2009). Apart that Schmidt's survey has demonstrated strong reliability and validity in previous research studies (Schmidt et al., 2009), its version has clearly distinguished each body of knowledge and the interaction of the knowledge. It emphasizes teachers' perceptions of their own TPACK concerning specific subject areas. It aims to assess how teachers integrate technology into their pedagogical practices within the

context of specific content domains. This enabled an understanding of the real needs of the respondents in the study. For this study, only items 1-46 of the survey were included, excluding subject-specific items irrelevant to the study's context.

Additionally, 16 items from Albrahim's (2020) study, focusing on Social and Communication Skills, Technological Skills, Pedagogical Skills, and Content Skills, were incorporated, aligning with the study's objectives. The survey encompassed a total of 44 questions. The labels for each type of knowledge (i.e., PK, CK, TK, PCK, TCK, TPK, and TPACK) were presented in the survey form; however, questions were given by section in the survey design. To be precise and clear, "literacy," as reflected in the original survey, is changed to "English language teaching." The validation of the instrument was presented and approved by the thesis panelist during the thesis proposal defense.

4. Community of Inquiry Survey

The present study incorporates the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework, recognized for its role in promoting knowledge construction and enhancing instruction in language teacher education, as supported by Shin's (2008) research. To investigate the effective teaching practices perceived by online teachers in their training, a CoI survey was included in the questionnaire. This survey, originally developed by Arbaugh et al. (2008), has undergone rigorous validation with diverse student populations, as demonstrated by studies conducted by Swan et al. (2008) and Arbaugh et al. (2008). It consists of 34 items categorized into three dimensions: teaching presence (13 items), social presence (9 items), and

cognitive presence (12 items). Importantly, all items from the Col survey were included in the Online Language Teacher Education (OLTE) survey, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the constructs under investigation.

The participants in this study had already completed pre-service and in-service training in TESOL-related courses offered by their various employers before conducting this study. Their recollection of these prior training experiences likely influenced their understanding of best instructional practices. To ensure the reliability and validity of the study, careful attention was given to the survey design. The questionnaire incorporated open-ended questions to elicit detailed responses from the participants, enabling a deeper understanding of their training experiences and facilitating further exploration of the topic.

5. Open-Ended Questions

Participants in this study were provided with the opportunity to elaborate on their experiences as online English teachers through a series of open-ended questions. These questions were carefully developed based on the literature reviewed in the study. For the specific wording and details of the open-ended questions, please refer to Appendix 1.

B. Interview

A qualitative interview was conducted after the analysis of the survey. Additional questions were added to the list. It helped to focus the interview questions as other issues developed. The author created possible interview questions, but additional questions emerging from the survey analysis were also included. This was

also important to better comprehend the respondent's teaching and professional service background and to clarify issues emerging from previously gathered data.

The participants for the interview were the seven voluntary online English teachers who provided their contact details from the survey. The researcher would like the participants to feel secure throughout the interview; hence, they may opt for online video or audio-conferencing, depending on their preference. The researcher recognized that some respondents were reluctant to freely express themselves if their identity was exposed. Given the participants consent, interviews were audiotaped. It was then transcribed for analysis.

The experts were consulted for the content validity of the survey questionnaire, open-ended and interview questions. As suggested, TPACK and Col labels were removed from the survey but were presented by section in the questionnaire form. In addition, the open-ended and interview questions were rewritten into more precise and less-dense words. Five non-practicing online English language teachers also did the pilot testing of the survey questionnaire. It was suggested that sections 4-10 should have phrase starters on their headers to help them choose the proper response.

Data Gathering Procedure

Two data collection procedures were employed in this study: a web-based survey questionnaire administered to online English teachers and partially structured interviews conducted with volunteering online English teachers. The web-based survey questionnaire served as a means to gather quantitative data from a larger sample of participants, while the partially structured interviews allowed for an in-depth exploration of specific topics and the collection of qualitative data.

First, the researcher looked for potential online English language schools which (1) hire Filipino teachers, (2) offer one-to-one online audio- or video-conferencing English language teaching services to Chinese EFL students, and (3) provide pre- or in-service training for their teachers. A set of criteria was defined to ensure that target participants have a common teaching service and professional experience. Results obtained from a small sample are more valid when the population is homogeneous, as heterogeneity can impact the interpretability and validity of the findings (Canadian Audit and Accountability Foundation, n.d.). Three online language schools in the country that met the above criteria were approached through email to get their cooperation and approval in inviting their online English teachers to participate in the study. Appendix 2 contains the letter of intention, list of questions, and approval request sent through email to these companies.

In light of the unresponsiveness from the shortlisted companies, the researcher took the initiative to directly contact individuals who have previously or currently worked as online teachers for these companies. This approach aimed to establish communication and engage with potential participants. The participants were asked to complete the web-based survey questionnaire and were also requested to share the questionnaire link with their colleagues. The survey was accessible online for two weeks, taking into consideration the limited time available for the study. After the designated time frame, both quantitative and qualitative data from the survey responses were analyzed. The analysis involved identifying correlations, themes, and emerging issues. These findings were then used to inform the development of interview questions for further exploration.

Third, survey respondents, who provided an email address and volunteered for the interview phase, were contacted through email. Appendix 3 contained the

email asking them to respond to the form specifying their time available for the interview, mode of communication, and research ethics guidelines. It was an audio-recorded one-to-one interview through their preferred video-calling software (e.g., Zoom, Skype, Google Meet, Voov). The recording was transcribed for qualitative analysis.

Finally, quantitative and qualitative data were compared and presented. Quantitative results were supported and elaborated by the gathered qualitative data.

Data Analysis

In a study by Jita (2016), descriptive statistics were employed to determine the TPACK level of the respondents. For this study, the first research question aimed to find each participant's mean TPACK skill rating. To calculate the mean score, the researcher followed the guidance provided by Bluman (2019). The scores of each TPACK item were summed, resulting in a total score representing the participant's performance across all items. This total score was then divided by the number of items, yielding the average score or mean TPACK skill rating. This computation allowed for a quantitative representation of the participant's overall TPACK skill level based on their responses to the items.

Additionally, the study examined the mean of each TPACK category, including PK, TK, CK, PCK, TCK, TPK, and TPACK. For each category, the values of all the items within that category were aggregated and averaged as reported by the respondents. These descriptive statistical procedures, guided by Bluman (2019), enabled the researcher to assess the TPACK levels of the participants by obtaining average scores for both individual TPACK items and broader TPACK categories.

A combination of quantitative and qualitative data analysis methods was utilized to address the second research question. The quantitative data analysis involved applying descriptive statistics to explore any significant differences in TPACK levels based on various teacher demographic backgrounds, such as years of teaching experience, educational level, technological proficiency, gender, and age groups. Noteworthy findings from these quantitative analyses were incorporated into the interview questions. The qualitative data analysis involved coding the responses obtained from the interviews. In this study, a coding system was developed through content analysis, involving identifying and categorizing patterns and themes in the qualitative data. It provided a structured approach to analyzing qualitative data, ensuring consistency, objectivity, and transparency in the coding process, thereby enhancing the reliability and validity of the findings (Krippendorff, 2018).

A descriptive analysis was conducted to determine the mean scores for each presence within the Community of Inquiry framework to address the third research question. This analysis involved calculating the average scores for each item statement related to each presence. These mean scores provided quantitative insights into the participants' levels of presence in the Community of Inquiry. In addition to the quantitative analysis, the interview responses were transcribed and coded. A coding analysis was applied to the qualitative data to identify recurring themes, patterns, and perspectives. This qualitative approach allowed for a deeper exploration of the participants' experiences and provided a more comprehensive understanding of the research question. By combining the quantitative descriptive analysis and the qualitative coding analysis, the study aimed to comprehensively understand the participants' experiences and perspectives regarding the different presences within the Community of Inquiry framework.

To answer the fourth research question, quantitative and qualitative data gathered and analyzed for this study were consolidated and examined to design a training program tailored for online English language teachers. Quantitative data dictated the content and mechanisms of the training program. Qualitative data, on the other hand, served as the rationale and support for its design. Instructional design models adapted for this paper were observed.

Ethical Consideration

Most importantly, the researcher observed the guidelines indicated by the University of the Philippines Open University Institutional Research Ethics Committee (UPOU IREC). Initially, the respondents were informed about the purpose of the study. Their participation and the data collected were treated with utmost confidentiality and anonymity.

Chapter IV

FINDINGS AND RESULTS

This chapter reports the results of the data collected through web surveys and interviews. Data are analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. The research findings are presented in order to answer the research questions.

There were 15 online English language teachers who completed the web survey, and seven out of 15 participated in the voluntary online interview. Respondents' demographics and a summary of demographics are presented on the succeeding pages.

Table 3*Demographics per Respondents*

Respondent Number	Biological Gender	Age	Teaching Experience as Online English Language Teacher	Educational Attainment	Course/ Degree	Technological Skill
1	Female	31-40	1-3 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSEd - Science	Confident explorer
2	Female	31-40	4-6 years	Bachelor's Degree	BA in English	Comfortable user
3	Female	21-30	> 6 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSBA	Comfortable user
4	Female	21-30	< 1 year	Bachelor's Degree	BS Hospital Management	Confident explorer
5	Male	31-40	> 6 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSEd – Business Technology	Confident explorer
6	Female	21-30	1-3 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSEd – English	Comfortable user
7	Female	31-40	1-3 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSEd – English	Confident explorer
8	Female	31-40	< 1 year	Master's Degree	MBA	Comfortable user
9	Female	21-30	4-6 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSEd	Confident explorer
10	Female	31-40	< 1 year	Bachelor's Degree	BS Elementary Education	Comfortable user
11	Female	21-30	1-3 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSBA	Confident explorer
12	Female	31-40	1-3 years	Bachelor's Degree	BS Elementary Education	Confident explorer
13	Female	21-30	1-3 years	Master's Degree	ME – Guidance & Counseling	Comfortable user
14	Female	21-30	1-3 years	Bachelor's Degree	BS in Industrial Engineering	Comfortable user
15	Female	31-40	< 1 year	Bachelor's Degree	BS Elementary Education	Comfortable user

Table 4*Demographics Summary of Respondents*

		Number of Respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	1	3%
	Female	14	97%
Age	21-30 y.o.	7	47%
	31-40 y.o.	8	53%
Technological Expertise	Comfortable User	8	53%
	Confident Explorer	7	47%
Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	13	87%
	Master's Degree	2	13%
Course	Education Graduates	10	67%
	Non-education Graduates	5	33%
Years of Teaching Experience	<1 year	4	27%
	1-3 years	7	47%
	4-6 years	2	13%
	>6 years	2	13%

Context of the Respondents

The researcher emailed three top online language schools in the Philippines to verify and better understand the instructional environment of the teachers. Unfortunately, there was no response. However, those who participated in the interview openly discussed their workplace conditions.

Seven respondents volunteered for the interview. They were from the three online language schools in the country. They were provided a list of job postings to confirm their company's hiring criteria. According to the educators, these employment criteria were still valid as of the interview period. Nevertheless, they could not give an exact number of employed online teachers in their company since this is under management's particulars.

About the training received by the teachers, all of the teachers stated that they received pre-service and in-service training. Pre-service training includes orientation about the company, students, and contents of the lessons, which all happen in one day. As a final step for online language teachers, they must conduct a teaching demonstration reviewed by the company's trainer. Moreover, in-service training is given to teachers to help them develop skills. Although in-service training is helpful, these are not obligatory, but teachers are highly encouraged to attend to earn points for promotion. As one of much in-service training given, the TESOL course is offered to teachers for free in two companies.

Furthermore, every respondent acknowledged that they provide one-on-one online English language instruction to Chinese students of all ages, from children to adults. The length of a lesson can range from 25 to 40 minutes. Each company uses customized audio/video-online conferencing software. Their lessons include role-playing, dialogue, formal discussion, and casual conversation to increase speaking

exercises in the target language. This indicates that conversational fluency is one of the English learning goals of their students.

Research Question 1: What is the TPACK level of online English language teachers?

Figure 4

Perceived TPACK Skills Rating of Online English Language Teachers

A total of 15 online English language teachers took part in the poll. The majority of the responders (n=13) scored over 4 on the TPACK scale. Overall, the responders' average TPACK skill rating is 4.46. This indicates that 86% of respondents believed they have excellent TPACK skills.

Figure 5

Perceived TPACK Skills Rating per Category (Overall Average)

As presented in Figure 5, the highest average rating is in Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), with 4.65 among the seven TPACK categories. On the other hand, TK is the category wherein respondents feel less confident, with an average rating of 4.27. TPACK categories with the pedagogical element (i.e., PCK, TPK, and TPACK) also scored higher than categories with content and technological elements only. The result echoes the studies of Chai et al. (2010) and Archambault and Crippen (2009). Also, several studies (Valtonen et al., 2018; Koh et al., 2010) have articulated PK as the strongest area of teachers. It shows that online English language teachers have strong confidence in their skills if the pedagogical aspect is included in any TPACK categories. If pedagogical knowledge is associated with other domains, content knowledge influences teachers' confidence more than technological knowledge. Online English language teachers appear less competent if the TPACK categories are linked to the TK aspect.

Research Question 2: Is there a relationship between OELTs demographic variables and their TPACK level?

Figure 6

Perceived TPACK Skills Rating by Educational Attainment

Moreover, online English language teachers are divided into two groups based on educational attainment. The majority of the respondents (n=13) are Bachelor's Degree holders, while only two respondents are Master's Degree graduates. Bachelor's degree holder teachers have an average rating of 4.46, and the Master's degree holder teachers perceived themselves with a 4.41 rating. The point 5 difference between the two groups signifies that educational attainment does not influence one's TPACK. However, the uneven distribution of respondents may have caused a biased result.

In the qualitative data, personal practices have helped improve both groups' teaching styles. In addition to that, the bachelor's degree holders listed professional development, personal attributes, and teaching experiences. They also emphasized

teaching experience as a specific work opportunity that has assisted them in becoming effective teachers of conversational fluency. The teaching experiences of two bachelor degree holders have enabled them to be flexible in their classes. According to Respondent 2, "I have been teaching as an ESL teacher for more [5 than] than five years now. My best practice is being flexible with my teaching style to different learners." Respondent 12, a classroom teacher for 17 years, mentioned that "Flexibility, resourcefulness, initiative are only some of the keys to make a job well done." (See Appendix 9).

Figure 7

Perceived TPACK Skills Rating per Category by Educational Attainment

Teachers with Bachelor's degrees outperformed Master's degree holders in 4 TPACK categories (i.e., TK, PCK, TCK, and TPK). On the other hand, Master's degree holder teachers scored higher in PK, CK, and TPACK. In general, neither group significantly differs in their overall TPACK ability.

However, it is not surprising that there is a dearth of respondents with a Master's degree for the study. Online English instruction is regarded as an entry-level position. Some firms do not demand a college degree (Dinu, 2021); nonetheless, nearly all online teaching companies require TEFL or TESOL certification (Johnson, 2021). This demonstrates that a teaching certification with a minimum of 100 hours of study time, with courses in assessment strategies, classroom management, English grammar, and a short practicum, is far more valuable than an individual's educational attainment. The qualitative data has also mentioned TESOL certification as a means of meaningfully assisting online English language teachers (Respondents 2,5,8 & 14) (See Appendix 9). In addition,

Respondent 14 said that TESOL training provides additional knowledge to teachers who are not Education graduates, yet, TESOL is 'not suitable for actual online teaching' (See Appendix 12).

Figure 8

Perceived TPACK Skills Rating by Course

The majority of the respondents are Education graduates, comprising ten individuals. The remaining five respondents are Business, Tourism, or Engineering graduates. Overall, the TPACK average rating skill of teachers with an Education degree is 4.54, whereas the non-Education degree group scores 4.29.

Figure 9

Perceived TPACK Skills Rating per Category by Course

Teachers, who are Education degree holders, have better scores in most TPACK categories (i.e., PK, TK, CK, TCK, TPK, and TPACK). Both groups scored equally in the PCK category, garnering an average rating of 4.53. The qualitative data suggest that Education degree holders cite their teaching and training chances on and off the teaching platform, in addition to their practices and traits, as an advantage for handling conversational English online. Respondent 1, an Education graduate, stated that “engaging in regular professional development programs or training is a great way to improve your teaching style.” She also reiterated in the interview that “I find my college education and teaching experiences helpful as an online ESL teacher.” Respondent 15, a holder of a degree in Education, similarly viewed her studies as significant, recalling that “education courses reminded me how to deal with students.

On the other hand, non-degree holders relied on their personal characteristics and personal practices that helped them improve their teaching style. This includes “listening to audiobooks to improve listening skills” (Respondent 3), “being a technology-oriented teacher” (Respondent 4), “reviewing lesson material before the class” (Respondent 11), “mimick[ing] other online teacher’s strategies thru online videos”(Respondent 8) and “[doing] discovery learning” (Respondent 14). In addition, they mentioned non-specific previous work experiences. Nevertheless, these work experiences progressed their communication skills like “...talking to people about products” (Respondent 11) and “talk[ing] with more confidence”(Respondent 8) (see Appendix 9).

Figure 10

Perceived TPACK Skills Rating by Years of Teaching Experience

The respondents are classified into four groups based on their years of teaching experience. Four teachers have taught for less than a year, seven teachers

for 1-3 years, two for 4-6 years, and two for more than six years. Online English language teachers with 4-6 years of teaching experience performed the best, while teachers with less than one year of teaching experience performed the worst.

In the open-ended question: "What specific work experience helps you become effective in handling conversational English in an online setting?" teachers, regardless of their years in teaching, responded about their teaching experience. This teaching experience includes "working for my company for five years" (Respondent 2), "...teaching experiences in school. I worked with different industries." (Respondent 5), "being a teacher by profession" (Respondent 15), and "teaching face to face" (Respondent 9). Teachers with less than one year of teaching experience and those teaching for 1-3 years regarded training as an important aspect of preparing online teachers. Respondent 15, an Education graduate with less than one year of teaching experience, called for "training opportunities." Teachers with 1-3 years of teaching experience were more specific. "We need training, tools, [sic] equipment" (Respondent 14), as well as "... training about the latest digital tools to teach online to make our lessons more fun and engaging" (Respondent 15) (see Appendix 9).

Figure 11

Perceived TPACK Skills Rating per Category by Years of Teaching Experience

Figure 11 demonstrates that with increasing years of teaching experience, there is an incremental score increase in all TPACK categories except TCK. However, teachers with more than six years of teaching experience would reduce ratings on PK, TK, TCK, and TPK. These teachers need more confidence in their technology skills; consequently, a TPACK category that includes a technological component (i.e., TCK) suffers. This is consistent with earlier research that experienced teachers lacked confidence in integrating technology (Koh et al., 2014; Lee & Tsai, 2010).

Furthermore, TK gets the least rating in all the TPACK categories for most groups. Online English language teachers perceive that their technology knowledge still needs to be improved. In Jang and Tsai's (2012) study, TK is the lowest score compared to the other TPACK categories, and both novice and experienced teachers felt less confident in this type of knowledge.

When qualitative data from respondents are analyzed, no common denominator amongst distinct groups influences their TPACK rating. Nevertheless, Respondent 2, with six years of teaching experience, said in an interview, “I am technologically oriented, but I need more support on technology-side because technology has been so quick to evolve now more than ever, and I feel others are more savvy than I am.” (See Appendix 12).

Figure 12

Perceived TPACK Skills Rating by Age

There are two age groups for the study. Seven teachers belong to the younger age group (i.e., 21-30 y.o), while eight teachers belong to the advanced age group (i.e., 31-40 y.o). The younger age group has higher TPACK skills, with an average rating of 4.53, than the advanced group, with 4.39. Lee and Tsai (2010) conducted a study on the perceptions of TPACK among Taiwanese in-service teachers utilizing web-based technology. Their findings aligned with Yaghi's (2001)

assertion that older teachers tend to exhibit lower levels of confidence when it comes to utilizing computers or technology. In improving their teaching style, qualitative data of the respondents among advanced age groups include professional development (Respondent 1), teaching experience (Respondents 2 & 12), personal characteristics (Respondent 7) and personal practices (Respondents 5, 8, 10 & 15). Meanwhile, the younger age group relied only on their personal characteristics (Respondent 4) and practices (Respondents 3, 6, 9, 11, 13, 14). Nevertheless, most of the respondents from both groups have highlighted that their teaching experience helped them become effective teachers (Respondents 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 14 & 15) (See Appendix 10).

Figure 13

Perceived TPACK Skills Rating per Category by Age

In each TPACK category, the younger age group (i.e., 21-30 y.o) rates higher in most specified skills except TCK. While some studies have suggested that the correlations between age and TPACK constructs are minimal (Koh et al., 2010; Koh & Chai, 2011), the provided figure presents suggestive findings related to three

specific TPACK categories: pedagogical knowledge (PK), technological knowledge (TK), and pedagogical content knowledge (PCK).

Foremost, PK receives the highest rating for both groups, indicating their pedagogical knowledge confidence. In addition, PCK, as both groups' second strong domain, has an enormous disparity among all the categories. The considerable gap between groups' CK ratings may have also influenced their PCK score. The words *content* or *material* is a recurring keyword from the younger age group when asked about their needs, most helpful personal practice, and training expectations. According to Respondent 11, the need to "review(ing) the material or lesson before the class" is a helpful personal practice that improves teaching style. "Training contents related to my needs as online ESL teacher" (Respondent 9) and "trainings with vocabulary drills or exercises related to content material are what I find interesting" (Respondent 14) (See Appendix 9).

Finally, the TK rating of both groups reveals a one-point difference indicating very little influence of respondent's age. Both PCK and TK results reecho Cheng and Xie's (2018) research findings which indicate a positive association between age and pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), while also indicating a negative correlation between age and technological knowledge (TK).

Figure 14

Perceived TPACK Skills Rating by Technological Expertise

In terms of technological expertise, eight respondents described themselves as "comfortable users," while seven described themselves as "confident explorers." The figure above demonstrates that the confident explorer group has a higher average rating for TPACK skill, at 4.62 than the comfortable user group, at 4.31.

In an interview, a comfortable user is described as being "interested [sic] to learning new things.. but do not want to have like changes every time every month" (Respondent 2), knowledge on "how to use a computer and.. laptop or smart phone with ease" yet "panic a little bit" when prompted with errors (Respondent 14). On the other hand, a confident explorer is defined as being "not afraid to search and try other internet application... like software", "excited for new [software] updates" (Respondent 1),"like to search for reviews about certain gadgets... looked for activities online", "research about different gadgets...which can best help ... to deliver the lesson smoothly"(Respondent 4), look for ways to solve computer problem with basic understanding on some technology terms (Respondent 5), "not afraid of using new features of the software" , "like to learn independently"

(Respondent 9) and “understand different functions of the software” (Respondent 11) (See Appendix 12).

Figure 15

Perceived TPACK Skills Rating per Category by Technological Expertise

Confident explorers have also scored higher in all TPACK categories, with a noticeable difference in rating when a technological aspect is included in the criteria (i.e., TK, TCK, and TPK). This proves Stewart et al.’s (2013) finding that using technology is an influential factor in TPACK as it determines teachers’ decision to integrate technology into their teaching and learning. Less confident technology users tend to stay away from using technology as they think it is too complicated.

Additionally, teachers’ CK rating displays a considerable difference. One explanation for this is that teachers who manifest TK would use technology to

explore more about the subject content they are teaching (Koehler & Mishra, 2009). This will result in better CK and TCK ratings.

Both confident explorers and comfortable users listed their teaching experience, personal practice and characteristics as ways to improve their teaching technique. However, the narrative accounts of confident explorers of this study displayed a declaration of openness to exploring new things in order to improve their teaching style. These are the traits of being “open-minded and learning more on technology” (Respondent 7) and “willing[ness] to accept new suggestions” (Respondent 5). Moreover, Respondent 4 gave an example as “looked for activities online that I can use to break the ice during the session” and “[sic] research about different gadgets, like webcam, headset, computer specs, which can best help me deliver lesson smoothly when glitches happen” (See Appendix 9). Confident explorers' attitude toward technology utilization serves as a catalyst for developing a greater level of analytical ability, allowing them to hone both knowledge and expertise. Baylor and Ritchie (2002) also demonstrated a strong correlation between instructors' readiness to change and their level of technology integration and skill with technology

On the other hand, comfortable users of technology were more likely to engage in passive activities such as viewing and listening to digital materials in order to improve their teaching style. One of these strategies is to emulate the practices of other online teachers via video. “I watched videos of seasoned online teachers” (Respondent 15). Two respondents watched videos of online teachers to know “how to conduct a certain topic” (Respondent 10) and to “mimic other online teacher’s strategies” (Respondent 8). In developing her teaching style, respondent 3 added that “I listen to audiobooks to help me improve my listening skills.” (See Appendix 9).

Research Question 3: What are the pedagogical practices in their language teacher education training that the online English language teachers find effective?

Data from Community of Inquiry (CoI) survey responses were analyzed to address this question. The CoI model illustrates how a group of individual learners learns through an educational experience that occurs at the nexus of social, cognitive, and teaching presence (Garrison, Anderson & Archer, 2000). The three basic presences – teaching, social, and cognitive – are inextricably linked. There is a correlation between the three presences and students' perceived learning, course satisfaction, instructor satisfaction, actual learning, and sense of belonging (Arbaugh, 2008; Akyol & Garrison, 2008; Richardson et al., 2017).

Figure 16

Community of Inquiry Average mean Score per Presence

Examining each dimension, teaching presence emerges as the highest-scoring aspect, with a mean score of 4.68, signifying its considerable importance for online English language teachers. Previous research by Mars et al. (2005) and Means et al. (2014) suggests that teacher presence in online learning is a stronger predictor of student achievement compared to peer interactions. Garrison et al. (2000) and Garrison & Cleveland-Innes (2005) argue that teaching presence is the cohesive force that binds an online learning community together, facilitating the cognitive and social activities crucial for successful online learning. Additionally, cognitive presence holds a significant advantage over social presence in this study, indicating its greater significance among the three domains. This finding aligns with the results of Diaz et al. (2010) regarding the Community of Inquiry (CoI) presence ranking. In the qualitative data, respondents expressed that the overall training was effective and helpful (Respondents 4, 6, 12, 13, & 15, see Appendix 9).

Teaching Presence

Figure 17

Teaching Presence Average Score per Design Element

The results indicate that direct instruction received the highest mean score of 4.71, indicating its perceived significance among the respondents. Facilitation closely followed with a mean score of 4.68, suggesting its substantial role in the training process. On the other hand, design and organization received the lowest mean score of 4.65, suggesting a relatively lower level of importance attributed to this aspect.

To gain deeper insights into the training program preferences of the respondents, a detailed analysis of each item and category within the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework was conducted. The mean scores of each item were interpreted and ranked, providing valuable information about the participants' perceptions. The evaluation of mean scores in the CoI framework was based on predefined ranges and descriptors, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the data.

1.00 – 1.79	Not satisfactory
1.80 – 2.59	Merely satisfactory
2.60 – 3.39	Satisfactory
3.40 – 4.19	Highly satisfactory
4.20 – 5.00	Excellent

Table 5

Descriptive Results of Teaching Presence

Categories	#	Item Statement	M	SD
Design and Organization		The instructor...		
	1	clearly communicated important course goals.	4.6	.63
	2	clearly communicated important course topics.	4.6	.63
	3	provided clear instructions on how to participate in course learning activities.	4.6	.61
Facilitation	4	clearly communicated important due dates/time frames for learning activities.	4.7	.45
	5	was helpful in identifying areas of agreement and disagreement on course topics that helped me to learn.	4.73	.59
	6	was helpful in guiding the class towards understanding course topics in a way that helped me to clarify my thinking.	4.73	.59
	7	helped me to keep course participants engaged and participating in productive dialogue.	4.6	.61
	8	helped me keep the course participants on task in a way that helped them to learn.	4.6	.63
	9	encouraged course participants to explore new concepts in this course	4.73	.59
Direct Instruction	10	Instructor actions reinforced the development of a sense of community among course participants	4.6	.63
	11	helped me to focus discussion on relevant issues in a way that helped me to learn.	4.67	.61
	12	provided feedback that helped me to understand my strengths and weaknesses relative to the course' goals and objectives	4.73	.59
	13	provided feedback in a timely fashion.	4.73	.59
Overall			4.68	

Table 5 presents the descriptive results of the perceived teaching presence within the training attended by the participants. The overall mean value of 4.68 indicates an excellent level of teaching presence. Although all items received favorable evaluations, analyzing their rankings provides further insights into the

specific aspects of teaching presence that was perceived most positively by the participants, contributing to a deeper understanding of the study results.

Table 6

Ranking of Teaching Presence Items by Mean Scores

Ranking	Item #	Category
1	Item #5	Facilitation
	Item #6	Facilitation
	Item #9	Facilitation
	Item #12	Direct Instruction
	Item #13	Direct Instruction
2	Item #4	Design and Organization
3	Item #11	Direct Instruction
4	Item #1	Design and Organization
	Item #2	Design and Organization
	Item #3	Design and Organization
	Item #7	Facilitation
	Item #8	Facilitation
	Item #10	Facilitation

Direct Instruction

Garrison et al. (2000) define direct instruction as a pedagogical approach where the instructor takes primary responsibility for teaching while involving students in the instructional process. In this study, direct instruction emerged as the highest-ranking design element under the construct of teaching presence, garnering a notable mean score of 4.71.

Specifically, items 11 to 13, which pertain to direct instruction, were examined in the survey. Among these items, item 12 and item 13 received the highest ratings from the participants. This indicates that the respondents highly valued the instructors' feedback that helped them understand their strengths and weaknesses regarding the course's goals and objectives, as well as the timely delivery of such

feedback. The positive ratings suggest that receiving prompt and constructive feedback played a significant role in enhancing the participants' understanding of their capabilities within the context of the course. Furthermore, item 11, which focuses on the instructor's facilitation of discussions on relevant issues, ranked third among all the items in the teaching presence construct. This finding underscores the participants' recognition of the instructor's guidance in directing purposeful and targeted discussions, leading to effective learning outcomes. The ranking highlights the importance of the instructor's role in creating an environment conducive to meaningful discussions and engaging the participants in relevant and beneficial topics for their learning journey.

Facilitation

Facilitation involves creating a supportive learning environment through communication cues, feedback provision, and instructional guidance. The mean score for facilitation was 4.68, positioning it as the second-highest element within teaching presence. Among the items in the facilitation construct, items 5, 6, and 9 received the highest rankings, indicating that participants perceived instructors who excel in identifying areas of agreement and disagreement, guiding class discussions to enhance understanding, and fostering an environment that encourages the exploration of new concepts.

The participants' expectations for their Teacher Education Program align with the attributes related to facilitation and content knowledge. They expressed the desire for instructors or mentors who are professional, knowledgeable in language teaching and technology (Respondents 1,2,3,10,12), and deliver contemporary training activities with efficiency and flexibility (Respondents 6,7,8,13,15).

Participants also emphasized the importance of having a friendly and non-authoritative approach from instructors (Respondent 5). The interview (See Appendix 12) further highlighted the importance of trainers who are open to suggestions from teachers, acknowledging their ideas as valuable contributions to becoming effective trainers.

However, it is important to note that three items related to facilitation (items 7 to 10) ranked lower among all the items within teaching presence. This suggests that participants assign relatively less importance to aspects such as peer-to-peer interaction, maintaining participant engagement and task-oriented focus, and the development of a sense of community among learners in the online learning context. Overall, the findings underscore the significance of facilitation in online teaching and learning environments. They emphasize the need for instructors to adopt a supportive and helpful role that fosters active engagement and knowledge construction. The study highlights the importance of aligning instructor practices with participant expectations, particularly in facilitation and content expertise, to create effective and engaging learning experiences.

Design and Organization

Design, as defined by Garrison et al. (2000), encompasses a course's structure, content, and organization. Within the teaching presence construct, the design received the lowest mean score of 4.65. Items 1 to 4 are associated with this element. Only item 4, which focuses on the instructor clearly communicating important due dates and time frames for learning activities, ranked second among all the items within teaching presence. This aligns with the importance of communication in direct instruction. On the other hand, items 1 to 3, which pertain to

clearly communicating course goals, topics, and instructions on participating in learning activities, were positioned in the bottom ranking. This suggests that online English language teachers gave less importance on knowing course goals and topics and on explicit instructions for participation.

Social Presence

Figure 18

Social Presence Average Score per Design Element

According to Kilgore and Lowenthal (2015), course participants can establish their social presence by sharing personal experiences that are relevant to the course, either partially or throughout the course. In the current study, respondents assigned equal scores to affective expression and open communication, with an average rating of 4.49. However, group cohesion received the lowest mean score of 4.33 among the dimensions of social presence.

The findings suggest that participants in the study valued the opportunity to express emotions and engage in open communication within the online learning

environment. This indicates their inclination to establish a sense of connection and emotional presence with their peers and instructors. However, the lower rating for group cohesion suggests that participants may have perceived challenges in fostering a strong sense of community and collaborative interaction within the course.

Table 7

Descriptive Results of Social Presence

Categories	#	Item Statement	M	SD
Affective Expression	14	Getting to know other course participants gave me a sense of belonging in the course	4.73	.59
	15	I was able to form distinct impressions of some course participants.	4.6	.63
	16	Online or web-based communication is an excellent medium for social interaction.	4.13	.99
Open communication	17	I felt comfortable conversing through the online medium.	4.33	.72
	18	I felt comfortable participating in course discussions.	4.66	.48
	19	I felt comfortable interacting with other course participants	4.46	.63
Group cohesion	20	I felt comfortable disagreeing with other course participants while still maintaining a sense of trust.	4.20	.77
	21	I felt that my point of view was acknowledged by other course participants.	4.33	.81
	22	Online discussion helped me to develop a sense of collaboration.	4.46	.63
Overall			4.44	

The participants in the study generally perceive a high level of social presence in the online learning environment, as indicated by the mean score of 4.44. This suggests that they feel a strong sense of social connectedness and interaction within the online setting. However, it is important to note that the effectiveness of online or web-based communication for social interaction, as measured by item 16, received a

relatively lower mean score of 4.13. While still considered highly satisfactory, this item ranked the lowest among all other items under social presence. Similarly, Cobb's (2009) study indicated CMC-related words as the lowest-scoring item among all the statements in the social presence category.

Table 8

Ranking of Social Presence Items by Mean Scores

Ranking	Item #	Category
1	Item #14	Affective Expression
2	Item #18	Open Communication
3	Item #15	Affective Expression
4	Item #22	Group Cohesion
	Item #19	Open Communication
5	Item #17	Open Communication
	Item #21	Group Cohesion
6	Item #20	Group Cohesion
7	Item #16	Affective Expression

Affective Expression

Activities aimed at fostering peer connections and trust through introductions and providing introductory material fall under the category of affective expression, as identified by Richardson et al. (2010). These activities include using profile photos and introducing oneself. In this study, the respondents gave affective expression and open communication equal ratings, with an average score of 4.49. Items 14 to 16 are related to affective expression.

Among these items, item 14, which focuses on the sense of belonging derived from getting to know other participants, received the highest rating within affective expression and ranked first in social presence. This suggests that participants place great importance on interacting and getting to know their peers, contributing to a

strong sense of belonging and connection. This finding is consistent with previous research (Gunawardena & Zittle; Skiba et al., 2000; Cobb, 2009) that emphasized the significance of self-introduction in online courses.

On the other hand, item 16, which assesses the suitability of online or web-based communication for social interaction, received the lowest rating among the affective expression items and ranked last in social presence. This suggests that respondents may have reservations or perceive limitations in using online communication platforms for social interaction.

However, the interview data revealed that respondents still preferred the online training modality due to its comfort and realism (Respondents 1 & 2, Appendix 12), as their classes are online. They also highlighted the convenience it offers (Respondents 1 & 14, Appendix 12). However, there was anticipation for conferences (Respondent 1 & 14, Appendix 12) and on-site seminars (Respondent 9, Appendix 12) where they could meet other online teachers.

Open Communication

Open communication, which encompasses conversations, peer-to-peer interactions, and connections between participants and instructors, received an equal mean score to affective expression, indicating its importance in facilitating effective communication and building relationships. Items 17 to 19 are classified under open communication, and all three items received excellent ratings.

Item 18, which measures the comfort level of participants in participating in course discussions, ranked second among all the items in social presence. This indicates that respondents felt at ease and confident engaging in discussions within the course, reflecting a positive and supportive environment that encourages active

participation. Similarly, item 19, which focuses on the comfort level of interacting with other course participants, ranked fourth. This suggests that respondents felt comfortable interacting with their peers, highlighting the importance of creating an environment facilitating comfortable and meaningful peer interactions.

Respondents ranked item 17, which pertains to feeling comfortable conversing online, as the lowest among the elements of open communication and fifth in social presence. This suggests that participants may have experienced a lower level of comfort or encountered challenges when engaging in online conversations. The fact that this item, along with item 16 in an affective expression containing the keyword "online," received the lowest rankings highlights a common theme. It implies that participants may perceive limitations or difficulties related to utilizing online communication platforms.

Group Cohesion

One of the prominent aspects of social presence is group cohesiveness, which involves fostering a sense of belongingness and group commitment, and working towards shared goals and objectives (Pelz, 2010). To promote cohesiveness within a learning community, competitive and collaborative group tasks have been identified as effective strategies (Anwar, 2016). These tasks encompass a range of activities such as icebreaker discussions, collaborative projects, peer feedback, online discussions, virtual team-building activities, and synchronous meetings. The purpose of these activities is to cultivate a strong sense of community, encourage collaboration, and foster interpersonal relationships among participants. However, it is noteworthy that group cohesion received the lowest mean score of 4.33, which coincides with the unfavorable rating given by respondents to a teacher presence

item associated with student involvement. Although items 20 to 22 related to group cohesion received positive ratings, their bottom ranking position suggests a potential challenge in achieving a cohesive group dynamic in the online learning environment.

Item 22, which highlights the role of online discussions in promoting collaboration, ranked fourth among all items in social presence. This suggests that participants perceived online discussions as valuable for collaborative engagement and knowledge sharing. Item 21, focusing on acknowledging one's point of view by other course participants, ranked fifth, indicating the significance of validation and recognition within the group. Participants' perception of their point of view being acknowledged contributes to a sense of inclusion and respect within the learning community. However, item 20, which centers on feeling comfortable disagreeing with other participants while maintaining trust, ranked sixth, second to last among all items in social presence. This finding suggests that participants may have encountered challenges or hesitations in expressing dissenting opinions while maintaining trust and positive interpersonal dynamics. This discrepancy highlights the complexity of navigating disagreements within a cohesive group, particularly in an online learning environment where non-verbal cues and contextual factors may be limited.

Interestingly, the qualitative data revealed that only one respondent mentioned working with a group, as indicated in Appendix 12. This finding suggests that the participants may not have widely reported or emphasized the experience of collaborative group work. The lack of explicit mentions of group work in the qualitative data could indicate either a limited focus on group activities within the course or a potential gap in participants' perceptions and reflections.

Cognitive Presence

Figure 19

Cognitive Presence Average Score per Design Element

The exploration aspect received a high rating in the present study, indicating its perceived importance in the cognitive presence construct. This finding aligns with a study by Kovanović et al. (2016), identifying exploration as the highest-rated aspect of cognitive presence. Interestingly, the three other aspects of cognitive presence in the current study were rated almost equally, with only a 2-point difference. This suggests that participants in the study attributed similar levels of importance to triggering events, information exchange, and resolution.

In contrast to the findings of the current study, previous research conducted by Almasi and Zhu (2017), Garrison and Akyol (2008), and Gasevic et al. (2015) reported integration as the most frequently reported aspect of cognitive presence. The finding of integration receiving the lowest mean score in the current study

indicates a discrepancy between the present findings and the findings of these preceding studies.

Table 9

Descriptive Results of Cognitive Presence

Categories	#	Item	Mean	SD
Triggering Event	23	Problems posed increased my interest in course issues.	4.33	.61
	24	Course activities piqued my curiosity.	4.6	.63
	25	I felt motivated to explore content related questions.	4.6	.63
Exploration	26	I utilized a variety of information sources to explore problems posed in this course.	4.47	.63
	27	Brainstorming and finding relevant information helped me to resolve content related questions.	4.6	.61
	28	Online discussions were valuable in helping me appreciate different perspectives.	4.6	.63
Integration	29	Combining new information helped answer questions raised in course activities.	4.53	.63
	30	Learning activities helped me to construct explanations/solutions.	4.46	.63
	31	Reflection on course content and discussions helped me understand fundamental concepts in this class.	4.4	.63
Resolution	32	I can describe ways to test and apply knowledge created in this course.	4.53	.63
	33	I have developed solutions to course problems that can be applied in practice.	4.46	.63
	34	I can apply the knowledge created in the course to my work or other non-class related activities.	4.46	.63
Overall			4.51	

In the present study, the cognitive presence dimension, representing the level of cognitive engagement and active participation in the learning process, achieved a mean score of 4.51. This high score indicates an excellent cognitive presence among the participants, suggesting their substantial cognitive involvement and active engagement in the learning activities. Notably, all items within the cognitive presence construct received excellent ratings. This indicates that participants in the study

perceived themselves as actively and meaningfully engaged in the cognitive aspects of the online learning experience. The high ratings suggest that participants demonstrated critical thinking, information processing, and knowledge construction throughout the online course. The findings of this study underscore the importance of fostering cognitive presence in online learning environments, as it is indicative of active and meaningful learning experiences

The qualitative data obtained from the respondents in this study provide insights into their perceptions of effective teaching practices in their training or courses. It is important to note that the respondents had diverse opinions and identified different activities as effective for learning. Some of the mentioned effective teaching practices included "role playing," which was highlighted by Respondents 1 and 2, and "reciprocal questioning" and "learner's interest," mentioned by Respondent 1. Respondents 3 and 13 emphasized the effectiveness of "active listening" and "error correction" in their learning experiences. Respondent 4 mentioned the value of an "interactive lecture," while Respondents 9 and 11 found "games" effective. Respondent 10 specifically mentioned the effectiveness of "teaching demonstration" in their training.

It is interesting to observe that Respondent 4 disliked self-paced training sessions that involved lengthy readings during the interview (refer to Appendix 12). However, despite this dislike, respondents, in general, reported that the overall training they received was effective and helpful, as mentioned by Respondents 4, 6, 12, 13, and 15 (refer to Appendix 9).

The diverse range of teaching practices identified by the respondents suggests that different approaches and methods may be effective for different individuals. It highlights the importance of considering learner preferences and

providing varied instructional strategies to accommodate diverse learning needs. Additionally, the overall positive perception of the training received by most respondents indicates that despite individual preferences or dislikes, the training program was perceived as effective and beneficial.

Table 10

Ranking of Cognitive Presence Items by Mean Scores

Ranking	Item #	Category
1	Item #24	Triggering Event
	Item #25	Triggering Event
	Item #27	Exploration
	Item #28	Exploration
2	Item #29	Integration
	Item #32	Resolution
3	Item #30	Integration
	Item #33	Resolution
	Item #34	Resolution
4	Item #26	Exploration
5	Item #31	Integration
6	Item #23	Triggering Event

Triggering event

According to Garrison (2016), a triggering event in the instructional design process is introducing a problem or dilemma that engages student interest. The triggering event should provide learners with activities related to the inquiry process (Fiock, 2020). It is worth noting that all of the specific items related to triggering events received excellent ratings, indicating their perceived effectiveness in stimulating cognitive engagement. Notably, items 24 and 25, which focused on course activities that sparked curiosity and motivated exploration of content-related questions, were ranked the highest among the participants. This suggests that these particular activities successfully captured the participants' attention and fostered their

active involvement in the learning process. However, item 23, which measured the impact of posed problems on increasing interest in course issues, received the lowest ranking among the triggering events. This finding suggests that the problems presented in the course generated less interest or motivation among the respondents in the cognitive aspect. There may be room for improvement in designing and presenting course problems to enhance their effectiveness in capturing the participants' interest and promoting cognitive engagement.

In an andragogic learning environment, providing opportunities for addressing real-world situations is crucial. Previous research by Horsley (2010) and Zipp et al. (2009) emphasizes the importance of incorporating real-world relevance in adult education. As evidenced by studies conducted by Wang and Chen (2009) and Lebedev and Fedoseyeva (2009), when students are given a chance to tackle topics directly relevant to their everyday experiences, their motivation to learn is enhanced. For instance, Respondent 8 expressed the expectation of a teacher education program relating to real-life situations. This aligns with the notion that incorporating real-world relevance in course content can enhance learner motivation and engagement. Overall, the findings suggest the significance of carefully designing triggering events that spark curiosity, motivate exploration, and create real-world connections to foster cognitive engagement in andragogic learning environments

Exploration

Exploration activities are a fundamental means to create a conducive learning environment for students, enabling them to engage in open discussions, generate solutions, and uncover new information (Richardson et al., 2012). The positive ratings obtained for items 27 and 28 signify the effectiveness of brainstorming,

information gathering, and online discussions in facilitating student learning and promoting social interaction. Although item 26 received a slightly lower rating, it still falls within the central range, indicating that students recognize the importance of utilizing diverse information sources when exploring the problems presented in the course. These findings underscore the critical role of well-designed exploration activities in fostering student engagement and enhancing social presence within the online learning environment.

Integration

As defined by Garrison (2007), integration within social presence refers to the process of connecting and synthesizing information from various sources to create a cohesive and meaningful learning experience. Items 29 to 31 fall under the integration element of the social presence construct, and all items within this element received excellent ratings. Items 29 and 30 received high rankings in the integration element, placing second and third, respectively. Respondents emphasized the importance of item 29, combining new information to address course questions, and item 30, constructing explanations or solutions through learning activities. These rankings highlight the value of information integration for enhancing the learning experience.

Item 31 had the lowest ranking among all items in cognitive presence. Item 31, involving reflection on course content and discussions for understanding fundamental concepts, received the lowest ranking. This finding highlights a potential need for more alignment between the perceived importance of reflection and its actual relevance and appeal to the participants.

Resolution

As a component of the cognitive presence construct, the resolution encompasses the application and utilization of knowledge gained from the course. The excellent ratings received by all three resolution-related items signify the participants' strong belief in their capacity to apply course knowledge. Specifically, item 32, focusing on testing and applying acquired knowledge, ranked second among all items. Additionally, items 33 and 34, involving the development of solutions to course problems and applying knowledge in real-world or non-class contexts, respectively, ranked third. These findings emphasize the participants' confidence in transferring and effectively utilizing course knowledge in practical situations. The high rankings also reflect the participants' appreciation for the practical application and relevance of acquired knowledge to their professional work or other activities.

Research Question 4: Based on their TPACK level and Col preferences, what training content and pedagogical guidelines should be provided to teachers?

Using the instructional design proposed for this thesis, the researcher observed the processes necessary to build a training outline for online English language teachers. The training blueprint (see Appendix 15) was created by analyzing and comparing the gathered data to the review of the related literature. The researcher acknowledged that no program is "one-size-fits-all." Thus, the online English language teacher training design comprises a course description, learning objectives, demographic considerations, and pedagogical standards that serve as recommendations for trainers or course developers.

Firstly, it is crucial to align the training content with the various components of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) to cater to the diverse needs of teachers. This entails encompassing Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), Technological Knowledge (TK), Content Knowledge (CK), Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK), Technological Content Knowledge (TCK), Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK), and TPACK in the training program. To ensure clarity and focus, written course objectives should be outlined for each TPACK category to guide the selection of appropriate topics.

The delivery of the training should prioritize the individual training needs of the teachers, taking into account their demographic characteristics. A training program blueprint should be created, summarizing the training needs of teachers based on their unique demographic traits. Although the order of training needs for each group has been identified, training providers are encouraged to conduct an assessment of teachers' current competencies. This assessment will help determine the specific

order in which the TPACK components should be addressed, ensuring a tailored approach to training.

The analysis of the TPACK needs summary reveals that Technological Knowledge (TK) is the most critical area for all teachers. Therefore, TK training content should be given the highest priority. The content of the TK training will be tailored based on individual teachers' technological adeptness and attitude, aiming to enhance their competency and confidence in utilizing technology effectively in their instructional practices.

In addition, a group of teachers consistently demonstrate low TPACK skill ratings across different demographic categories. These teachers need to receive comprehensive training in all TPACK domains. However, to address initial concerns about technology, the training program should introduce each domain sequentially. The recommended sequence begins with TK, CK, and PK. This approach allows teachers to gradually build their confidence and familiarity with technology before delving into subject-specific content knowledge and pedagogical strategies.

Novice teachers with less than one year of teaching experience require prompt, comprehensive teaching support to enhance their instructional practices. Alongside the training content, immediate assistance and guidance are essential for their successful transition into teaching. On the other hand, experienced teachers who have been in the online teaching platform for longer duration are highly encouraged to participate in training programs as well. This provides an opportunity for reflection, skill evaluation, and metacognition, allowing them to continuously improve their teaching methodologies and stay updated with current best practices in the online environment.

To ensure the success of the training program, several key elements should be considered. Firstly, the program should include qualified mentors with professionalism, expertise, and compassion. These mentors will guide and support the participants throughout their learning journey.

To foster a sense of camaraderie and collaboration among the participants, introductory activities should be incorporated into the program. These activities help create a positive and inclusive learning environment.

To enhance engagement and relevance, real-life issues and challenges should be integrated into the training program. This approach allows participants to apply their knowledge and skills to authentic situations, promoting a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Effective pedagogical practices should be emphasized throughout the program, including interactive discussions, group collaboration, and timely feedback. These practices foster active engagement, critical thinking, and knowledge sharing among the participants.

Encouraging curiosity, exploration, and information gathering is essential in promoting a deep understanding of the content. Incorporating activities such as brainstorming sessions and online discussions can stimulate curiosity and encourage participants to explore different perspectives and ideas.

Lastly, the training program should build participants' confidence in transferring and applying their acquired knowledge to practical solutions. This can be achieved by providing opportunities for hands-on practice, real-world simulations, and problem-solving activities.

Recognizing the diverse preferences and needs of the participants, the training program should offer flexible delivery modes beyond the online format. This

could include blended learning approaches or alternative platforms to accommodate different learning styles and circumstances. By incorporating these elements into the training program, participants can benefit from a comprehensive and engaging learning experience that supports their professional growth and development.

Chapter V

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary, conclusion, and recommendations based on the data analyzed in the previous chapter.

Summary of the Research

The rapid expansion of the online language education market in the Philippines has resulted in a surge of interest among Filipinos seeking employment. The allure of competitive salaries and relatively flexible qualification requirements has attracted many individuals to pursue online language teaching. However, as the demand for international students grows, online language schools need to meet the increased expectations and regulations surrounding teacher qualifications. This has created a pressing need for online language schools to enhance their training programs to ensure the delivery of high-quality education and meet the evolving demands of the market.

The study aimed to investigate the training needs of online English teachers in the Philippines. The study followed a research design that integrated elements from the ADDIE and SAM processes while excluding certain steps. The selection and omission of specific steps in the study are based on the underlying aim to adhere to the designated time constraints while concurrently establishing a resilient data processing framework for the envisaged training program.

The study focused on targeting online English teachers in the Philippines who met specific criteria related to their teaching experience and qualifications. Initial attempts to recruit participants through language schools were unsuccessful, leading to using a snowball sampling method with the help of the researcher's network. A

verification process was implemented to ensure data validity, and 15 eligible teachers participated in the survey. From this group, seven teachers expressed willingness to engage in subsequent interviews. While the sample size is small, it is considered more valid for homogeneous populations. Homogeneity in the sample helps facilitate effective group interaction and dynamics.

The research instruments used in this study were a survey questionnaire and interviews. The questionnaire consisted of verification, demographics, an adapted TPACK survey, an adapted Col survey, and open-ended questions. It was administered using Google Forms, allowing efficient data management and communication with participants. The questionnaire aimed to collect information on participants' qualifications, characteristics, teaching practices, technological skills, and perceptions of effective teaching. The interviews were conducted with voluntary participants who provided their contact details and aimed to gather in-depth insights into their teaching and professional backgrounds. The instruments underwent content validation and revisions to ensure clarity and relevance. These research instruments provided comprehensive data to support the study's objectives.

In gathering the data, the researcher initially attempted to contact online language schools that met specific criteria to recruit participants. However, due to a lack of response, individuals who had previously or currently worked as online English teachers were directly contacted. These individuals were asked to complete the web-based survey questionnaire and share the questionnaire link with their colleagues. The survey remained accessible online for two weeks. After the survey period, the quantitative and qualitative data from the responses were analyzed, including identifying correlations, themes, and emerging issues. Participants who volunteered for the interview phase were contacted through email, and one-to-one

interviews were conducted using their preferred video-calling software. The interviews were audio-recorded and later transcribed for qualitative analysis. The collected quantitative and qualitative data were then compared and presented, with the qualitative data supporting and elaborating on the quantitative results.

The data analysis in this study involved both quantitative and qualitative methods. Descriptive statistics were used to calculate each participant's mean TPACK skill ratings and determine the mean scores for different TPACK categories. This quantitatively represented participants' TPACK levels based on their responses. Using descriptive statistics, the quantitative analysis also examined the relationship between TPACK levels and teacher demographic backgrounds.

Qualitative data analysis involved coding the interview responses to identify patterns, themes, and perspectives. Content analysis was used to develop a coding system for consistent and objective qualitative data analysis. This allowed for a deeper exploration of participants' experiences and provided qualitative insights into the research questions.

Descriptive analysis determined the mean scores for each Community of Inquiry framework presence. This quantitative analysis provided insights into participants' levels of presence in the Community of Inquiry. The interview responses were also transcribed and coded using a coding analysis to identify recurring themes and perspectives, complementing the quantitative analysis.

The quantitative and qualitative data were then consolidated and examined to design a training program for online English language teachers. The quantitative data informed the content and mechanisms of the training program, while the qualitative data provided the rationale and support for its design. Instructional design models were adapted to guide the development of the training program.

The following section outlines the findings and recommendations, focusing on the perceptions of online English language teachers regarding their TPACK skills and preferred pedagogical practices. The research questions and themes emerging from the data analysis are addressed. The research questions are:

1. What is the TPACK level of online English language teachers (OELTs)?
2. Is there a relationship between OELTs demographic variables and their TPACK level?
3. What are the pedagogical practices in their language teacher education training that online English language teachers find effective?
4. Based on their TPACK level and CoI preferences, what training content and pedagogical guidelines should be provided to teachers?

Summary of Findings

TPACK of Online English Language Teachers

A poll involving 15 online English language teachers revealed that most respondents (86%) believed they possessed excellent TPACK skills, with an average rating of 4.46. Among the TPACK categories, Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) received the highest average rating (4.65), while Technological Knowledge (TK) had the lowest average rating (4.27), indicating lower confidence in that area. The results align with previous studies (Valtonen et al., 2018; Koh et al., 2010) emphasizing the significance of pedagogical knowledge in teachers' confidence, highlighting that content knowledge is more influential than technological knowledge.

There is a relationship between certain demographic variables of online English language teachers (OELTs) and their TPACK level:

1. Educational attainment: The study found that educational attainment, specifically having a Bachelor's degree or a Master's degree, did not significantly influence the TPACK level of OELTs. Both groups had almost similar TPACK ratings, indicating that educational background alone did not determine TPACK proficiency.
2. College courses: OELTs with an Education degree had higher TPACK scores in most categories than non-Education degree holders. Education graduates emphasized their teaching and training experiences and personal practices in handling online English instruction. Non-degree holders highlighted personal characteristics, practices, and previous work experiences in improving their teaching style.
3. Years of teaching experience: There was a relationship between years of teaching experience and TPACK level. Overall, as years of teaching experience increased, there was an incremental increase in TPACK scores. However, teachers with over six years of experience showed lower confidence in pedagogical knowledge and technology-related skills, indicating a decline in TPACK scores in certain categories.
4. Age groups: The younger age group (21-30 years old) demonstrated higher TPACK skills than the advanced age group (31-40 years old). Older teachers generally showed less confidence in using technology, aligning with previous research. Both age groups emphasized the importance of teaching experience in improving their teaching style, but the advanced age group also highlighted professional development and personal characteristics.
5. Technological expertise: The current study categorized OELTs into "comfortable users" and "confident explorers" based on their technological expertise. The

distinction between these groups was defined within the current study. The confident explorer group had higher TPACK scores across all categories, particularly in technology-related areas. Comfortable users displayed basic knowledge but hesitancy towards changes, while confident explorers actively sought out new technology and were open to exploration. Confident explorers' positive attitude towards technology utilization correlated with higher TPACK levels.

The impact of demographic variables like gender and educational attainment on the TPACK level was limited. At the same time, age, technological expertise, non-education background, and teaching experience of 0-3 years were associated with lower TPACK scores. Younger age groups, confident explorers, education degree holders, and teachers with over four years of experience excelled in most TPACK categories. Respondents acknowledged that their effectiveness in teaching is attributed to a combination of factors, including their teaching experience, personal characteristics, practices, and access to professional development opportunities. Technological Knowledge (TK) consistently received low ratings, while Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) displayed high and predicted ratings in other TPACK categories.

Preferred Pedagogical Practices in their Language Teacher Education Training

The study's findings shed light on several critical aspects of the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework. Regarding teaching presence, participants highly valued direct instruction, where instructors take primary responsibility for teaching and provide feedback that helps them understand their strengths and weaknesses. Facilitation, creating a supportive learning environment, and guiding discussions was also recognized as crucial. However, the design and organization of the course

received lower ratings, indicating a need for clearer communication of goals, topics, and participation instructions.

Regarding social presence, affective expression played a significant role in fostering a strong sense of belonging and connection among participants. Interactions and getting to know peers were highly valued. However, there were reservations about using online communication platforms for social interaction. Open communication, including participating in course discussions and interacting with others, was rated positively, highlighting the importance of a positive and supportive environment. However, participants reported lower comfort levels when conversing through the online medium. Group cohesion faced challenges, as participants expressed difficulties in feeling comfortable disagreeing with others while maintaining trust. This suggests potential difficulties in achieving a cohesive group dynamic in the online learning environment, potentially due to limited emphasis on collaborative group work within the course.

Regarding cognitive presence, triggering events that engage student interest was highly rated, particularly activities that sparked curiosity and motivated exploration. However, the impact of posed problems on increasing interest received the lowest rating, indicating room for improvement in designing and presenting course problems. Incorporating real-world relevance in the course, content enhanced learner motivation and engagement. Exploration activities, such as brainstorming and online discussions, effectively facilitated student learning and promoted social interaction. Integration activities involving connecting and synthesizing information received excellent ratings, highlighting their value in enhancing the learning experience. However, reflection on course content and discussions for understanding fundamental concepts had the lowest ranking, suggesting a potential

misalignment between the perceived importance of reflection and its appeal to the participants. Finally, resolution activities focused on applying and utilizing course knowledge received excellent ratings, indicating participants' confidence in their ability to apply acquired knowledge, emphasizing the practical application and relevance of acquired knowledge to their professional work or other activities.

Implications to Training Design

1. TK is the most obvious domain where teacher support is much needed. It is also influential in other components of TPACK. When it comes to technology, one's age does not necessarily indicate one's level of expertise but rather one's attitude toward technology. Thus, companies should constantly support their staff's development of technology knowledge and skill. To get the most out of technology support training, teachers should be classified according to how they view technology in their instruction. So, course goals and instructional strategies will be more closely aligned.
2. Teachers with all of the following traits should be given high priority and encouraged to participate in training programs:
 - a. Less than three years of teaching experience
 - b. Graduates who did not complete Education-related courses
 - c. Between ages 31 and 40 (senior group for this study)
 - d. Consider themselves as Comfortable Users of technology (less expert for this study)

This group is seen to be the least advantaged.

3. Teachers with less than one year of teaching experience feel least confident among the groups in most of the TPACK categories. It will be ideal if rookie

members receive extra support from senior teachers (>4 years of teaching experience) through a buddy system. Both parties could benefit from this collaboration in terms of their professional development. Novice teachers will be less hesitant to ask about their challenges. On the other hand, senior teachers will have the opportunity to execute metacognition in guiding new teachers by reflecting on their personal practices.

4. In one-to-one language teaching, the tendency for excessive familiarity and predictability in one-to-one language teaching instills complacency in senior teachers, causing them to coast. Thus, teachers with more than six years of teaching experience are greatly encouraged to continuously seek knowledge related to TPACK domains, whether it is through self-directed study or participation in professional development opportunities. TK and PK should be prioritized among all the other domains. The rapid development of technology results in new knowledge and abilities. Contemporary TK will enable them to manage their technology-assisted classroom effectively.
5. School administrators should continually assess online English language teachers' TPACK skills. With this regulation in place, they can help their personnel improve their TPACK knowledge and abilities to the fullest extent possible. Teachers' good technology integration may lead to learners' successful learning.
6. The primary objective of courses within the proposed training program is cultivating genuine enthusiasm for continuous personal learning. Furthermore, the inclusion of practical experiences holds immense significance in the enhancement of individuals' skills and expertise. Through active participation in real-world applications and hands-on experiences, learners gain valuable

opportunities to apply their theoretical knowledge in practical settings, resulting in a profound comprehension of concepts and a honing of their skills. Integrating practical experiences throughout the learning process empowers individuals with the tools and capabilities to foster competence and achieve mastery in their respective fields.

Conclusion:

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Online English language teachers have good confidence in their TPACK skills. Nevertheless, it is still necessary to support them through professional development programs. To further develop other TPACK domains, supporting them on the TK is critical.
2. Demographics of online English language teachers reveal the TPACK needs of each group. Hence, it is crucial to consider teachers' demographics in setting out a training course.
3. Online English language teachers should be treated as knowledgeable professionals rather than pliable persons. Teachers should be viewed as experts who can search out and supply appropriate solutions to their difficulties. Examining their perspectives and opinions is important to design a better program that can efficiently increase their knowledge and capabilities.
4. The course instructor's competence in pedagogy and content, together with their ability to facilitate online discussions, is considered important for good training. The instructor-student connection and knowledge transfer is seen as more valuable than peer-to-peer conversation.

5. Communication and feedback are still critical components of online courses. Clear and timely feedback from training instructors can humanize distant learning. It develops a personal relationship between the instructor and course participants, possibly increasing the latter's motivation, confidence, and skill retention.
2. TPACK and CoI are helpful frameworks in designing a course for online English language teachers. The convenience of the frameworks allows different studies to alter and contextualize survey items based on the subject of their courses.

Highlights of the Recommended Training Program Blueprint

1. The data gathered from this study proposes building a training outline for online English language teachers.
2. The design includes a training blueprint created by analyzing data and reviewing literature.
3. The training design recognizes that no program is "one-size-fits-all."
4. The training program includes a course description, learning objectives, demographic considerations, and pedagogical standards.
5. The training content aligns with the various components of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK).
6. Written course objectives are outlined for each TPACK category to guide topic selection.
7. The training delivery prioritizes individual training needs and considers teachers' demographic characteristics.

8. A training program blueprint summarizes the training needs based on teachers' unique traits.
9. Technological Knowledge (TK) is identified as the most critical area for all teachers and receives the highest priority.
10. Teachers with low TPACK skill ratings across different demographic categories require comprehensive training in all TPACK domains.
11. Novice teachers require prompt teaching support, while experienced teachers are encouraged to participate for reflection and skill improvement.
12. Key elements for a successful training program include qualified mentors, introductory activities, integration of real-life issues, effective pedagogical practices, curiosity and exploration encouragement, and building participants' confidence through hands-on practice.
13. The training program should offer flexible delivery modes beyond the online format to accommodate different learning styles and circumstances.

Pedagogical Guideline for Online Language Teacher Education Program

1. Online language schools should provide a trained instructor who is well-versed in the subject and conducts classes professionally. The instructor should have strong knowledge of pedagogy and content. In addition, the mentor should also be able to communicate the learner's strengths and weaknesses relative to the course goals. Ideally, the instructor should be an expert in the topic and passionate to the student's work environment.
2. Teaching instruction should emphasize activities that inculcate knowledge rather than their engagement with other participants.

3. It is also crucial to establish camaraderie before the training begins. Allowing individuals to introduce themselves is an excellent way for the learners to participate during the session.
4. Despite the convenience of online instruction, online English language teachers, as learners, still look forward to training not limited to online set-up.
5. Topic content encouraging course participants to imagine solutions to problems through guided activities and debate could make training more exciting. Hypothetical inquiries and preconceived difficulties do not pique learners' interest.

Consideration of the Study

The present study had a limited pool of participants, consisting exclusively of online English teachers. Despite extensive announcements, the response rate from online English language teachers was relatively low, emphasizing the voluntary nature of their participation. However, the respondents who participated demonstrated a strong interest and investment in the topic, offering valuable insights. Caution should be exercised when generalizing the findings due to the small sample size and lack of participant diversity. Collaborating with online language school providers could have improved the participation rate and provided a more comprehensive understanding of the background and demographics of online English language teachers.

One aspect that should be considered as a limitation of this study is using open-ended questions in the web survey form. While certain respondents provided descriptive explanations, there were instances where the answers remained brief. To mitigate this limitation, incorporating additional word prompts, such as 'how' or 'why,'

could have served as effective reminders to encourage respondents to provide more detailed and comprehensive responses. However, it is important to note that conducting interviews proved an excellent choice in eliciting answers and opinions from enthusiastic participants, which provided valuable support to complement the survey findings.

Recommendations for Future Practice

As one of the beneficiaries of this study, online English language teachers are encouraged to continuously engage themselves in training so that they will be able to acquire and adopt new knowledge, especially on technological aspects where change is constant. This would also be a good opportunity for them to practice metacognition, an important professional development technique. Moreover, online English language teachers should be aware of TPACK in their careers. Rodriguez-van Olphen (2004) states, "When teachers have an understanding of TPACK, they have the foundation to enhance second language learning with a purpose." Thus, it is recommended that teachers themselves should seek out more training in this knowledge area to improve their online teaching competence.

Online Language School companies are also challenged to modify their training programs to match the real needs of their teachers. Assessment of TPACK skills of their teachers will help them identify the skills that need reinforcement. It is also suggested to provide their teachers with training facilitators who are competent and professional for the course. This will not only amplify training attendance but also inspires teacher-learners to become competent facilitators as well. Consequently, it is necessary to evaluate courses and the quality of online course instructors.

In addition, training program developers and/or instructors for online English language teachers should pay particular attention to the patterns that emerge among the ranking of presence, elements, and items for the CoI in this study. Those rankings may boost the teacher-learners' drive to participate in training programs.

Higher education institutes in the country are also recommended to strengthen technology-related courses at school. Due to the rapid expansion and demand for technology in our society, it is inevitable to escape from technology in and out of our field of expertise. Hence, we must prepare our future workforce to be knowledgeable and adept regarding new innovations.

To enhance the training courses' robustness, improving the evaluation phase is recommended. The current evaluation involved only four experienced online English language teachers, which may limit the breadth of feedback received. To address this, it is advisable to include a more extensive and more diverse group of teachers in future evaluations to ensure a comprehensive assessment. This will provide valuable insights into the courses' effectiveness and suitability in real-world teaching scenarios. By gathering feedback from a broader range of online English language teachers and conducting thorough testing, the courses can be refined and customized better to meet the needs and expectations of the target audience.

Recommendations for Future Research

A replication of this study with more cohorts of online teachers, both within and outside the Philippines, may provide us with more data for comparison and further validation. TPACK of teachers in other disciplines, levels, employment, and service status can be a new direction to examine. It may capture data helpful in developing guidelines specific to their group and determining how pertinent TK is for

all online teachers. In addition, future research should examine various factors determining the degree of TPACK. Apart from the factors in this study, teachers' beliefs, attitudes toward technology, self-efficacy, and interests are just a few examples to be included.

More research is also needed to verify the fitness of the training program developed for this paper. A case study on the program's applicability may provide insight into its qualities and shortcomings. In addition, the ADDIE evaluation phase is hoped to be used in future studies as part of the training program project design process. This could be possible with full participation from one online language school. With that inclusion, it is expected that a solid training program would be developed.

In addition, there is a call to do future studies on how to help course instructors develop competence in teaching online. Online training facilitators, as also revealed in this study, have a considerable significance to the training attended by online English language teachers. Thus, it is necessary to look for ways how they can improve the quality of teaching online.

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Appendix 1
Survey Questionnaire

Section I – Verification

1. Have you had teaching experience to adult Chinese EFL learners whose aim is to improve their oral conversation fluency?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

2. Are you currently teaching as an online English language teacher in the Philippines?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

3. Are you currently teaching online through audio or video conferencing?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

4. Which of the following activities do you use in teaching oral conversation fluency to students?
 - a. role play
 - b. opinion sharing
 - c. reasoning gap activities
 - d. puzzles
 - e. map reading
 - f. problem solving
 - g. decision making
 - h. interview
 - i. dialogue
 - j. None of the above

Section II – Demographics

1. What is the name of your current ESL company?
2. Which group best describes your years of experience as an online English teacher?
 - a. less than one year
 - b. 1 – 3 years
 - c. 4 – 6 years
 - d. More than 6 years
3. Which best describes your education?
 - a. Bachelor's Degree
 - b. Master's Degree
 - c. Doctorate
 - d. Please specify: _____
4. Which group best describes your technology skills level right now?
 - a. enthusiastic beginner
 - b. reluctant user
 - c. comfortable user
 - d. confident explorer
4. What is your biological gender?
 - a. male
 - b. female
5. Which age group do you belong in?
 - a. 21-30
 - b. 31-40

c. 41-50

d. 51-60

e. 60 +

6. Please provide your email address if you are willing to participate for the future interview.

Section II – TPACK Survey

Technology is a broad concept that can mean a lot of different things. For the purpose of this questionnaire, technology is referring to digital technology/technologies. That is, the digital tools we use such as computers, laptops, iPods, handhelds, interactive whiteboards, software programs, etc. Please answer all of the questions and if you are uncertain of or neutral about your response you may always select "Neither Agree or Disagree"

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. I know how to assess student performance in a classroom.					
2. I can adapt my teaching based upon what students currently understand or do not understand.					
3. I know how to organize and maintain classroom management.					
4. I know how to assess student performance in a classroom.					
5. I can adapt my teaching based upon what students currently understand or do not understand.					
6. I can adapt my teaching style to different learners.					
7. I can assess student learning in multiple ways.					
8. <i>I know how to motivate students and show enthusiasm and interest.</i>					
9. <i>I know how to encourage knowledge construction based upon learners' prior knowledge and life experience.</i>					
10. <i>I know how to facilitate and maintain interactive discussion and information exchange.</i>					
11. <i>I know to respect and consider cultural differences.</i>					
12. <i>I can clearly request information and ask questions.</i>					
13. <i>I can maintain a warm, friendly, and inviting collegial atmosphere</i>					
14. I know how to solve my own technical problems.					
15. I can learn technology easily.					
16. I keep up with important new technologies.					
17. I frequently play around the technology.					

18. I know about a lot of different technologies.					
19. I have the technical skills I need to use technology.					
20. <i>I can access various technological resources and tools, such as email, Internet browsers, LMSs, text and video chat applications, and productivity software and applications.</i>					
21. <i>I can understand the learning and teaching capabilities and limitations of these tools.</i>					
22. <i>I am alert to the latest updates and renovations of educational technology and software.</i>					
23. I have sufficient knowledge about English language teaching					
24. I can use a literary way of thinking.					
25. I have various ways and strategies of developing my understanding of English language teaching .					
26. <i>I can express and master extensive knowledge of the content.</i>					
27. <i>I know how to link the subject and content with scientific, social, cultural, and any other relevant phenomena</i>					
28. <i>I can use sufficient and commonly understandable language.</i>					
29. <i>I can facilitate and maintain interactive discussion and information exchange.</i>					
30. I can select effective teaching approaches to guide student thinking and learning in the English language .					
31. I know about technologies that I can use for understanding and doing language learning .					
32. I can choose technologies that enhance students' learning for a lesson.					
33. My teacher education program has caused me to think more deeply about how technology could influence the teaching approaches I use in my classroom.					
34. I am thinking critically about how to use technology in my classroom.					
35. I can adapt the use of the technologies that I am learning about to different teaching activities.					
36. I can select technologies to use in my classroom that enhance what I teach, how I teach and what students learn.					
37. I can use strategies that combine content, technologies and teaching approaches that I learned about in my coursework in my classroom.					
38. I can provide leadership in helping others to coordinate the use of content, technologies and teaching approaches at my school.					
39. I can choose technologies that enhance the content					

for a lesson.					
40. <i>I know how to emphasize the important points using font colors and effects</i>					
41. <i>I can ensure the quality and accuracy of written messages and feedback and detecting typographical and grammatical errors</i>					
42. <i>I can show sensitivity and empathy when communicating online</i>					
43. I can teach lessons that appropriately combine language teaching, technologies and teaching approaches.					

*Note: *Italic blue font texts* are Albrahim's (2020)' online teaching tasks.

Section III – Community of Inquiry

Training online English teachers is effective if

Teaching Presence					
	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
<i>Design & Organization</i>					
1.The instructor clearly communicates important course topics.					
2.The instructor clearly communicates important course goals.					
3.The instructor provides clear instructions on how to participate in course learning activities.					
4.The instructor clearly communicates important due dates/time frames for learning activities.					
<i>Facilitation</i>					
5. The instructor is helpful in identifying areas of agreement and disagreement on course topics that helped me to learn.					
6. The instructor is helpful in guiding the class towards understanding course topics in a way that helped me clarify my thinking.					

7. The instructor helps to keep course participants engaged and participating in productive dialogue.					
8. The instructor helps keep the course participants on task in a way that helped me to learn.					
9. The instructor encourages course participants to explore new concepts in this course.					
10. Instructor actions reinforces the development of a sense of community among course participants.					
<i>Direct Instruction</i>					
11. The instructor helps to focus discussion on relevant issues in a way that helped me to learn.					
12. The instructor provides feedback that helped me understand my strengths and weaknesses relative to the course's goals and objectives.					
13. The instructor provides feedback in a timely fashion.					
Social Presence					
	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
<i>Affective expression</i>					

14. Getting to know other course participants gives me a sense of belonging in the course.					
15. I am able to form distinct impressions of some course participants.					
16. Online or web-based communication is an excellent medium for social interaction.					
<i>Open communication</i>					
17. I feel comfortable conversing through the online medium.					
18. I feel comfortable participating in the course discussions.					
19. I feel comfortable interacting with other course participants.					
<i>Group cohesion</i>					
20. I feel comfortable disagreeing with other course participants while still maintaining a sense of trust.					
21. I feel that my point of view was acknowledged by other course participants.					
22. Online discussions help me to develop a sense of collaboration.					
Cognitive Presence					

	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
<i>Triggering event</i>					
23. Problems posed will increase my interest in course issues.					
24. Course activities will pique my curiosity.					
25. I feel motivated to explore content related questions.					
<i>Exploration</i>					
26. I utilize a variety of information sources to explore problems posed in this course.					
27. Brainstorming and finding relevant information help me resolve content related questions.					
28. <i>Online discussions are valuable in helping me appreciate different perspectives.</i>					
<i>Integration</i>					
29. Combining new information helps me answer questions raised in course activities.					
30. <i>Learning activities help me construct explanations/solutions.</i>					

31. Reflection on course content and discussions help me understand fundamental concepts in this class.					
<i>Resolution</i>					
32. I can describe ways to test and apply the knowledge created in the course.					
33. I have developed solutions to course problems that can be applied in practice.					
34. I can apply the knowledge created in the course to my work or other non-class related activities.					

Section IV– Open Ended Questions

1. What are your personal practices that help improve your teaching style?
2. What is the most important quality to have to become an online teacher?
3. What specific work experience helps you become effective in teaching conversational English in an online setting?
4. What training activities do you believe are meaningful for you?
5. What teaching practices in your training/courses are effective in learning?
6. As a Filipino citizen, what are your Teacher Education Program expectations for online English Teachers?
7. As a Filipino citizen, what else do I need to know to understand what you feel is important to preparing and supporting online English teachers in the country?

Appendix 2

Intent Letter to Potential Online Language Schools

September 22, 2021

Dear _____:

I am currently enrolled in the Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education at the University of the Philippines Open University. I am in the process of writing my Master's Thesis. The study is entitled "**Designing a Training Framework for Filipino Teachers Teaching Oral Conversation Fluency to EFL Chinese Adult Students through Online Conferencing**". I am writing to ask for your participation and support for my study.

You may partake in the study by (1) answering the given questions below **and/or** (2) endorsing the survey link to your online teachers. Your valuable answers to the given questions below will confirm and understand the context of your online school set up in the Philippines. You may directly send the answers by replying to this email.

List of Questions:

- What are your hiring requirements?
- How many online English teachers do you currently have?
- Do you provide training for your teachers?
- How do you deliver online language teaching services?
- Do you offer online English language teaching for conversational fluency?
- Do you use communicative language teaching activities such as role-playing, opinion-sharing, dialogue, etc., to teach conversational fluency?

In addition, I hope that the administration will help increase the response rate of this study by endorsing the web survey link to your online teachers. The said survey is available on this site: <https://forms.gle/FktsqbGo7VBpH5it9> . The survey results will be pooled for the thesis project, and individual results of this study will remain confidential and anonymous. Should this study be published, only pooled results will be documented. No costs will be incurred by either your school or the individual participants.

Your participation and support for this study will be greatly appreciated. If you have any questions or concerns, you may contact me at my email address: emmalyn.balon@upou.edu.ph.

Kindly acknowledge the receipt of this email.

Sincerely yours,

Emmalyn G. Balon
MA LLE Student
University of the Philippines – Open University

Approved by:

Prof. Janette H. Malata-Silva, PhD
Thesis Adviser

Appendix 3

Email to Volunteer Respondents (Interview Phase)

Dear Respondent,

First of all, I would like to thank you for taking the time answering the survey for the thesis entitled: Designing Training Framework for Online English Language Teachers. To further understand the gathered survey results, I will be conducting an interview session online. This is a one-to-one interview and discussion on matters related to designing the training program for Online English language teachers. In connection, I am reaching out to ask for your confirmation for the said interview. Kindly inform me of your decision by answering the [survey form](#).

Survey form link: <https://forms.gle/xTLTkL9StQL1g5Cq9>

If you have any questions, you may directly reply to this email or through my Skype **emma.well**.

Thank you very much for your time and support. Keep safe always.

Sincerely yours,

Emmalyn G. Balon
Researcher - UPOU

Interview Confirmation

Greetings of Peace and Wellness!

Dear Respondent,

I am grateful of your willingness to participate for the interview phase of this study. To reiterate, I am currently writing a thesis entitle: "Designing a Training Framework for Filipino Teachers Teaching English through Online Conferencing". The study explores the training needs and pedagogical preferences of Filipino online English language teachers. The participant must be a practicing Filipino online English as Foreign Language (EFL) teacher utilizing audio-/video conferencing.

Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. If you refuse to participate or wish to withdraw from the study, it will not bear any effect to any relationship with the researcher and will not involve any loss of benefits or penalty. You are also free to withdraw from the study at any time. If you wish to withdraw, you may contact the researcher.

Your participation is not expected to cause any harm to you. You will not receive any monetary or material compensation for your participation.

All information you will provide will be strictly kept confidential and preserved to maintain the privacy and confidentiality of results. Information taken from the study will be presented anonymously, and no names and email addresses will be presented in the data. Any information that could be used against you and used to identify you will be kept secured. The results will be used solely for research purposes.

By submitting this form, you are indicating that you have read and understood the description of the study.

If you have any questions regarding the study or about your rights as a research participant, or should you wish to have a copy of the consent form, you may contact the researcher at emmalyn.balon@upou.edu.ph

Thank you in advance for your participation.

Respectfully yours,

Emmalyn G. Balon
Researcher

emmalyn.balon@upou.edu.ph (not shared) [Switch account](#) [Draft restored](#)

*** Required**

Are you willing to participate for the interview session through online conferencing for this study? *

Yes

No

Next Page 1 of 2 Clear form

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Google Forms

Interview Confirmation

emmalyn.balon@upou.edu.ph (not shared) [Switch account](#) [Draft restored](#)

*** Required**

Interview Details

Note: This is a one-to-one interview session which is expected to last for about 30 minutes or less. It will be conducted through your preferred video-calling software. It would be best if you can provide your a preferred schedule so I can find the most convenient time for both us.

Email Address *

Your answer

Available Time for the Interview *

Your answer

Video-calling Software Preference *

Skype

Zoom

Google Meet

VooV

Other: _____

Please provide details of your meeting room details (e.g. Skype ID, meeting code and password) *

Your answer

Any concern/s

Your answer

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Appendix 4

Demographics of the Respondents

Respondent Number	Current ESL Company	Biological Gender	Age	Teaching Experience as Online English Language Teacher	Educational Attainment	Course/ Degree	Technological Skill
1	51Talk	Female	31-40	1-3 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSEd - Science	Confident explorer
2	CCClass	Female	31-40	4-6 years	Bachelor's Degree	BA in English	Comfortable user
3	51Talk	Female	21-30	> 6 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSBA	Comfortable user
4	51Talk	Female	21-30	< 1 year	Bachelor's Degree	BS Hospital Management	Confident explorer
5	51Talk	Male	31-40	> 6 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSEd – Business Technology	Confident explorer
6	51Talk	Female	21-30	1-3 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSEd – English	Comfortable user
7	51Talk	Female	31-40	1-3 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSEd – English	Confident explorer
8	51Talk	Female	31-40	< 1 year	Master's Degree	MBA	Comfortable user
9	AcadSoc	Female	21-30	4-6 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSEd	Confident explorer
10	51Talk	Female	31-40	< 1 year	Bachelor's Degree	BS Elementary Education	Comfortable user
11	AcadSoc	Female	21-30	1-3 years	Bachelor's Degree	BSBA	Confident explorer
12	51Talk	Female	31-40	1-3 years	Bachelor's Degree	BS Elementary Education	Confident explorer
13	51Talk	Female	21-30	1-3 years	Master's Degree	ME – Guidance & Counseling	Comfortable user
14	51Talk	Female	21-30	1-3 years	Bachelor's Degree	BS in Industrial Engineering	Comfortable user
15	51Talk	Female	31-40	< 1 year	Bachelor's Degree	BS Elementary Education	Comfortable user

Appendix 5

TPACK Survey Results

	PK	TK	CK	PCK	TCK	TPK	TPACK	Overall
1	4.90	4.78	4.80	5.00	5.00	4.92	4.91	4.88
2	5.00	4.56	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.96	4.95	4.90
3	4.80	3.67	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.79	4.86	4.51
4	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.75	4.81	4.98
5	5.00	5.00	4.80	5.00	5.00	4.96	5.00	4.98
6	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.92	5.00	4.95
7	4.40	4.22	4.20	4.00	4.00	4.71	4.00	4.34
8	4.60	4.22	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.13	4.00	4.10
9	5.00	4.44	4.60	4.33	5.00	4.21	4.00	4.68
10	4.30	3.78	4.00	4.67	5.00	4.88	5.00	4.41
11	4.50	4.22	4.40	4.67	4.00	4.58	4.00	4.32
12	4.40	4.33	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.08	4.00	4.17
13	5.00	4.11	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.42	5.00	4.73
14	3.90	3.44	3.00	4.00	3.00	4.17	3.00	3.54
15	4.00	3.22	3.20	3.33	3.00	3.29	3.00	3.37
OVERALL	4.65	4.27	4.40	4.53	4.33	4.46	4.40	4.46

Appendix 6

TPACK Survey Results by Demographics

Gender	# of R	PK	TK	CK	PCK	TCK	TPK	TPACK	OVERALL
Male	1	5	5	4.8	5	5	5	5	4.98
Female	14	4.63	4.21	4.37	4.5	4.29	4.42	4.36	4.42

Educational Attainment	# of R	PK	TK	CK	PCK	TCK	TPK	TPACK	OVERALL
Bachelor	13	4.63	4.28	4.38	4.54	4.38	4.49	4.38	4.46
Master	2	4.80	4.17	4.50	4.5	4	4.25	4.50	4.41

Degrees	# of R	PK	TK	CK	PCK	TCK	TPK	TPACK	OVERALL
Non-Education	5	4.56	4.11	4.28	4.53	4	4.17	4.20	4.29
Education	10	4.70	4.34	4.46	4.53	4.50	4.60	4.50	4.54

Teaching Experience	# of R	PK	TK	CK	PCK	TCK	TPK	TPACK	OVERALL
Less than 1 year	4	4.48	4.06	4.05	4.25	4.25	4.17	4.25	4.21
1-3 years	7	4.59	4.3	4.34	4.52	4.14	4.40	4.29	4.42
4-6 years	2	5	4.5	4.80	4.67	5	4.88	4.50	4.79
More than 6 yrs	2	4.90	4.33	4.90	5.00	4.50	4.79	5	4.74

Age	# of R	PK	TK	CK	PCK	TCK	TPK	TPACK	OVERALL
21-30	7	4.74	4.27	4.57	4.71	4.29	4.51	4.43	4.53
31-40	8	4.58	4.26	4.25	4.38	4.38	4.41	4.38	4.39

Technological Skill	# of R	PK	TK	CK	PCK	TCK	TPK	TPACK	OVERALL
Comfortable User	8	4.58	4	4.28	4.50	4.13	4.31	4.38	4.31
Confident Explorer	7	4.74	4.57	4.54	4.57	4.57	4.62	4.43	4.62

Appendix 7

Community of Inquiry Survey Result per Respondent

Presence	Teaching Presence			Social Presence			Cognitive Presence				OVERALL
Elements	Design & Organization	Facilitation	Direct Instruction	Affective Expression	Open Communication	Group Cohesion	Triggering Event	Exploration	Integration	Resolution	
Respondent 1	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.33	3.67	3.33	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.68
Respondent 2	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Respondent 3	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Respondent 4	4.75	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.33	4.33	4.33	5.00	5.00	4.67	4.76
Respondent 5	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Respondent 6	4.50	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.33	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.88
Respondent 7	4.25	4.17	4.67	4.33	4.33	4.33	4.33	5.00	4.33	4.00	4.35
Respondent 8	4.25	4.50	4.00	3.33	4.00	3.67	4.33	4.67	4.33	5.00	4.24
Respondent 9	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.67	4.67	4.00	4.33	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.53
Respondent 10	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	3.67	3.67	4.67	4.00	4.33	4.33	4.44
Respondent 11	4.75	4.50	5.00	4.33	4.67	4.33	5.00	4.67	4.00	4.33	4.56
Respondent 12	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.33	4.00	4.00	4.03
Respondent 13	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Respondent 14	3.25	3.00	3.00	3.33	4.00	3.33	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.18
Respondent 15	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.33	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.68
OVERALL	4.65	4.68	4.71	4.49	4.49	4.33	4.51	4.58	4.47	4.49	4.55

Appendix 8

Community of Inquiry Survey Result per Presence Statement

Teaching Presence

Categories	#	Item Statement	M	SD
Design and Organization		The instructor...		
	1	clearly communicated important course goals.	4.6	.63
	2	clearly communicated important course topics.	4.6	.63
	3	provided clear instructions on how to participate in course learning activities.	4.6	.61
	4	clearly communicated important due dates/time frames for learning activities.	4.7	.45
Facilitation	5	was helpful in identifying areas of agreement and disagreement on course topics that helped me to learn.	4.73	.59
	6	was helpful in guiding the class towards understanding course topics in a way that helped me to clarify my thinking.	4.73	.59
	7	helped me to keep course participants engaged and participating in productive dialogue.	4.6	.61
	8	helped me keep the course participants on task in a way that helped them to learn.	4.6	.63
	9	encouraged course participants to explore new concepts in this course	4.73	.59
	10	Instructor actions reinforced the development of a sense of community among course participants	4.6	.63
Direct Instruction	11	helped me to focus discussion on relevant issues in a way that helped me to learn.	4.67	.61
	12	provided feedback that helped me to understand my strengths and weaknesses relative to the course' goals and objectives	4.73	.59
	13	provided feedback in a timely fashion.	4.73	.59
Overall			4.68	

Social Presence

Categories	#	Item Statement	M	SD
Affective Expression	14	Getting to know other course participants gave me a sense of belonging in the course	4.73	.59
	15	I was able to form distinct impressions of some course participants.	4.6	.63
	16	Online or web-based communication is an excellent medium for social interaction.	4.13	.99
Open communication	17	I felt comfortable conversing through the online medium.	4.33	.72
	18	I felt comfortable participating in course discussions.	4.66	.48
	19	I felt comfortable interacting with other course participants	4.46	.63
Group cohesion	20	I felt comfortable disagreeing with other course participants while still maintaining a sense of trust.	4.20	.77
	21	I felt that my point of view was acknowledged by other course participants.	4.33	.81
	22	Online discussion helped me to develop a sense of collaboration.	4.46	.63
Overall			4.44	

Cognitive Presence

Categories	#	Item	Mean	SD
Triggering Event	23	Problems posed increased my interest in course issues.	4.33	.61
	24	Course activities piqued my curiosity.	4.6	.63
	25	I felt motivated to explore content related questions.	4.6	.63
Exploration	26	I utilized a variety of information sources to explore problems posed in this course.	4.47	.63
	27	Brainstorming and finding relevant information helped me to resolve content related questions.	4.6	.61
	28	Online discussions were valuable in helping me appreciate different perspectives.	4.6	.63
Integration	29	Combining new information helped answer questions raised in course activities.	4.53	.63
	30	Learning activities helped me to construct explanations/solutions.	4.46	.63
	31	Reflection on course content and discussions helped me understand fundamental concepts in this class.	4.4	.63
Resolution	32	I can describe ways to test and apply knowledge created in this course.	4.53	.63
	33	I have developed solutions to course problems that can be applied in practice.	4.46	.63
	34	I can apply the knowledge created in the course to my work or other non-class related activities.	4.46	.63
Overall			4.51	

Appendix 9

Responses to Open-Ended Questions

Question:	What are your personal practices that help improve your teaching style?
Respondent 1	Engaging in regular professional development programmes or training is a great way to improve your teaching style.
Respondent 2	I have been teaching as an ESL teacher for more 5 than years now. My best practice is being flexible with my teaching style to different learners.
Respondent 3	I listen to audiobooks to help me improve my listening skills.
Respondent 4	Being a technology oriented teacher helped me improve my teaching style. Knowing my students a little and playing some fun activities to break the ice among students.
Respondent 5	I am willing to accept new suggestions. I am open to learning new things.
Respondent 6	Through teaching everyday
Respondent 7	Being open minded and learning more on technology since education and science is evolving and attention span has changed overtime; I am open-minded on learning more about technology since education is evolving too.
Respondent 8	My ability to mimic other online teacher's strategies thru online videos
Respondent 9	Reading the material and brainstorming before class.
Respondent 10	I usually watch different videos of other teachers on how to conduct a certain topic. Then, I apply some of the strategies that I learned from them and other strategies that I know would also benefit my students.
Respondent 11	Reviewing the material or lesson before the class.
Respondent 12	Being a classroom teacher for 17 years became an advantage in online teaching. Flexibility, resourcefulness, initiative are only some of the keys to make a job well done.
Respondent 13	reading and exposure to English media
Respondent 14	Discovery learning and learning by doing
Respondent 15	I watched videos of seasoned online teachers. I attended trainings.

Question:	What is the most important quality to have to become an online teacher?
Respondent 1	Teaching Expertise
Respondent 2	You have to be patient and emphatic to your students. The best way for students to be motivated in learning is to be the motivator ourself.
Respondent 3	Flexibility, creativity and sincerity.
Respondent 4	Patience and Skills- pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary
Respondent 5	We should not be sensitive and we should be more open minded.
Respondent 6	You have to more patient and innovative.
Respondent 7	Patience, dedication and empathy
Respondent 8	Patience
Respondent 9	Patience
Respondent 10	For me, the most important quality to have to become an online teacher is patience.
Respondent 11	Being fun, engaging and honest to the learner.
Respondent 12	Adaptability to change and patience are what I think as the most important quality as an online teacher.
Respondent 13	knowledge, empathy, flexibility, and language skills
Respondent 14	Should be creative to catch the attention of students. Like using toys, cozy background, flash cards, different kind of voices and total physical response. The internet connection should be stable.
Respondent 15	Making the students feel comfortable. Letting them feel that you are there to help.

Question:	What specific work experience help you become effective in teaching conversational English in online setting?
Respondent 1	My education together with my teaching experiences help me become effective in teaching conversational English.

Respondent 2	I believe my job itself at present. Working for my company for 5 years helped me hone my skills in teaching through the online courseware and effective teaching platform that our company provides.
Respondent 3	Teaching FREETALK to my adult and teenage students.
Respondent 4	Being a face to face teacher pre pandemic
Respondent 5	My teaching experiences in school. i worked with different industries.
Respondent 6	English as Second language teacher
Respondent 7	Being an online teacher
Respondent 8	I work in a service-oriented job. It helps me to talk with more confidence
Respondent 9	Teaching face to face.
Respondent 10	I can say that it's teaching adult learners.
Respondent 11	Being a front-liner in my previous work, talking to people about products, this help me in the online platform.
Respondent 12	Being a service provider at 51talk. We are trained to become effective English online teacher.
Respondent 13	active involvement in a university school paper during college
Respondent 14	We evaluate our students. The student can give us bad or good feedback.
Respondent 15	Being a teacher by profession.

Question:	What training activities you believe are meaningful for you?
Respondent 1	Hands on training activities.
Respondent 2	All training activities I must say. I get to learn effective strategies and techniques from different facilitators. Topics such as (Giving feedback in and after class , Providing effective extensions, How to handle different level of learners and the like.)
Respondent 3	Teaching demos
Respondent 4	Anything related to a topic that boosts my ability and passion as a teacher ; Well-designed topics that boost my ability and passion as a teacher.
Respondent 5	almost all the trainings i had are meaningful to me because i gained friends.
Respondent 6	Jk12
Respondent 7	Leadership and training seminar, introduction and simulation on new styles of teaching
Respondent 8	TESOL and TEYL
Respondent 9	Training related to the course material. Training contents related to my needs as online ESL teacher
Respondent 10	For me it's conducting the demo. Facilitators have different techniques for me to learn. Hands-on, demonstration, lecture
Respondent 11	Maybe some trainings about technology/backups.
Respondent 12	There were many webinars/trainings offered to us. Example: Understanding Chinese Parents, Strategies to use in teaching kids, engaging students to learn through the use of TPR and Visual materials. Every training course helped me become effective in handling classes
Respondent 13	51 talk training, other trainings on writing for campus journalists
Respondent 14	TESOL
Respondent 15	My education courses reminded me how to deal with students.

Respondent Number	What teaching practices in your training/courses are effective in learning?
Respondent 1	Getting students engagement by role playing, reciprocal questioning, relating lessons to learners interests help me improve my teaching style.
Respondent 2	I notice that students enjoy doing role plays during the class, this will encourage them to practice their fluency as well. I think the most effective way is to let the student speak more and be a good listener then corrections will follow (do not interrupt or correct students when they are still talking because most of them will be discourage to speak more.)
Respondent 3	Active listening and responding to students' concerns. Correcting mistakes.

Respondent 4	I think every practice in our training course helped me become a teacher that provides effective learning
Respondent 5	Interactive lecture.
Respondent 6	The training itself helps me to become a good online teacher.
Respondent 7	Use of variety of medium for teaching to encourage student participation
Respondent 8	Guide on how to teach English to young learners
Respondent 9	Games are effective in language learning.
Respondent 10	Demonstration
Respondent 11	Activities and those related games that will help the learner remember the lesson.
Respondent 12	Almost all trainings were effective in actual teaching.
Respondent 13	grading language, rapport, effective error correction. I think every practice in our training course helped me become a teacher that provides effective learning
Respondent 14	Vocabulary drills, Learning by practice;
Respondent 15	The training itself helps me to become a good online teacher.

Question:	As a Filipino citizen, what are your Teacher Education Program expectations for online English Teachers?
Respondent 1	Professionalism. It goes without saying that students expect their teacher to be professional.
Respondent 2	It is important that an online English teacher should have the fundamental knowledge in teaching. I believe taking international trainings and being certified in TESOL or TEFL is also very important.
Respondent 3	With good internet connection and learning equipment, online education is effective. Without them, this kind of program would be nonsense. ; knowledgeable on online education
Respondent 4	I expect that Teacher Education Program could foster enhancement and develop life long learning skills
Respondent 5	TEFL and TESOL
Respondent 6	Efficient training
Respondent 7	I expect flexibility, open mindedness and eagerness to learn more in order to deliver quality education
Respondent 8	Fluency in English and the ability to relate the topic to real life situations;
Respondent 9	Learning the course material and added training is expected.
Respondent 10	I expect that there could be more trainings that would help online ESL teachers to enhance their teaching skills more. Facilitators who know whats going on in online classes
Respondent 11	Being recognized, as well as respected by other professionals.
Respondent 12	You must be computer savy and be equipped with the different tools you can use in teaching.; Mentor that can guide us on distance education
Respondent 13	progressive; contemporary; modern training; updated
Respondent 14	TESOL certified
Respondent 15	Creative. Just like inside the classroom wherein we have to have enegizers,drills, motivation,games and songs.

Question:	As a Filipino citizen, what else do I need to know to understand what you feel is important to preparing and supporting online English teachers in the country?
Respondent 1	It is important that we have trainings about newest digital tools to teach online to make our lesson fun and more engaging.
Respondent 2	We have to encourage and support especially new online English teachers by giving them bird's eye view about the foreign culture of their students and share effective teaching strategies they can be used in their classes. Workshops and trainings are necessary to familiarize what kind of technology that will be use in conducting online classes.
Respondent 3	With good internet connection and learning equipment, online education is effective. Without them, this kind of program would be nonsense.
Respondent 4	I think it is better to understand that every Filipino can be a good teacher if given an opportunity. What of the factors affecting teachers in preparation to teaching English is the environment of the work place, especially at home, where not every teacher has an access to a quiet environment— resulting to a lessen quality of delivery of the lesson.
Respondent 5	You should know that teachers in the Philippines have different teaching experiences that means teachers have different salary grade.
Respondent 6	To b a English Teacher in my country of course you have to be very patient, innovative, efficient
Respondent 7	Stronger internet connection and provision of appropriate equipment
Respondent 8	Efficient technology - laptop, internet connection etc
Respondent 9	Time management and equipment needed in teaching.
Respondent 10	I think it is important that ESL online teachers need to be mentally and emotionally prepared because most of the time, teaching online is more stressful than teaching in a normal classroom set up. You have no total control of the situation specially if the student is not participative, impatient, rude or can't comprehend well.
Respondent 11	I think it is the feeling of having enough resources, also by giving importance to online platform considering that this is somehow essential nowadays.
Respondent 12	I need to know what the government's stand to ESL teachers. Some were not compensated properly.
Respondent 13	training opportunities

Respondent 14	By sponsoring them if have financial capabilities
Respondent 15	We need trainings, tools, equipments.

Appendix 10

Coding Analysis – Open Ended Questions per Demographic Factor

Bachelor's Degree vs Master's Degree

What are your personal practices that help improve your teaching style?

What is the most important quality to have to become an online teacher?

What specific work experience help you become effective in teaching conversational...

What training activities you believe are meaningful for you?

What teaching practices in your training/courses are effective in learning?

As a Filipino citizen, what are your Teacher Education Program expectations

As a Filipino citizen, what else do I need to know to understand what you feel is important to preparing and supporting online...

Education vs Non-Education

What are your personal practices that help improve your teaching style?

What is the most important quality to have to become an online teacher?

What specific work experience help you become effective in teaching conversational English in online setting?

What training activities you believe are meaningful for you?

What teaching practices in your training/courses are effective in learning?

As a Filipino citizen, what are your Teacher Education Program expectations

As a Filipino citizen, what else do I need to know to understand what you feel is important to preparing and supporting online...

Years of Teaching Experience

What are your personal practices that help improve your teaching style?

What is the most important quality to have to become an online teacher?

What specific work experience help you become effective in teaching conversational English in o...

What training activities you believe are meaningful for you?

What teaching practices in your training/courses are effective in learning?

As a Filipino citizen, what are your Teacher Education Program expectations

As a Filipino citizen, what else do I need to know to understand what you feel is important to prep...

Age

What are your personal practices that help improve your teaching style?

What is the most important quality to have to become an online teacher?

What specific work experience help you become effective in teaching conversational English in onlin...

What training activities you believe are meaningful for you?

What teaching practices in your training/courses are effective in learning?

As a Filipino citizen, what are your Teacher Education Program expectations

As a Filipino citizen, what else do I need to know to understand what you feel is important to preparing...

Technological Expertise

What are your personal practices that help improve your teaching style?

What is the most important quality to have to become an online teacher?

What specific work experience help you become effective in teaching conversational English in onlin...

What training activities you believe are meaningful for you?

What teaching practices in your training/courses are effective in learning?

As a Filipino citizen, what are your Teacher Education Program expectations

As a Filipino citizen, what else do I need to know to understand what you feel is important to preparing...

Appendix 11

Interview Questions

1. Briefly explain or narrate how do you teach English conversational fluency to adult Chinese EFL learners.
2. What skill (e.g. teaching, interpersonal, computer, management, etc) do you have that set as an advantage in teaching English conversational fluency online?
3. How does your personality help you become effective in teaching conversational fluency in an online setting?
4. What are the new skills you have gained in your profession as an online EFL teacher teaching conversational fluency?
5. How did you learn the said skill/s?
6. What is the most challenging task in teaching conversational fluency in an online set up?
7. What hampers you to become an effective online English teacher? How does that hinder you from success?
8. What is the most challenging task in online English language teaching? Why?
9. What are the teaching practices in your professional development programs or training that help you learn effectively?
10. What teaching courses are you looking forward to in your professional development programs?
11. How should professional development programs or training be given to online English language teachers?
12. How do you define Confident Explorer/Comfortable User?

Appendix 12

Interview Transcription

Interviewer:	Hi, Teach! Good afternoon. How are you po?
Respondent 1:	Ok lang po. Kumusta?
Interviewer:	Mabuti din naman, Teach. Teach, thank you for participating for the study and having this interview today. Can you see me and hear me well, teach?
Respondent 1:	Yes, teach.
Interviewer:	Teach, before anything else, let me introduce myself. I am Emmalyn Balon, a student from UPOU. I am conducting this interview to for my thesis, I will ask you questions related to the training needs and pedagogical preferences of Filipino online English language teachers. All the information you will provide will be strictly kept confidential and information taken for this study will be presented anonymously. You have the option to switch on or off your camera at any time throughout the interview.
Respondent 1:	Ok teach.
Interviewer:	Also, teach, this will be audio-recorded for later's analysis. Are you ok with that?
REspondent 1:	Yes, teach.
Interviewer:	Do you have any questions teach before we start?
Respondent 1:	Ok lang ba to answer in Tagalog teach?
Interviewer:	Sure teach no problem.
Respondent 1:	Thanks teach.
Interviewer:	Ok teach. What ESL company are you currently employed teach?
Respondent 1:	51talk
Interviewer:	Ok teach. Teach, I'll send a message on the chatbox. Can you confirm if these are still the hiring requirements in 51Talk?
Respondent 1:	Basic Qualifications. technical. Yes teach.
Interviewer:	Thanks teach. Can you provide an estimate number of ah teachers in 51Talk?
Respondent 1:	Sorry teach. Hindi ko alam pero madami kami every time may mga event si 51.
Interviewer:	Ok teach. Do you receive trainings in 51Talk?
Respondent 1:	Yes po. We have a lot of trainings like. um TEYL, and TESOL and NQT.
Interviewer:	What are those teach?
Respondent 1:	TEYL is Teaching English to Young Learners, TESOL is Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages and NQT is Newly Qualified Training. We usually do NQT during our on-boarding. TEYL and TESOL are later na po.
Interviewer:	Okay teach
Respondent 1:	Free pala yong TESOL teach kaso kaso we have to stay in the company for like 2 years para makuha yong certificate or digital copy.
Interviewer:	Oh I see teach.
Interviewer:	Can you narrate teach how do you teach English conversational fluency to adult Chinese EFL learners?
Respondent 1:	Sa amin kasi teach is we have.. we only teach for 25 minutes to one student. The student sometimes has a teaching material or sometimes it's just an empty page. We

	start discussing about the topic. I ask a question then si student will just answer my question.
Interviewer:	What software do you use teach?
Respondent 1:	AC teach. Software ni 51.
Interviewer:	Next question teach. What skill do you have, that set as an advantage in teaching English conversational fluency online?
Respondent 1:	Umm. I think teach yong college education, education degree ko. I find my college education and teaching experiences helpful as an online ESL teacher. Kahit hindi lahat ng napag-aralan ko nagagamit, some strategies are helpful. Naapply ko sa online.
Interviewer:	That's good teach. What is your personality teach, that help you become effective in teaching conversational fluency in online setting?
Respondent 1:	I am. I'm friendly person.
Interviewer:	How does this personality help you become effective teach?
Respondent 1:	Some students can be rude even if it's just your first meeting. Or maybe you know, the student just had a bad day or maybe just the personality of the student. Because I'm friendly, I can rapport with my student. Tapos, we can have good conversation kahit moody si student.
Interviewer:	Are there any new skills you have gained as online teacher teaching conversation?
Respondent 1:	Umm..wait teach ha.
Interviewer:	K teach.
Respondent 1:	I think po teach, it's the he, listening. I'm more of listener now. I give the student more chance to talk kesa sa kin.
Interviewer:	How did you learn the it?
Respondent 1:	We were told teach to give the student more chance to speak. Kaya conscious din ako to limit my words. Like nasa teaching material ilang, mga percentage ako magsalita or si student.
Interviewer:	Ah ok teach. What is the most challenging task in teaching conversational fluency in an online set up?
Respondent 1:	Being knowledgeable. In the platform, you will encounter different kinds of learners. Some are still students and some are professionals like lawyers, engineers. Students are not dumb, but English language is their problem. if you have no idea of what you are talking or doing online, it will be obvious.
Interviewer:	I see, teach. What hampers you to become an effective online English teacher?
Respondent 1:	Ano ulit yon teach?
Interviewer:	What hampers or stops you from becoming an effective online teacher?
Respondent 1:	Umm.. sometimes teach, yong teaching material.
Interviewer:	Can you elaborate teach?
Respondent 1:	Example teach, pinapasunod talaga na ano ipagawa ano yong nasa material but then hindi naman nagagawa ni student, ng bata or di nasunod.
Interviewer:	Ok teach. What is the most challenging task in online English language teaching?
Respondent 1:	Rude students.
Interviewer:	Bakit teach?
Respondent 1:	There are students who would, like say fuck you or show you gun, mag di-dirty finger. It's insulting.

Interviewer:	I'm sorry to hear that teach. Grabe naman yan.
Respondent 1:	Naku teach, marami pa. Ka-stress
Interviewer:	Um, what are the teaching practices in your professional development programs or training that help you learn effectively?
Respondent 1:	For me uh teach, siguro it's the the teacher facilitator. Facilitator display professionalism. If the facilitator is professional, I can say I learn effectively.
Interviewer:	Professional in what sense, teach?
Respondent 1:	Professional in handling the training. Someone knowledgeable on topic , can give variety of tips, knows how to deal with online teachers, on-time.
Interviewer:	Ok teach. What teaching courses are you looking forward to in your professional development programs?
Respondent 1:	I guess.. yong art of questioning at technology.
Interviewer:	Can you be specific on technology teach?
Respondent 1:	I hope to get training on what's the latest digital tools or applications that I can use for my online classes.
Interviewer:	Thanks teach. How do you want to receive your trainings, teach?
Respondent 1:	How do I want to receive?
Interviewer:	Like it's the mode of delivery ng training? online or offline?
Respondent 1:	I'd rather have it.. online teach.
Interviewer:	Why po?
Respondent 1:	Kasi convenient siya like nasa bahay ka lang; pero teach nakakatuwa din pag may mga conferences kami or gathering. May mga learning din ako natutunan doon.
Interviewer:	Oo nga teach noh.
Respondent 1:	Yes teach.
Interviewer:	Anyway, do you? Are you a comfortable user or a confident explorer in terms of .. of technology usage?
Respondent 1:	Confident explorer
Interviewer:	Why or How do you define that in yourself?
Respondent 1:	Um. you are not afraid to to search and try other internet application like I mean software po. I feel excited like in AC po kasi may mga bug siya. Na-ex-excite ako sa new updates. Ano din po pala, gino-google ko yong DIY solution sa PC error ko
Interviewer:	I don't have any questions now teach. But, is there anything you'd like me to know about online teaching and teachers?
Respondent 1:	Umm..wala naman teach.
Interviewer:	Ok teach. Yun lang po teach. Maraming salamat po sa time ninyo.
Respondent 1:	Welcome teach.
Interviewer:	Sige teach, bye po
Respondent 1:	Bye teach.

Interviewer:	Hello. Good morning po! This is Emma.
Respondent 2:	Hi!

Interviewer:	Thank you for participating for the study and doing the interview today. Can you see me and hear me clearly?
Respondent 2:	Yes, Miss.
Interviewer:	Before we start the interview, let me introduce myself. I am Emmalyn Balon, a student from UPOU. I am conducting this interview to ask you questions related to the training needs and pedagogical preferences of Filipino online English language teachers. All the information you will provide will be strictly kept confidential and information taken for this study will be presented anonymously. You have the option to switch on or off your camera at any time throughout the interview. Do you have any questions before we start?
Respondent 2:	No, Miss.
Interviewer:	Ok let's start. What ESL company are you currently employed?
Respondent 2:	Ok lang ba to answer in Tagalog teach?
Interviewer:	Sure teach no problem.
Respondent 2:	Thanks teach.
Interviewer:	Ok teach. What ESL company are you currently employed teach?
Respondent 2:	CC Class
Interviewer:	Ok. I'll send a message on the chatbox. Could you please confirm if these are still the hiring requirements in your company?
Respondent 2:	(silence) Yes, Miss.
Interviewer:	Alright. Can you provide an estimate number of teachers in your company?
Respondent 2:	Around 50 plus teachers? I'm not sure Miss since we have home-based teachers when the pandemic started.
Interviewer:	Do you have trainings?
Respondent 2:	Yah. We have regular trainings. These are given by our co-teachers who are like experts or excelling in one area. Like for example, if one teacher is good at enrichment activities. They will be tapped to give as resource speaker for our training.
Interviewer:	How about other training programs such as TESOL or TEFL?
Respondent 2:	Our company does not provide those training but if we like, we can enroll outside or online.
Interviewer:	What do you mean by you enroll outside or online?
Respondent 2:	What I mean to say is that.. for example, you like to get TESOL certificate, you can enroll in any school offering those courses or you can also study online.
Interviewer:	Ahh I see. Let's have the next question. Briefly explain or narrate how do you teach English conversational fluency to adult...
Respondent 2:	oh..wha
Interviewer:	Ok. I will just send the questions in the chatbox so you can also read them.
Respondent 2:	Ok ok..thanks
Interviewer:	Briefly explain or narrate how do you teach English conversational fluency to adult Chinese EFL learners
Respondent 2:	We do have this app called CCTalk. We do have classes online so we have students from different levels, kids to adults, tertiary to working professionals. We use CCTalk, that is our tool.
Interviewer:	Do you have to teach 25 minutes too?

Respondent 2:	Oh yes.. 25 minutes for adults, 40 minutes for kids.
Interviewer:	How do you teach conversation with the students?
Respondent 2:	We do have two courses for conversation. One is Daily English and one is Business English. So most of my students who are in the university choose Daily English, or students who are in the professional level who would like to practice their fluency, would also choose Daily English. But for working professionals like doctors, teachers, IT engineers and the like, they would definitely choose Business English. We have also in our platform as I said CCTalk. There are already books there. The students choose the book there by themselves.
Interviewer:	Okay. Thank you. Next is, what skill Do you have that set as an advantage in teaching in teaching conversation English?
Respondent 2:	Oh, since we do have, what we have is a teaching inter Yes, computer, I have time management . So just like what the example that you have shown there, but well, for our online platform, Emma, we don't we actually, for adults, we don't have the do classes, all classes are audio. And for about for kids, that's when we get to happen. Video classes, because it would it's very important for children to see you the way you move the way you move your hands do your expression of your face. But for adults, we only get to have like audio classes. So you have to really be good with your pronunciation, your communication skills , everything. It's really very important. Right? And what kind of skills? Yeah, I think you have to be enthusiastic in your class, you also have to be knowledgeable with your lessons . So before the class you have to read you have to review. But since I have been working for my company for five years now, I am quite familiar with the lessons . So it's just it's easy for me. Yeah. Okay.
Interviewer:	So. So do you think that as you go, as, as you advances in yours in the platform, you will gain mastery of the content? And the teaching style?
Respondent 2:	I think so. Yes, I think so. Especially like me, when I get to have classes every day, like 15 to 20 students a day. So you will definitely familiar with different levels . Because everyday they're like level, we have level three to level 12 students, okay, everyday.
Interviewer:	Is it? Because .. is it because the content is all the same?
Respondent 2:	No, actually, the contents there, it's so broad, so many, like, you know, like, for example, in daily English, I think there are like more than 100 topics. So it's not every every class has a different lesson, there are different topics to choose from. And now the company has actually introduced another type of platform, but that is going to be discussed since as you know, the curriculum or not the curriculum, but that there is an ESL policy now in China, that kids aren't allowed to have classes during the weekends, right? Yes. So that's why they're there more business professionals that that our company is trying to, to get especially bought, like, for example, like working professionals in one pharmaceutical company. So how do you call that bundle? Package? Yes. Okay.
Interviewer:	So yeah, thank you for that. It's a new it's a new knowledge or new inside for the thesis and then what is for you? What is the most challenging task? Well, because you gain mastery already, you know, it's, you know, the content or maybe the teaching style, you have that. But what is the most challenging task in teaching conversational fluency,
Respondent 2:	I guess, different types of learners and the online setup now , for actually, when the pandemic started, that is when the challenge really went or came. Like, for example, I used to teach in the office for four years. But because since of a big sense, let me check what want to start. But March, I think it was March of last year 2020, when teachers are all asked to work at home. So it's a new setting, it's a, it's, you have to be very mindful of the surroundings, especially the sound noise . Now that I have a daughter, so I have to, it's more it for the first month, it was kind of Crusher, but now I were I was able to get the hang of it. And it doesn't affect my classes. And I think it's just like, you know, the daily routine that you have just like talking to your students,

	since you said, just like what you have mentioned, mastery. Yeah, I think it's not really that difficult. But for the first few months, when we started to work at home, the transition period, it was very, quite challenging.
Interviewer:	So the challenging thing there is when you switch to when you transition to home, office to set Yeah. Okay. But when it comes to, like, for example, teaching, teaching professional professionals?
Respondent 2:	No, no, no, I don't think so. Maybe the challenge would be for new teachers, if they don't have any background about it. Like when I started working, I think it was very, it was quite tough and challenging, you will meet different students, different personalities. So that's the Yeah, I think that is the challenging part. But for teachers who have been teaching for quite long, I'm sure they were able, like me, like you, you, you know how you know what to do.
Interviewer:	Yeah. And but the content, for example, if you're in beginner, you think you would have a problem, it would be a challenging task for you the content itself, or it's more of the teaching style?
Respondent 2:	I don't think so I think it's more of your strategy as a teacher, your teaching style, your patients, your personality as a teacher, because there are actually students who are just like what I've said, different levels, different learners, different way of coping and learning. So there are students who level three, just you have mentioned, they're so difficult, like, the way they pronounce you have to really be patient. So I guess it's not just a teaching style, but the personality of the teacher. Okay. It's really very important.
Interviewer:	Okay, thanks. Thanks. There's another thing this is still connected, before we go to the teaching programs. I in the in the gathered survey, it shows that on the English language teachers have difficult find, they are very low in terms of technology knowledge. Okay, so what technology knowledge is important for online language teachers?
Respondent 2:	Well, just like what I have mentioned, I think every online teaching ESL company, they have this online platform, right? Just like us, we are using me, we are using CCtalk I think other companies do have those apps also, that their company has provided. So I guess I guess that is the most important thing they have to master that. But aside from that, I think they would not have any difficulties or complication. If that if they will just have to know or I have trainings of how to use their own apps. Alright.
Interviewer:	So it's basically the use of your app it's it's basically the use of that certain program that your company Yes. Okay. So right you don't need to use like for example being so quick in searching on Google or you know, using email
Respondent 2:	again, I'm so sorry. Yeah, we we don't use we do have Microsoft Excel that is just for recording okay. And we do have, we do have, we call this we do after while we are having a class even I think your even your company, when you are having a class, you have that feedback form feedback form, so you do multitasking. So while you're teaching, you're going to write down those corrections or new words and comments recommendations to your student on That on that feedback form. So I guess that is the challenge for some teachers, they have to be, they have to do multitask. They do multitasking, since they only have five minutes. Break right after the class, there will be another student 25 minutes. All right.
Interviewer:	Okay. Yeah, I see. So it must be you're also very good at multitasking while using the technology and teaching at the same time.
Respondent 2:	Yes, it's not that difficult, actually. So, yeah, maybe for new teachers, they are not quite, but after two or three months, I think it would not be difficult for them anymore. Since they will be familiar, everything will like a learning curve. It is a learning curve. Right. Yeah. Okay.
Interviewer:	And then you mentioned also that one has to be test it, you know, the personality, you have to be patient. So, okay, well, even it is known that teachers have to be patient. So but in teaching online, how necessary it is for a teacher to be patient?
Respondent 2:	Or? Well, I? Yes, I think it would, it really requires not just patient, but do you have to

	love what you do. Your passion. The students are, you know, I always believe that it's not just the the lessons that the students will remember, but the way the teacher will let the students feel, if the students feel that they're the teachers are impatient, they will feel that students are very smart, it's this the only the difference, the only thing that is different is the language, but the way we feel is just the same, you know, they will feel if they are if you're sincere, in your teaching or not. So that's why we do have what we call feedback. Every time we have a class, the student will rate you, as a teacher, they will give you five stars for the highest one as far as this as the satisfactory so they can give one, two or three. And that is the satisfaction that will show in your record. And other students will definitely see that because the student will give you a comment. Right? Yeah. Okay.
Interviewer:	So thank you for that. Now. Next, let's have are in teaching conversational English, which is more important. Is it the confidence or the content knowledge?
Respondent 2:	Both? Because if you are if you have, if you're ineligible, if you have content knowledge, but you are not confident in teaching, that student will not believe you. Right, yeah. So I guess that it's really both you have to be confident, but not overly confident. You have to also, you have to also be open to what the students has, or his opinion or views with the topic that you're teaching. Right? So let them let them speak more than you. Right. So when they have to ask you questions about that, that's when you have to be confident to answer those questions. But you have to let them answer what they think about the topic or less the questions. Okay,
Interviewer:	so next one is, yeah, we, we have this already that as you stay longer in the platform, if you have more experience, you will get mastery. Right? So how does it help you develop the teaching skills? Is it because you reflect on it? Or it's just that you? Do you reflect on your teaching style? Each day?
Respondent 2:	No, it just goes with the flow. You know, Emma, the teaching style really varies of who you are talking to, like if you're talking to kids. So the teaching strategy is quite different. When it's just automatic. It's just an it's just, I think it really boils down to like your passion and your personality and teaching students that like the teaching style, it's how you assess the student. That is why there's mastery, because as a teacher, you already know, like, good thing, there's levels. This lesson the students is level three, level four, level five, so you can really assess how what kind of teaching strategy you can use for that student. Okay, yeah, so yeah.
Interviewer:	So it's like binds like, for example, if there's if you see in the record of the child this is level one student you have like, default default knowledge of Oh yeah, I think you're gonna use this kind of strategy when I teach level one kid
Respondent 2:	Ah, yes. Well, I just want to share something with you. Every time we have a class actually, we do have discourse consultant, of course consultant is from from mainland China, the one that assesses the why course consultant like from the headquarters itself. So there is this green bubble. Before we enter the class, there is the alright assess the student, this student is very lost. He doesn't know how to speak like, that isn't confident like that they already assess the students. So the teachers who is going to have that class that student already has the knowledge of how to, to, to have that class to that student. Okay. Yeah. So it's really very helpful. All right.
Interviewer:	So there's also collaboration with consultants.
Respondent 2:	Yes, but they don't have to talk to you anymore. There's just this green bubble, Like, Comment already on the side that this student is like this, like that. And we can also see the feedback of other students or other teachers from that class. Okay, yes.
Interviewer:	Yeah. Okay. So it's like everyone is commenting about this person, and then you can get an idea of who is who or what kind of student would this be?
Respondent 2:	Yes. But the students could not see that they can just Yeah.
Interviewer:	All right. Now, let's thank for that things. And now let's move to the when it comes to teaching the online teachers. Okay, the trainings that you're receiving. Okay, so I have a question here. I like for example, of course, you have your in service training

	days, right. Like while you're in the program. Yeah. So, like, aside from TESOL TEFL what are the one that is offered from your company itself? Do you have that kind of?
Respondent 2:	Yes, we do have/ We also to TESOL TEFL. They offer that. And we always have monthly workshop . All right, every month, we do have that. Just like for example, me last of if I'm not mistaken, I guess I have wrote I have written it for you. I just like for example, strategies for giving instruction that was the workshop that we had just last month. And mine was I have I actually had conducted a workshop for giving feedback , yes, giving feedback for, for learners. Giving feedback is really you know, it's very giving feedback in and after class. So when you say it's during the class and after class, that is very helpful for students to be able to know whether or not they're doing well in their lesson.
Interviewer:	So there's always a workshop or like training everyone. Okay. But for you, you stayed longer. So you, it seems that you are becoming a mentor this time, as well? Yes. So is it like, for example, things in your in your in your company? Like, if you stay longer? Do you still have to attend more? Are there trainings given for you or you would be promoted to someone who will give the training?
Respondent 2:	No, no, it's, it's actually what I like about the company. It's not just because it's not just because you have been working for long you have the chance to to be a mentor? No, it is given to everybody. Teachers are encouraged to volunteer, they can volunteer if they want and, and we do have this ratings like top teacher, top one, top two, top three, top four like that. So those who are in the top left, top teachers, whether they're introvert extrovert, or ambivert, they really the company will let them Oh, since you are the top two, you have to let this you have to take this workshop. Right? You sit here the top three, so you have to really help the author. Yes. So there's no reason to say no, you're bait for that anyway.
Interviewer:	Wow, that's great. So but but if you give the training to them, you're still paid for that? Or?
Respondent 2:	Yes, you're paid for that. All right. That's your bid for that. Okay.
Interviewer:	awesome. All right. So yeah, it's interesting. We and but anyway, for you. So even if you're, for example, then you're six years already or more in the last five years in the platform, you can still attend to trainings, right?
Respondent 2:	Yes, we must. We must, because every trainings is different different teachers every month different speakers. And it's very interesting to hear your colleagues speak for the first time, especially new teachers.
Interviewer:	Do you also get paid for that?
Respondent 2:	or no, no, no, no, no. For those who are not paid, but it will definitely give you points on your KPI key performance indicator , and if you attend that, chances are for getting a bonus. It's very high.
Interviewer:	Okay, see, I get that. Okay, and then so there are also in the survey I gathered. Teaching demonstration is the most common answer that help them help features to learn effectively.
Respondent 2:	What do you mean by teaching demonstrate
Interviewer:	like, for example, if they have trainings, they love their trainings to have teaching demo.
Respondent 2:	Oh, yes, of course. How can we be able to learn if we don't have an example or someone is going to teach us a word like what to do? We do have an S native speakers because the company has teachers from other countries also England, California and others. So the speakers just like yesterday, we had a speaker from from Thailand, but he is British, she he is an American, but his base there and his teaching in high school Jiang, also same company. So he actually taught about the CC cues, concept checking like that. So we get learned from his style like that. So very helpful.
Interviewer:	All right. So it's but it's actually the mentor who will be showing the demonstration or, yeah, okay,

Respondent 2:	the mentor. And also there's what you call like, recordings, because every class is recorded. So the mentor can actually choose best teaching clips, right? That the, the, and we listen, or watch if it's a video class, right? All right, we actually get to watch because, like, the recorded the recordings, just not the voice, but also the screen, the screen is recorded. So we can see oh, this is how she does it. Oh, this is how she give feedback. This is how she Circle Line. Right? Okay,
Interviewer:	I see. But do you also think that Well, do you do also demonstrations like that the attendees? Do they have to do demonstrations as well? Or do you just have to watch the video?
Respondent 2:	No, they're not forced, but they are encouraged us to be put on mic. Okay. And what is nice is, teachers are actually very attentive. But if they're not going to speak, it would be random. You have no choice, you will be put on mic and you have to give an example. Oh, teacher, Dinah teacher, Emma, do this roleplay example. That Okay, I
Interviewer:	see. So now, thanks. For example. Well, you do you receive training? Right? So how do you want your training to be given?
Respondent 2:	Oh, via we, we still use our online platform, all trainings teachings are, are done in our online platform? Yes, cc houzhang. App or CC talk? Okay, so
Interviewer:	you prefer it as online? Not Yes. Your face, not face to face? Why you prefer it online?
Respondent 2:	It is more comfortable. And it is more realistic? Since our classes are done online. Okay,
Interviewer:	I see. What about the design, like, I know, in your, as I am getting an information for me not information, I'm getting an idea from you that, you know, when you give the training, it's like, for example, you're good at this kind of this kind of skill, then you have to share it with other teachers. Do you think that's effective? That's helpful?
Respondent 2:	Or I think so, so far, it is very effective. And it also matters of what kind of PPT or PowerPoint presentation you use. And of course, the speaker has to be knowledgeable of what it's going to teach. If he doesn't know if he is nervous. It's really very obvious. And if it's boring, no, no connection between the teacher and the mentor. I think it's not going to be fun at all. All right, so
Interviewer:	Okay, so there's another thing too teachers from the survey, teachers want to be supported in their mental and emotional state, as online English language teachers, can you? Can you give me an idea about this?
Respondent 2:	Yes, well, we do have this newsletter, every quarter. That newsletter we do have this teacher's teacher corners, where, where me or we as teachers can give our feedback about what topics to talk about, like mental health, how how do you keep yourself from from how to keep yourself sane? While you're working at home, and also we do have this activities like we do have this activities like send videos or competition like that how to what you do at home, to in your break time to be emotionally or mentally be, okay, how to take care of yourself during the pandemic like that. So the company is really doing its best for teachers to not just be productive or be enthusiastic in their classes, but out even or not, even if they're not teaching, right, since there are actually teachers who teaches from 8am to 12 Midnight Okay, so how can they be able to yes, that have that push or encouragement just like you, you're very hard working. I remember you can work like that.
Interviewer:	But not anymore. Yeah. Okay. Yeah. Thank you, then yeah, it's really important that you know, that these things, the mental and emotional state are being supported. And it's good to know that your company is offering this. This seems like unique to me. Yeah.
Respondent 2:	Yes we do have that.
Interviewer:	better than the other company?
Respondent 2:	Well, actually, I don't want to compare it with other companies. Maybe because we do have the survey. Quarterly survey, every time there is teacher survey. Our teachers can actually give comments like suggestions. What will you have, what

	activities you'd like to offer? And yeah, so teachers really good and the management can have a meeting about it.
Interviewer:	That's a very nice management, I guess. Okay. Well, there's another one how I'm not so sure I can get back to the survey. But how do you define yourself? Are you a confident explorer or the comfortable user when it comes to technology?
Respondent 2:	to be honest with you? I'm more of the comfortable user.
Interviewer:	Comfortable user. Okay. Yeah. How do you define it to yourself?
Respondent 2:	Well, I know it's kind of just want to be honest, like, I'm, well, I'm always interested to learning new things like that if it's necessary. But as much as possible, I don't want to have like changes, keep on learning, you know, every time every month, or there would be new changes like that. There's new new things that Oh, my goodness, because you already are used to doing this. And then here comes another thing. Right, but, but that's okay, if you don't have a choice, but as much as possible. I'm comfortable with what I'm using already. So I hope there will be no changes. Yeah, yeah. Because of course, it's you still have, you know, you still have to adjust again or adapt the news?
Interviewer:	Yes.
Respondent 2:	Maybe you change but not frequent, you know, not too frequent up. I am technologically oriented, but I need more support on technology-side because technology has been so quick to evolve now more than ever, and I feel others are more savvy than I am.
Interviewer:	Okay, thanks. This would be the last one, how helpful it is to be connected with other teachers, especially during the training.
Respondent 2:	Okay, well, you know, they're just like, what you just like what we have talked about earlier, there are different types of personalities like extrovert, introvert and ambiverts, right. So you cannot actually force teachers to speak up or talk to you if that is their personality. But of course, expect that as a teacher, you have to, you have to connect with others. That's what you're teaching online, you have to speak. So even if you're an introvert, you have to be an extrovert, you have to really be enthusiastic. So it is very important to have connection with other teachers, especially now because of the pandemic. You have to help each other. I think that's the most important. Yes, and yeah, yes. Let me just have last week for two weeks. I am an assessor, QA assessor, for new teachers, from other companies like I had saw five, one talk and let the like, yes. So they, so I assessed them. And at the same time before their demo, final demo class, we have one part is demo. Like, you have to listen to how they teach. And then you assess them, you give them you give them correction. So as much as possible, I give them all the insights that I can give because they're my co ESL teachers, so that on their final demo, they will be more confident. This is what I'm going to do, especially they're using a different platform. Yes, yeah. So that's what I do, not just for my co teachers, but by CO ESL teachers or whoever needs help. Right? We just have to help each other. Well, so
Interviewer:	you were really have a very wonderful personality
Respondent 2:	All Thank you. That's, yeah, that's
Interviewer:	That's coming up.. coming as a friend but really coming as an interviewer,
Respondent 2:	know, am I the world is annoying. We it's just nice to be of help to others you know, just not as a teacher. But if you could be able to help others especially. We all go through different stages, different stresses and looking for a job right now. It's tough. So why make things complicated? Help each other as you if you can.
Interviewer:	Yeah. Amazing. I wanted to do a standing ovation for you. Okay, so. Okay. Is there anything else you'd like to share? Well, that's it. Thank you. Thank you. Yeah, and we don't exceed our time, but it's okay. Thank you so much. But but maybe you're doing something else too. So I don't want to you know, thank you oh
Respondent 2:	yes okay no problem for preparing them for my last and actually it's my day off today

	it's just that you know after my operation and then again wish Englishwoman so just after the operation so, like Munna I have already rested for quite a while so I have to go back to work again and save. So good luck to your thesis and I wish you that you could be also your thesis could help others, other ESL teachers and everybody I'm sure it will. I'm sure that's
Interviewer:	thats my motivation.
Respondent 2:	Thank you. Keep it up. Okay. Thank you Bye bye. See you soon.
Interviewer:	See you soon. Bye bye.

Interviewer:	Hello.
Respondent 4:	Yeah, can you hear me? Hello? Hello, can you hear me?
Interviewer:	I can hear you. All right. Yeah. Hi, my name is Emma. So thank you so much for coming for the interview.
Respondent 4:	Yes, okay, no problem.
Interviewer:	Okay, so before we start, let me just introduce myself. I am Emmalyn Balon. I am a student from the University of the Philippines Open University. We are doing this interview for as part of a thesis which is entitled designing a training program for online English language teachers.
Respondent 4:	Okay.
Interviewer:	So I will ask you questions related to the training needs and pedagogical preferences of Filipino online teachers. Okay, okay. All the information you will provide will be strictly kept confidential. And the information taken for the study will be presented anonymously. So you can turn on or off your camera anytime. Okay?
Respondent 4:	Sure.
Interviewer:	And this will be audio recorded to for that for that analysis later. Are you comfortable with that?
Respondent 4:	Yes, it's okay.
Interviewer:	All right. Do you have any questions before we start?
Respondent 4:	Well, no.
Interviewer:	Okay, so my first question is what the ESL company are you currently employed?
Respondent 4:	Five, one talk.
Interviewer:	I will be sending you the high requirements in the chatbox. Can you please check or read? If there is are still though, if you just please confirm if these are still the hiring requirements in five, one talk?
Respondent 4:	I think yes, it's the same. I think it didn't change since the I think especially the technical it's still the same day didn't change much. I think it's still the same. Yeah, yeah.
Interviewer:	Okay, can you provide an estimate number of teachers in five one talk?
Respondent 4:	Sorry, but I cannot provide an exact number. But since when I like blogging, and when I go on YouTube before started working for five winter, I searched when I started doing a search about you know, tips online, there are like, there are many online, online ESL teachers from five one talk who, who are who are doing blogging, and I think there are a lot of them already. So I can say there are many online, five one talk teachers, and I also see their conferences. There are so many of them.
Interviewer:	Yeah. Okay, so do you receive trainings?

Respondent 4:	Um, yeah, we receive trainings. Before we start working, we have an orientation training. We also have coaching session. And also TESOL and Teaching English for Young Learners. Yes.
Interviewer:	Can you tell me what what's the coaching coaching session mean?
Respondent 4:	The coaching session is it's actually a q&a with the QA, the quality team, they're gonna they will ask you questions about what happened with this one, you will you will get a coaching session if there is a negative feedback from negative feedback from the student and then, the QA will contact you, they will ask you to attend a coaching session with them. And they didn't ask you why what happened and things like that.
Interviewer:	Alright, so this is not, this is not like a training.
Respondent 4:	It's like more of a reminder, reminder of, of your performance reminding you of oh, you know, the classes.
Interviewer:	So, how about the, you mentioned TYL and TESOL?
Respondent 4:	Oh, yeah. TYL is for young for young learners, if you are, if you want to specialize in teaching the young kids like kids with like in kindergarten, and the tea. So I think it's for everyone, they encourage this, especially if they encourage this to everyone. And I think T Sol is very important, especially if you want to be an online ESL teacher in the Philippines. Because if when you look for a job, if you have a Teasle certificate, it's really an advantage.
Interviewer:	Okay, I see. All right. And my next question teach for you is how do you teach conversational fluency to adult Chinese EFL learners?
Respondent 4:	Actually, our classes are 25 minutes. And we have we teach Chinese students we have very young kids. We also have university students Um, students in high school, we also have adults.
Interviewer:	What courses do you teach for the adults? Like for the university students and the adults that you mentioned?
Respondent 4:	The adults I think, for for for that courses we have i els Business English and free talk. Yeah, I think these are the classes I, I had.
Interviewer:	Okay. So all right. what's what? So I else? Can you tell us more about these courses? Like how do you teach the conversation with them?
Respondent 4:	I else is like, it's like a speaking exercise because it is, you know, there are the, this is this is a test taken by university University students, specially if they want to study abroad, and there is a speaking test speaking part there. And Chinese students wants to practice their speaking. So there's like a question I will give them the question they will give, there will be guide or bullet points of what to say so, and they have to give me the answer fluently. Also, the business English, there's like a dialogue. Like, oh, how to use the business phrases correctly. And in free talk. It's just spontaneous talking. Like just random topics that come to your head. Yes. So that's it. That's the conversate that's how we teach. That's how we we teach the conversation fluency.
Interviewer:	Okay. Um, can you tell me what skill do you have that set us an advantage in teaching English conversation fluency?
Respondent 4:	I think I am. Okay. I, I have I have technology skills? I have technology skills . I I know I, I like to do something with technology, because I'm a vlogger I post videos on YouTube. So I really know how to use effects in you know, I know how to produce videos. So I'm not afraid of I'm not afraid of doing anything on my computer. Okay, and also I think I have I think I have a face to face teaching experience . I, I was I was OFW teacher in other country. And I think that helps me to teach in teaching online. I think that experience also helped me and also my I have a tourism degree . So in tourism, of course, we we are taught how to you know, communicate with other nationalities . So I think that's also helpful when I come teaching online because I don't teach. I don't I teach foreigners I teach other. Like I teach Chinese.

Interviewer:	How does your personality help you become effective in teaching conversational fluency?
Respondent 4:	I am talkative I like to, to I am talkative and I talking a lot. And because I'm talkative, we have a smooth conversation with my student. And it makes my student feel very relaxed and feel welcomed in my lesson. And that, that makes me feel that I am an effective teacher because my student can talk to him he can respond to my questions. And I am also patient like, you know, the students sometimes are distracted in the in the in the class, I don't easily get angry. But of course I try to be patient when that things happen.
Interviewer:	Okay. What are the new skills that you have gained in your profession as an online as an online ESL teacher teaching conversational fluency?
Respondent 4:	I'm sorry, Teacher. Sorry, what is that again?
Interviewer:	What are the new skills that you have gained in your profession in your career now as an online teacher, teaching conversation, you know, to Chinese students?
Respondent 4:	I think now I can understand better how others are speaking I mean their accent. For example. As a teacher, my, for example, some students would say sneak instead of snack. So because of that, I think if you consider that as a skill, I can easily understand now what they mean when they say, Oh, I eat, I eat a snack today. And sometimes, and then I can easily, I just can correct them. Oh, you mean I can eat? I eat snack today, so and then sometimes there have bad pronunciation, but I still understand what they mean to say. And I think that's a new skill I learned in this in this work.
Interviewer:	How did you learn that skill?
Respondent 4:	I'm just the frequent classes because you, I have like, I have students whom, who marked me as their favorite. So every time I have frequent class with them, I noticed the same mistake and the same bad pronunciation. So I know already that they mean to say that word. That mean, they mean to say that, they mean to say the right word, but they were just not able to say it correctly. So it's more of the teaching experience. And usually, you know, if you have variety or different kinds of learners, like the Chinese students, you will get to know the common sound mistake or their sound, they have difficulty in saying the sound. So you know, already some patterns of what sounds are difficult for them, like the letter S, I noticed they have difficulty in saying the S sound or maybe like the R or L. So like, really, they can say, Lily, something like that.
Interviewer:	Okay, so what is the most challenging task in teaching conversational fluency?
Respondent 4:	I think it's the, for me, it's the environment because it's, you know, it's just sometimes the environment, you really need to have a quiet environment when you teach online, because it's one of the complaints that you're gonna get in, in your teaching. So I think that you really need to have a quiet environment.
Interviewer:	What hampers you also to become an effective online English teacher?
Respondent 4:	If I think it's really the environment, because if if you have a quiet environment, the student will not complain about it, you know, you will not get that negative feedback. And you and you don't get the coaching session for that.
Interviewer:	And but what about the content itself? Or the, you know, the teaching strategies?
Respondent 4:	As for me, the contents are easy that you can just add, besides your teacher, teacher's guide, you can read it before the class if you want to. And then And besides the some lessons, or, you know, like, you have that lesson before already, so you're familiar about teaching, I went up for teaching, because I have face to face teaching experience. I can I know how to handle the class. So it's not a problem with me, my problem is mostly on the quiet environment, because there's like dog everywhere, and you cannot control the situation.
Interviewer:	Yeah, the environment.

Respondent 4:	Oh, yeah. And also, also the internet connection , you know, in the Philippines, or internet connection is not so stable. And I think that's also challenging because, especially when you're having a talk, it's, I think it is so difficult, it's challenging, that you have a lesson on, like, for example, you're having a free talk and then your voice is cutting off or maybe your upload, upload, or download speed is too slow or too low, then you cannot hear your student carefully. I mean, you cannot, you cannot really get what they are trying to say because they're cutting off or maybe you are speaking and then you are cutting off to the other end of the students. And so I think that's very challenging. And then you get negative feedback again.
Interviewer:	Okay, um, what are the teaching practices in your professional development programs or training that helped me learn effectively?
Respondent 4:	Okay, let me think about that. I think it's every practice. I mean, I think all the practices that we did in our training, like you know, we have workshop and we have also demonstration , and so we can see that's very effective because you can really remember the mistakes in that teaching demonstration or, or what should be improved in the teaching demonstration.
Interviewer:	I see.. what teaching courses are you looking forward to in your, in your professional development programs?
Respondent 4:	I think it's the well designed topics. Topics that can help me in my can help me in my, my skills and passion as a teacher, like, you know, like understanding by my students, yeah, this kind of courses.
Interviewer:	Okay, um, how should your professional development program or training be given to online English language teachers?
Respondent 4:	Well, I say, online is a is online learning is also good on as a student, but like there, but you will never know what is just boring, you know, to read a lot to read a lot on your own. you don't know if you have the same if it's the same understanding that others that how others get it, and it's self paced. And it's also too long, I feel it's too long. If it's online courses, that's too long. I don't like it. I, I feel that conferences I see in, in the videos on YouTube that they have like this conference, and they they have this conference, and they have reenactments of their classes. And it's funny because they also have, it's, it's funny, and they also have critics are like, how should that be groove or how to make that class more interesting?
Interviewer:	Okay, um, one more question that I want to ask how because you said you're, you have technology skills, but how do you define yourself? In terms of technology use? Are you a comfortable user? Or are you a confident explorer?
Respondent 4:	I say I'm a confident explorer because I, I like to search, I look for, I like to search for reviews about certain gadgets. And also, I looked for activities online that I can use to break the ice during the session. I also research about different gadgets like webcam headset, computer specs, which can best help me to deliver the lesson smoothly, especially when glitches happen.
Interviewer:	Okay, is there anything else you'd like to say?
Respondent 4:	Yeah, it's okay. That's it.
Interviewer:	Alright, so thank you so much, and I wish you have a nice day thing, but participating.
Respondent 4:	No worries.
Interviewer:	No worries.
Respondent 4:	Bye bye.

Interviewer:	Hello.
Respondent 5:	Hello.
Interviewer:	Hi, good afternoon. How are you?

Respondent 5:	I'm doing great. How about you?
Interviewer:	I'm good. Thank you. My name is Emmalyn Balon. And before we start, let me just introduce myself. Okay. Yeah, I'm Emmalyn Balon, I'm a student from UPOU and I am conducting this interview to do for for my thesis and I will ask you questions related to the training needs and pedagogical preference as a Filipino online English language teachers and all the information that you will provide will be strictly kept confidential. And, yes, the information and information taken for the study will be presented anonymously. Okay. All right. Yeah. So you have the option to switch on or off your camera at any time throughout the interview. Okay. Okay. Yeah. And I would like also to thank you for participating for this study, and having the schedule for today.
Respondent 5:	Yeah, sure. No problem.
Interviewer:	Okay. So, anyway, before we start, this will be audio recorded for later's analysis. Are you okay with that? Uh, sure.
Respondent 5:	Sure. It's okay with me. Okay. Sure.
Interviewer:	So, let me ask you the first question. Okay. Right, what ESL company are you currently employed?
Respondent 5:	Well, currently, I'm working in 51talk.
Interviewer:	Okay. That's nice. I will send you a message in the chat box. Can you confirm if these are still the hiring requirements in 51talk?
Respondent 5:	Okay, one second. Let me check. Yes, that's right.
Interviewer:	All right. Okay, so can you provide me an estimate number of, you know, the number of teachers in five, one talk?
Respondent 5:	Um, I guess we are like 5000, but I'm not sure. So I'm not sure I have no idea at all.
Interviewer:	Okay, I see. Alright, and do you also receive trainings in 51talk?
Respondent 5:	Yes, we have a free example. Like, if you are a new teacher, definitely you will be having a training for kids, and also for adults. And then we also have this, if you really want to improve or increase your rate per class, you you will be undergoing, you know, IELTS and TESOL examination, you know, which is given by the company for for you.
Interviewer:	Oh, that's good to hear. Okay, can you get the certificate right away?
Respondent 5:	Well, as far as I know, well, and like, like, in my experience here, no and five, one talk, I waited for like a year or two for me to get this certificate. And that's actually it's a protocol of the company.
Interviewer:	Oh, I see. Okay, so can you tell me how do how do you teach English conversation fluency to other Chinese EFL learners
Respondent 5:	I'm here in our company in 51talk of course, we are given a book most like what one book we have here is actually Business English. So of course, their conversation their conversation part in at the same time, but before we go to the conversation part, we need to discuss first the vocabulary or the phrases that we will be encountering good conversation part. And at the same time, we also have other books. That was I forgot actually, but it has also, you know, conversation part and vocabulary part there. And then we also have free talks. So basically, in free talk lesson, we will be like my like my, like myself, you know, I asked first my student, What topic do they want? Or today's free talk lesson? And then, but sometimes they would just tell me like, it's up to me what questions that I have in mind. So as a teacher, I have to be prepared, you know, questions that I need to ask during the free talk lesson to my student. Alright,
Interviewer:	so you how long would that last? The free talk that you were saying?
Respondent 5:	Oh, the free talk. As we get paid here in five, one talk like 25 minute class. So basically, we should finish the free talk lesson for 25 minutes as well.
Interviewer:	Okay, I see. All right. Thank you for that teacher. And okay, so let me have you do you use software?
Respondent 5:	Yeah, we have AC software, we call it easy software. You know, we're in the queue area to quality analyst or quality assurance, you know, can barge in, you

	know to listen to our Lesson if there are things that we need to improve, or how, you know, how we teach the student, so yeah, we use AC software. But if there are, you know, problems with the software, we will go directly to QQ it's also a Chinese app. Now, you know, to conduct classes
Interviewer:	now, right? Okay. Sure. And, okay, what skill do you have that set as an advantage in teaching English conversation online?
Respondent 5:	Well, I'm teaching conversation is really challenging for me as a teacher, although I am experienced teacher ready, but what skill teaching skills that, you know, really develop, during in this in this kind of situation, I guess my experience , okay. You know, I've been teaching her for like, more than five years now. And aside from, you know, like, like, I, myself, I, I know how to teach Chinese students very well, because I work in China before, but I've been, I teach them like, like, their food, their culture, like, their education, something like that. And also, because of these experiences that I have, I can see that my teaching experience is really an advantage, you know, teaching Chinese students when it comes to teaching English conversation.
Interviewer:	I see. All right. Okay, so I think that would be all A, is there anything else you'd like to add? Um,
Respondent 5:	aside from this, that the teacher experience, I also, you know, I develop also my computer management . And also, like, how fast am I to you know, type, like, on the chatbox? Because we do corrections, like the grammar of the student, like the pronunciation of the student. So, my computer skill is also you know, being developed. Oh, you know, working here in five, one talk,
Interviewer:	okay. What are the new skills? It so is that your new skill that you have learned or
Respondent 5:	are not actually to be honest, before when I was in the university, or maybe in high school? I know how to, you know, type on a computer, but not as fast, you know, that was like, my experience now in typing using typing, like making corrections. But working here, you know, it helps me to improve my typing skill, my computer management skill, you know, like, well, let's say for example, before, like, only 10% With knights, like 80 to 90% improvement. All
Interviewer:	right, that's a great. Okay, and anyway, teach, um, how does your personality help you become effective in teaching conversational fluency?
Respondent 5:	Well, I must say that I am an open minded person, you know, I feel students working, you know, I feel adults, students, working professionals, you know, appreciate if teacher if teachers listen, and sometimes, you know, conversation can lead to out of the blue revelation.
Interviewer:	Yeah, what do you mean of that? So you're open minded. And,
Respondent 5:	for example, let's see, like, like, I was, as I was saying a while ago, like, I have worked in China before. Whenever I ask questions about their culture, and then even, yeah, my code, their culture, they will, you know, really surprise, because, you know, I can give whatever questions, whatever questions or whatever answers they have, I can actually, you know, give opinion. But of course, with respect to their culture, and that's why they not to brag, they love booking my class, like, almost every day, because they are very, they are not so shy, or, you know, shy or they're not afraid to express their selves as well to me, all right, because I can relate to them. Okay, I
Interviewer:	see. Thank you. Thank you, teacher. My next question for you is what is the most challenging task in teaching conversational fluency online?
Respondent 5:	Well, this is a very good question. But you know what, as I was saying during your first question A while ago, like we, we in teaching adults, we have this free topic of free, free, free time. Oh, this is very challenging for me like, no topic to discuss . So as a teacher, you have to be prepared because this kind of thing is not everyone's cup of tea. And there are students who are, you know, either parroting or silent sharing the class . This actually happens for adults as well, because for example, if I asked question to adult student like, having, I mean, his or her English is not really fluent. If your question is not really actually answerable by yesterday, now, they will just say yes or no. So it's really challenging for me as a teacher. But what if, if that student, you know, book to me again, and that student cancel my class, so I guess it would be a lucky day for me.

Interviewer:	All right. Okay. Sure. Okay, and what anyway, what hampers you or what stops you to become effective online English language teacher.
Respondent 5:	Um, to be honest, lack of support . I mean, for example, if I got a negative feedback from a student, let's say, they say that the feedback is all about the teacher is not is not good. And teaching the teacher is very boring, something like that. And then I asked, you know, suggestion from the QA or from the, from, you know, from, from our team, sometimes they're very busy sometimes. Even for example, if I say something about this student, you would not the management would not listen to me. If I give suggestion they do, they do not recognize it. The day much, you know, pretty much attention on students side. Because after all, this is business. Okay. And there's
Interviewer:	them that teacher, yeah, okay. And what is the most challenging task? In online teaching?
Respondent 5:	challenging task? Um, I guess. Teaching levels zero students for me.
Interviewer:	Okay. Oh, zero.
Respondent 5:	And, I mean, let's say let's say teaching kids, we know in China, they're their first language not English at all. They're they speak Mandarin or patois. So, if I have the student, like, four or five years old, they basically they do not, you know, speak English. Okay. So as a teacher, like as a teacher, you have to use simplest words. All right? For and also, you have to do some actions. Okay, well, we call it TPR. Here in five, one talk, I forgot the meaning of TPR. Actually, but yeah, it's TPR. This is a very effective way. So that even though you you speak the simplest word, but if you add the TPR, or the gesture action, I'm sure. It could be a very big help, that sort of the student could actually understand you, what are you trying to instruct them during the lesson?
Interviewer:	Okay, I see. And, of course, teach you have said earlier that you have attended, you know, trainings or trainings offered in your, of course, you have attended one of those trainings. Right? So what are the teaching practices in your professional development programs, or in the trainings that help you learn effectively?
Respondent 5:	Well, I'm so lucky, you know, that five one talk has those operate as those trainings and opportunities for teachers. In that kind of training, we are given a chance to share our insight our, our teachings, teaching skills or teaching strategies, whatever if we have this kind of student, and also during that training, I am willing to accept new suggestions. And I'm open learning to new things. So having that training is really a great opportunity for us here. Teachers and five one talk.
Interviewer:	Okay, thank you. And is there any courses or what teaching courses you are looking forward to in your trainings?
Respondent 5:	Um, I guess teaching level zero students , okay. Yeah, because most of the students here in five one talk we are focusing on kids. All right. So I hope that I will talk with give more trainings for that. Okay. Oh, Though I am experienced teacher ready, as I was saying, I work in China before, but as a teacher I have to be, you know, have to be, you know, I should be open, I should be, you know, I should, there should always be room for improvement . So I should be open for that. Okay, so I guess that, that's it.
Interviewer:	I see. And what about now? How should your professional development trainings given to teachers?
Respondent 5:	I love I really love it because the trainers are very friendly . Okay, it's not.
Interviewer:	So you want it like the trainer should be friendly?
Respondent 5:	You're friendly at the same time. Not authoritative. Because, and yeah, friendly and also, like, open for suggestion? Because I know, yeah. Because, you know, there are some trainers are very strict, like they just depend or dwell of, like, what they want to teach the teachers but I want a trainer, like, who is very open to suggestions from teachers, okay, because as a trainer, I believe so that teach as a trainer, you can aside from your giving information, giving ideas to teachers, teachers have their own ideas as well, that could help you to become an effective trainer. So I hope that the trainer should also be you know, how this willingness to to listen to teachers side or ideas.

Interviewer:	Ah I see. I got another one. Are you? Are you a comfortable user or a confident explorer when we say, like technology or use of technology?
Respondent 5:	Confident I think.
Interviewer:	Okay. Could you please elaborate it? The confident explorer
Respondent 5:	Ok. To me, it is using a laptop. PC. phone or any gadget, you know. I look for ways or means to solve my present problem like example I have computer problem, I you know, where which button to check or end. I understand, um, you know ping, technology terms I mean. Like ping, bot, other details just basic idea
Interviewer:	Okay, I see. All right, thank you teacher. Is there anything else that that you you'd like to add?
Respondent 5:	Um, I guess that's all for now.
Interviewer:	All right. Okay. So that would be all my question. Also, teacher. And thank you so much for participating in this study.
Respondent 5:	I hope I was able to answer all your questions, but if you have, if you're not satisfied at all, you can message me in Skype as well.
Interviewer:	Okay. Yeah, sure. Okay. Thank you so much for that.
Respondent 5:	Thank you, my beach bag Nice to meet you.
Interviewer:	Thank you.

Interview:	Hello, good afternoon.
Respondent 9:	Good afternoon
Interview:	Hi, my name is Emma.
Respondent 9:	Hello
Interview:	Yeah. Before we start, let me introduce myself. Okay. I am Emmalyn Balon, a student from UPOU. I'm conducting this interview for my thesis. I will ask you questions related to the training needs and pedagogical preferences of Filipino online English language teachers. Okay. All the information that you will provide will be strictly confidential. And the information taken for this study will be presented anonymously.
Respondent 9:	All right.
Interview:	You have the option to turn on or off your camera anytime. Okay. All right. So this will be audio recorded. Is that okay?
Respondent 9:	Yeah, sure.
Interview:	Okay, so do you have any questions before we start?
Respondent 9:	That is okay.
Interview:	All right. So let me ask you first, what ESL company are you currently employed? Right now?
Respondent 9:	Im, I'm currently in AcadSoc.
Interview:	Okay, sure. So I will be sending you a hiring requirement from AcadSoc. Can you can you confirm if these are the hiring requirements in your company right now? Or as far as you know?
Respondent 9:	Okay. Yeah, I think it's, it's still, it's still the same.
Interview:	Okay, thank you so much. And do you have an idea, how many teachers do you have?
Respondent 9:	It's hard to say. Because we are home based teachers, and I don't know, if, how many of us in there.
Interview:	Okay. That's not a problem. It's all right. And do you have? Do you receive trainings in your company?
Respondent 9:	Yes, we have some trainings. We have trainings before, before we started, like, before I started working for AcadSoc. I received there are always orientation. And about the process in working here. And I also, have like TESOL certificate, but I have my TESOL certificate before from other ESL company. And yeah, we also have trainings, continuous trainings in AcadSoc about the content of the material, things like that.
Interview:	Okay. So you mean to say you have received before you work for AcadSoc? You already have your TESOL certification? Is that correct?
Respondent 9:	Yes, Yes, that's right.
Interview:	Okay, um, can you tell me how do you teach conversational fluency to adult Chinese EFL learners?
Respondent 9:	We teach Chinese students. We have small kids to adults. We teach them conversation online. We have lessons. There are books that we follow and there are there are dialogue that to read by the student and by the teacher. And we also have talk after or we discuss some reading, like we the student will read the text, and then I will ask them questions and then the student just answer.
Interview:	Okay, how long do you teach in in one class? I mean to say, how many minutes do you teach for every student?
Respondent 9:	We actually have like 25 minutes in our class.

Interview:	Okay. Do you have a software?
Respondent 9:	Um, yeah, we use software.
Interview:	Okay. And do you know, do you have any problem using the software?
Respondent 9:	Um, not really, because they teach us how they give us training on how to use that. Also, before we we start working.
Interview:	Alright, thank you so much for that. So anyway, you have mentioned that you are a confident Explorer in technology. Okay. How do you define yourself a confident explorer?
Respondent 9:	I am confident explorer in using technology because I can, I can explore, I can search for many things online , like, when I have problems, I go on YouTube, and then I try to search I go on looking for alternatives for how to, how to fix my problems. And I also, I'm also not afraid of using new features of, of the software . Like there's, if you know, ManyCam. ManyCam is a very interactive tool video tool. And then you can use it to get the attention of your student. And I think some people are scared to learn it by themselves. But for me, I like to learn independently .
Interview:	Yeah. Okay. So, all right, thank you for that. So what skill do you have that set as an advantage in teaching English conversation fluency online?
Respondent 9:	I think it's my teaching experience , face to face because I'm also an education graduate, I have an experience in teaching face to face and I believe because I know already how to teach . I can I can bring it in the online, online in the online class. And, yeah, that's why.
Interview:	Okay, so that's good to know. Okay, so you're also an education graduate, and what is your personality that helps you become an effective and that you become effective in teaching conversational fluency in online setting?
Respondent 9:	I prepare I think, I am a person who likes to do preparation. So I am organized and I organize my thoughts before I start my class I, I get ready. I prepare myself and I prepare also the things that I want to ask for the students that really like I want to, I want to I prepare, I prepare what questions to ask to them. And I think, yeah, I just do that. And when I, I guess if that helps me effect becomes effective because I, I, I can easily transition my questions from I can easily transition one topic to another topic. And my student feels there's no dead air in the lesson. And I feel they are happy about that.
Interview:	Okay, um, my next question teacher is that what are the new skills that you have gained in your profession as an online ESL teacher? Teaching conversational fluency?
Respondent 9:	Um, I guess it's more of a using of technology, and I mean, adapting, adapting to technology , like I can switch because I have an experience in face to face . I know how to motivate my students also online I can use again give them stickers, and I show it online to them. And then I know I can adapt I think that's that's I believe that key that the new skill change my methods from face to face to a new to online set up . Okay. And I have also learned how to how to use games in my lessons online.
Interview:	Okay, all right. And what is the most challenging task in teaching conversational fluency?
Respondent 9:	Um, I think it's the most challenging. I think if there's no topic , because, you, I, as I said, as I said before, I like to organize my thoughts. And then if suddenly there's like no topic to, to talk about in the lesson. It's just challenging because you really have to think , first, what's the interest of the student? And we have a variety of students online. And sometimes you can just guess their interest. Or maybe if I have, if I have a question in mind, like, favorite, favorite food favorite animal, or, or anything about favorites, or dead carbon topics, I'm afraid that other teachers have asked up already. And it's challenging to think of my students interest. Like, I don't just don't know what they What's your interest beforehand, and there's no topic and I have to think about it, I have to make a smart guess.
Interview:	Okay, the question is, what hampers you to become an effective online English

	teacher? And how does that stop you from to your success?
Respondent 9:	um, I still have a problem with a time management, time management, because I'm in online class, it's 25 minutes, and I'm there, the sometimes the books are too long, and you have to enter or times the student have to talk a lot. And, and you also, and you also, you're also carried away in the topic or in the discussion, and suddenly the time has passed. And you cannot give a good wrap up a good conclusion for your lesson. And I think that stops me from being effective because there's, I'm not sure if the student is satisfied with you know, just just no wrap up. No conclusion. Also, I think, one another thing is about the technology, I mean, the equipment, because if you're an online teacher, you really need to have a good equipment like you should have best quality of web camera, good working computer. Because sometimes there are many things that you have to open or you have to you have to operate in your computer. And also, sometimes there are, there are internet problems. And yeah, I think it's very important to be due to be supported and this because I cannot I cannot have a good class, if my equipment is if my equipment is working terribly. And my internet is intermittent. So because your student feels there's like awkwardness when there's like a problem with the equipment. And I don't think that makes me become effective teacher.
Interview:	Okay, I see teacher, I understand that. Another thing is, what is what are your teaching practices that say, teaching practices in your professional development training that help you learn effectively?
Respondent 9:	Oh, um, okay, teacher, let me. Can you say that one more time?
Interview:	Um, what are the teaching practices in your professional development programs or training that help you learn effectively?
Respondent 9:	I think um, the things that helped me learn effectively um, I think the activities in the training like sometimes we have games or how do you say that like a pakulo that trainers have good way of delivering the lesson to us. And I think, especially even we are like, teachers, if we go learning, there are games incorporated in our lessons like I don't know how to explain that. But we have like, game session in our training, which is very interesting. And I learned by that I learned through that.
Interview:	Okay, teacher, so what are you looking forward in your professional development training?
Respondent 9:	Um, I think, I think I'm learning the learning more about the course material, and training contents. Really related to my needs, as online ESL teacher, also, um, you know, teaching online is, it's not really just, it's, it's not totally like, teaching and face to face, you need. I think, if you teach online, you need more emotional support, and mental support, because, um, there are students, because I encountered this in my classes. There are students who are so far off also impatient, and impatient, or rude, and some, it's stressful, it's, it's more stressful than teaching in a normal classroom. So I think we have, if if you want to be an online, ESL teacher, you should be prepared. And I look forward for training that, that help teachers on this area.
Interview:	Okay, so the emotional and mental mental support. Right, teacher?
Respondent 9:	Oh, yes. That's, that's right
Interview:	Okay. So you also mentioned so, you also mentioned teachers that are like this different kinds of students? Is that the reason why you have is that the reason why you need to be patient?
Respondent 9:	Oh, definitely. It's so different when you are teaching online, you know, because you cannot the student is so far and then when you try to call their attention, you cannot just get them. I mean, you cannot just scare them, because if they're too far..
Interview:	Yes, you're right, too. It's a distance learning. Okay. And you also, what about the importance of the content? I mean, you always prepare teach, right? You always prepare before your lesson. How important is that to you?
Respondent 9:	I think as I said already, if you if, if you have trainings on if you have I mean, if you're, if you get ready and prepare for your lessons, like in face to face classes,

	you're more ready to come in your classroom. And sometimes the books in the online class or in the online school, they're so varied and sometimes you encounter new teaching material, and that's the training that we need because sometimes we have not attended the training and then we don't know how to teach yourself sometimes a preparation really works or a prep the preparation really is really helpful.
Interview:	. Okay, teacher how there's another question How should professional development programs or training be given to online English language teachers?
Respondent 9:	Um, I could say um, online teacher I think online online setup is alright, it's okay. Because we don't need to go outside and we we can attend to our classes right away after the training. So use good, though, but I'm as a face to face teacher before. I also like, I have the experience of attending training, you know, in, in, in a real classroom and I mean, like a seminar and I think that that is also effective for learning because you can, you can talk to other teachers and you can you know make plans together like I remember in our in our seminar before as a face to face teacher there is there is there's a seminar and we the teachers make groups and we have activities and we can present it in the in our seminar, so I think that's interesting too.
Interview:	Okay, thank you so much teacher. So is there anything else that you, you'd like to add?
Respondent 9:	Um.no more.
Interview:	I think that would be all teacher thank you so much for participating for the interview. And I wish you have a nice day.
Respondent 9:	Bye bye.
Interview:	Bye.

Interviewer	Hello.
Respondent 11:	Hi. Good morning.
Interviewer	Good morning. Yes, this is this is Emma.
Respondent 11:	Hi.
Interviewer	First of all, I would like to thank you for really participating for this interview. Yeah, it's okay. Before we start, I will just introduce myself.
Respondent 11:	Okay.
Interviewer	All right. I am Emmeline Ballard. I am a student from the University of the Philippines, Open University I am currently writing my thesis and as part of it, I am conducting this interview the title of my thesis is designing a training program for online English language teachers.
Respondent 11:	Okay
Interviewer	so, I will ask your questions related to the training needs and pedagogical preferences are Filipino online teachers and all the information you provide will be strictly kept confidential and information taken for the study will be presented anonymously.
Respondent 11:	Okay
Interviewer	So you can turn on or off your camera anytime. Okay.
Respondent 11:	Okay, no problem.
Interviewer	And also, just to let you know that this will be audio recorded for later analysis. Is that okay?

Respondent 11:	Yeah, no problem.
Interviewer	Alright, so let's begin.
Respondent 11:	Okay.
Interviewer	Alright, so my first question is, can you tell me about which ESL online ESL company you're currently employed or working?
Respondent 11:	I'm currently working for Acadsoc.
Interviewer	Alright, so Acadsoc. So I will be sending you the the job requirements, the job hiring requirements from Akkad. sock. And can you please tell me if they're if this is still the same up until now?
Respondent 11:	I guess everything is is correct. Yeah, I think because I have gotten I have, like, like, when I when I applied for AcadSoc this was already the hiring requirements. And I believe it's still it's still true. Until now.
Interviewer	Okay, thank you for that confirmation. And, okay. Can you also tell me or provide an estimate number of teachers in Acadsoc?
Respondent 11:	I'm not so I'm not so sure about the number. But there are, I guess we are more than more than 2000 teachers in AcadSoc. Maybe that's just that's just a guess. And there are also teachers working home based so I'm not so sure of, how many teachers we have in the country.
Interviewer	Okay, can you tell me if you receive trainings in AcadSoc?
Respondent 11:	Yes, actually, we have training my the first training if I remember correctly, the first training that we that I had was after I pass the interview, so when you pass the interview, there will be a pre pre like read demo teaching demonstrate, there's like after you pass the interview, there will be a training on how you will do your teaching demonstration for them to see if you can get back the class or the the training, the training includes like a brief introduction about the company, the dynamics in the company, and also the teachers the different kinds of platforms or I mean, the different software's that we use for the company. And so, and after that, they also teach us some strategies like TPR. How to you know, how to help students guiding students how to practice their language skills.
Interviewer	Okay, so talking about the language skills, do does AcadSoc offer conversational fluency courses or lessons?
Respondent 11:	We have conversation. In most of our courses, we really have conversation because the our students we owe We help our students to speak in English to, to use complete sentences. When when they, when they interact with us, like for example we have, we teach a vocabulary word. And then we have to, we can guide them how to, to say the complete sentence, even the simple ones, the simple sentence patterns, things like that. So I, I believe we have we help students to be be conversant.
Interviewer	Okay. How about after, after you are hired? Are there still trainings given to teachers?
Respondent 11:	Yeah. AcadSoc offers a free TESOL courses. It's free for all the teachers in AcadSoc and this one will help us to be qualified or regarded as quality teachers in the platform in our school.
Interviewer	Okay, that's good to know. And my next question, how about your, how, can you tell me what skill do you have that set us an advantage in teaching English conversational fluency?
Respondent 11:	Can you say that again? I'm sorry.
Interviewer	Okay, I will just send you the message in the chat box.
Respondent 11:	Okay.
Interviewer	Okay. So can you tell me what skill do you have that set as an advantage in teaching English conversation fluency.

Respondent 11:	Um, I think my skill is I'm sociable. So I have that. I can easily socialize with other people and that skill helped me to easily connect with my students when I teach online, and I can make good connection with them. So I think that that is an advantage for me.
Interviewer	Okay, and how does your personality help you in becoming effective in teaching conversational fluency online setting? Okay, I will just send you the question Okay, you can read it also.
Respondent 11:	Okay, thank you for that. Um, I am I am a fun person and I am also engaging I mean, I, I am, I am funny. Like, I tried to engage my students so that we can really have a good good class and you know, not all online students are interested to learn and not all students are always interested so, as a teacher, I think you have to be I have you have to be funny entertaining to the students. And that's my personality and I am very fun I really, I really keep a good vibes. So, so I can so I can connect with my students. And I think for other teachers, they can also be excuse me sorry. They can also be engaged have fun, you know to be funny. Also, it's I am an honest person I am sincere I mean to say I am sincere so I always I think if you're sincere online the students can also feel that one your sincerity.
Interviewer	Okay, teacher am okay. So, what are the new skills that you have gained in your profession?
Respondent 11:	I think because I, because I let me think about that, I think using different platforms using different software's because before I didn't know how to help, I didn't know if the software like QQ or class in or you know, other other software's that we use in the in the company. But because of that I know already because of this work, I get to learn different kinds of software and I already know how to use them whenever I have class. And that's, I think, a new skill also, when it comes to teaching. Teaching is also another new skill that I learned because in this work you really have to you have to teach You know, even you have to teach learners, Chinese students. And I think I am not. I don't have education. I mean, I am not an education student before. So I had no foundation and teaching. But in here, I learned how to teach how to teach vocabulary, how to guide the students how to use TPR. And yeah, that's it.
Interviewer	So how did you learn these skills? Because you were not in a Yeah. Because you said you were not education graduates. So how did you learn that skill?
Respondent 11:	Well, actually, from the training itself, because as because I have training before, before my final demonstration, and then, so they teach us about the equipment to use. And also, the trainer, give us tips on how to, on how to engage the students and how to use some features in the software. Also, they teach us some teaching strategies, like how to how to make corrections, or how to ask students to do a listen and repeat activity. And I think if you are already a teacher, and then you have always, you know, you have always classes every day, frequent, the frequent use, and the frequent class will help you to know what to do. So that's, I think, how I learned this skill.
Interviewer	So what's the most challenging task in teaching conversational fluency in an online set up?
Respondent 11:	Um, I, I think it's it's more of like, the students are not interacting to you. Because it's, it's, it's challenging, because you have to, you know, the student must say something in this in the in the class, but if you're the one always talking there, it's like boring. And it's also challenging, because you have to do a lot of motivation, you have to do a lot of activity so that the students will respond or say something
Interviewer	Okay, so what do you do for that teacher, if that happens, because it's very challenging.
Respondent 11:	just use a lot, I just use some props. And I tried to call the students attention, like, thing I'm, I wanted to show something to my student, or sometimes I just, sometimes just let it like, if the student don't want to say anything, and then I'll just do it by myself. I will say the, I will say, Oh, do this one, listen, and repeat. And I'll do it by myself until the student follows.
Interviewer	Okay, so, right, teacher I understand now. But anyway, what hampers you to

	become effective in online English as an online English teacher? And how does that stop you from you know, from success?
Respondent 11:	I think it's not enough resources . Not enough resources for like, the equipment. Because I if you're an online teacher, you really need good, good equipment, good computer, or good internet connection. And yeah, so that. Yeah, I think that's it, and also the salary because I mean, not all, not all online teacher receive the same salary. And I mean, not because we have ranking and some new teachers don't receive more salary than those who have seasoned teachers. And of course, if they don't have those who are still new in the company, they still struggle on they still struggle on the resources that they have to use, like they have to. Maybe if they have good computer already, that's good enough. Like, I also mean to say yeah, not enough resources. Like also, props they have to
Interviewer	and Okay, understand What is the most challenging task in online English language teaching?
Respondent 11:	For me, I think it's the technology troubleshooting . Because when you have problem in while you're having a class, that's really stressful. And it's challenging, because you have to get back to your class right? As soon as possible. And, of course, you have to build again, the connection that you have in the class. I mean, to say, if, for example, you're having a class, and suddenly there's a, you lose the internet connection, you have to find ways how to get back to your student quickly. And then you have to, you know, you have to continue the lesson. And then you have, and, of course, it's I think it's embarrassing that, oh, you had a mistake. I mean, it's not a mistake, you had a problem during the lesson time. So I think that's challenging. Because you have to, you have to, you know, you have to restart, you have to restart your, your internet, your router, then you also have to think of how to connect again, with the student how to, how to, how to tell to your student that if there's like, this problem is not so big, you know, so that they won't be they won't give you a complain.
Interviewer	Okay, understand? What are the teaching practices in your professional development programs or training that help you learn effectively?
Respondent 11:	Um, teaching practices, I think it's, it's the it's the concrete examples that they give us, but not so. Like, they give us picture. They give, they lead us to, like, I think the teaching practices, they show us how to use the, there's like a demonstration on how to use certain software, for example, they will tell us like, if you do this, they give us the pros and cons, if we, if we do this kind of thing in the software, this will happen. Or if we don't check this one, this thing will happen. So it's more of the demonstration. If you if you can see it, then you can easily understand I think that's the teaching practice that I learn effective, because I can remember it now.
Interviewer	what about the teaching courses that you look forward? In? In your professional development programs,
Respondent 11:	I think it's more of technology back up, because they teach us about how to use the software, how to use how to use the software, how to teach how to use TPR, and how to encourage students, but there's, I think, lack of content on how we can on on, what are the other things that we can do when when they're like, problems that we cannot control that's out of our control? So, for example, how the ups and then like, there's a problem with the Internet, what should be our, our first aid, or first aid? Or if you get what I mean? Like, what should be our what should be the first thing to do if aside from restarting our router on and off, like, I hope there could be like a little of input from the IT IT staff guys that how, like, what if, for example, there's a bug, what's the possible solution for us to do?
Interviewer	Okay,
Respondent 11:	and, and also, I think, another is the activities that you know, this is in for the for the lesson, I hope they can also give us some activities related to games that will help the student to remember the lesson . Because of course, we want the we want students to learn and what are the other effective ways for the students to to get good vocabulary, even if they are learning online?

Interviewer	Okay, thank you for that. And how should be professional development programs or training be given to online English teachers.
Respondent 11:	Um, as for me, I think there should I think it's the trainers should be experienced or or the trainers should have experienced teaching online because how can they understand our situation or how can they fully understand the vet classroom if they have not experienced it by themselves , so, I hope the trainer also like when we have our training they understand already what do we mean to say off one situation? Because sometimes when like, the the QA team will just ask us I hope they you know, I hope they can listen or they have experienced already on experience already on teaching online.
Interviewer	Okay, alright. So, another question is how do you consider yourself when it comes to technology use comfort comfortable user or confident Explorer?
Respondent 11:	So, can you say that again,
Interviewer	I was asking if How do you consider yourself Are you a confident explorer, when it comes to technology or comfortable user when it comes to using technology?
Respondent 11:	I can say I am a confident explorer
Interviewer	What do you mean have What do you mean have confident explorer? How do you understand be confident explorer?
Respondent 11:	For me, I am more confident explorer, because I can I can confidently use different kinds of software. And I am I am able to, to understand different functions of the software. Software buttons or software features. So I think I'm confident Explorer, and yeah, that's it
Interviewer	Okay, so, is there anything else that you'd like to share with each other about about online online English language teaching?
Respondent 11:	Yeah, um, I think I also want to, to know the the stand of of our government towards online ESL teacher because not everyone is given good compensation. Like we are freelancers and it is difficult to go where to vent out our complains.
Interviewer	Oh I see. I see your point.
Respondent 11:	Yeah.
Interviewer	Ok. I think I do not have any others questions now. thank you once again for giving this time for the interview.
Respondent 11:	It's okay.
Interviewer	Ok. So thank you and bye bye
Respondent 11:	Bye bye.

Interviewer:	Hello, good afternoon.
Respondent 14:	Hi, good afternoon.
Interviewer:	Hi, this is Emma. And yes, thank you so much for, for having this interview today.
Respondent 14:	It's okay with me. But is it okay if I will close my camera? So with that because I, I noticed that my connection today is not so good. All right, sure, no problem.
Interviewer:	Okay. All right. Before we start, let me just introduce myself. Okay. So I am Emmalyn Balon and I am a student from UPOU. And I'm conducting this interview for my thesis, which is entitled, designing a training framework for online English language teachers. And there are questions that I'm going to ask you relating to the training needs and pedagogical preferences of online English language teachers. Okay, so all the information that you will provide will be strictly kept confidential. And information taken for the study will be presented anonymously. Okay. Okay. All right. And this will be audio recorded. Is that okay? For you?
Respondent 14:	Sure. No problem.
Interviewer:	All right. So and also you can switch on or off your camera anytime. Okay.
Respondent 14:	Okay. But I prefer to turn it off, because my connection is not so good today.
Interviewer:	Alright. Sure. No worries. So is there anything else you'd like to ask before we start?
Respondent 14:	It's okay with me.
Interviewer:	We can start now. All right. So first is what ESL company are you currently employed?
Respondent 14:	I work in five, one talk now.
Interviewer:	All right, 51Talk. Okay. So I, how about this, I will send you a message in the chat box. Okay. Hi, Ray. Okay, the hiring requirements is can you confirm to me if these are still the hiring requirements of five one talk? Can you just please check?
Respondent 14:	Okay, let me see. For this one. Yeah, that is correct.
Interviewer:	Okay. Sure. Thank you. And can you tell me or can? Can you provide an estimate of how many teachers are you are there in 51?
Respondent 14:	Um, maybe around 3000 or 5000? Teachers, because our company is really growing.
Interviewer:	Okay, well, that's a lot. Yeah. Okay. Do you receive trainings in 51 talk?
Respondent 14:	Um, yes. For example, like, if you are, I mean, if you pass the hiring process, before they will, you know, deploy you or before they will give you some classes or before they will allow you to open slots, because it's a booking system, they will conduct a training first, you know, to, to really check. If you really suits for kids, if really suited for kids or for adult learners.
Interviewer:	I see. Okay. So that there's a so before you go on, really a live teaching, like the real one. Yeah, you have to undergo a training, how many days would that last? Is that like a whole day?
Respondent 14:	Not really whole day. It's just like for let's say, for kids training, it's like, maybe two to three hours. And for adults, maybe only one hour two.
Interviewer:	Okay, so that happens in one day. Exactly. Alright. Okay. Sure. And do you have other trainings, so after you are employed?
Respondent 14:	And once you get I mean, once you get started working in in five, one talk, they would ask you to have a TESOL training. This is your ticket to to, to level up your your ranking because teachers have this ranking system, like, at the same time, your rate will increase if you undergo some trainings, for example, is TESOL training.
Interviewer:	Oh Okay, how's that be? So given is that like, face to face, or you have to go to the site? Or?

Respondent 14:	Oh, it's only the it can only be done online,
Interviewer:	online. Okay, so you can do it by group or individually.
Respondent 14:	It's individual training. I mean, we will sign up something in like, I forget this TESOL website. We will sign up our information there. And then of course, we will have logins and then we will do the tasks there and then if we finish we can send a report or email to our administrator Train, and then we then we will just wait for the result. And if we pass, then we will wait for the certificate to be given to us
Interviewer:	Okay, so you have, so I'll just make it clear, you have to sign up. And then after you sign up, you do the training all by yourself like it's, there's just a manual to read in the site. Is that right?
Respondent 14:	Exactly, exactly.
Interviewer:	Okay. Okay. I see. All right. So I think can you tell me do you.. does five one talk teach conversational fluency to adult Chinese EFL learners?
Respondent 14:	Yes, definitely. Like me. Most of my students are adults. So basically, we have this role playing lesson or dialogue, dialogue as well and even question and answer. Yeah, something like that. All right.
Interviewer:	So there's really conversation.
Respondent 14:	Yeah, five, one talk. Conversation lesson.
Interviewer:	Okay, I see. And how many minutes? Do you teach online?
Respondent 14:	25 minutes.
Interviewer:	Okay. Do you have? Can you tell me where do you conduct that lesson? When, where which platform or software do you use?
Respondent 14:	Oh we have AC software
Interviewer:	Okay. Is that easy to use? Are you.. have you need some training?
Respondent 14:	If you are, like me, in my first month, I, we need training, okay, are this you know, like, more on troubleshooting like that, like how to use the tools in that software? You know, to achieve a, a smooth lesson and also to have an engaging lesson at the same time.
Interviewer:	Okay I understand. And what skill Do you have that set as an advantage in teaching English conversational fluency?
Respondent 14:	I, I guess my teaching experience , I can say that discovery learning and learning by doing
Interviewer:	What do you mean by that?
Respondent 14:	Its like when I discovered if when I discover something that I have some certain skills for example, before I am not so good with conversation, I mean, like, like, like certain, like, what topic I should discuss to the student. By, by because we have in our in teaching adult, we have this free talk lesson. So some, some adults would ask me, like, what, what could be our topic for today? So as a teacher, you should be prepared. Or if ever, you're not really prepared, you can just ask questions to the student and then, and for me, that's learning by doing
Interviewer:	Oh I see, so you just learn by Yeah, learning by doing. Okay. And what about your personality? How does your personality help you become effective in teaching conversational fluency?
Respondent 14:	I guess, creativity in presenting the topic , there should be like, props, props, in a sense that, for example, let's say toys, okay? To help the students engage and be interested in talking at the same time. And also, if you are teaching adult, you have to be creative in asking question. Because to avoid, you know, being a boring teacher in the class, you have to be creative in presenting the topic or question to the learners.

Interviewer:	Okay, I see. So, did you. Did you learn that skill? Did you learn that creativity in asking question, in your experience, or from your TESOL training?
Respondent 14:	Um, yes, I because of the TESOL training, I it was a very, very helpful course. For online teachers like me. It's like, with this training, it gives additional knowledge to us, like me, because I'm not a teacher when I graduated, but with this TESOL training it gives additional ideas and knowledge for me to improve my teaching skills and to be more engaging in my lesson.
Interviewer:	Oh, okay. So what are the new skills you have? So, so you're so you learn skills from TESOL training from Attending it right?
Respondent 14:	Yes.
Interviewer:	Okay, so what is the most challenging anyway? In teaching conversational fluency in online set up?
Respondent 14:	Um, we know that Chinese students, they are not really need to when it comes to English, I mean, it's not their first language. So, most of them are they have lack of vocabulary. And they are not so confident in, in, in expressing themselves, maybe because they are afraid to express themselves because they have maybe they have bad pronunciation, or they are not sure that if they are using the right vocabulary when it comes to conversational English All right,
Interviewer:	I see. So, that's, that's difficult because it's like, they cannot there's, they cannot talk to you fluently.
Respondent 14:	Yeah. So, as a teacher, you have to use simple words so that they can understand what you're saying or asking to them.
Interviewer:	Okay, understand anything else you'd like to add? Or is that all?
Respondent 14:	I guess that's all.
Interviewer:	Okay. What hampers you to become successful as an online ESL teacher?
Respondent 14:	Um.. to become an online English teacher, and if you really want is not easy, but if you want to be successful, technology equipment is really important for you to
Interviewer:	Can you explain more about the technology equipment.
Respondent 14:	Um, let's see, our company requires a specific computer specifications. So you need to meet those requirements. Because our software like the ACS, I was saying it, it requires a lot of space on your computer. So, so that for you to have a smooth class, so you should meet, or you should have a good computer specification. And also there should be a financial assistance for teacher, right? I mean, we know that all teachers are not, you know, fortunate, I mean, not doesn't have a good financial or don't have financials or not financial stable. So, I hope that I hope our company would provide us equipment, for example, let's say, if there is a power outage, in our big, it's very common in the Philippines, I hope the company would provide us a backup equipment. If but if a teacher you know, can have that on their own, if the but like, you know, they have to save money, they have to do they have to save money from their salary to buy a backup equipment, let's say UPS, or even generator, or for internet, like you should have, like a portable modem. Like that. And also I feel that it's unfair, you know, to to receive a negative feedback. I mean, for example, if we receive negative feedback, sometimes our company did not less does not listen to teacher side, they would go directly to what the students saying, okay, although they check the recording, but we don't have any rights anymore to express our side. And what really, what's the bad thing for that is that we go to the SA deliberation
Interviewer:	what is SA?
Respondent 14:	like your agreement, your agreements like a contract, okay?
Interviewer:	If I'm correct service agreement,
Respondent 14:	yes service agreement, something like that, okay. So, as much as possible, you

	should avoid that having negative feedback because it will really lead you to as a deliberation. And if you have this like, many times in a month, you will be terminated or be disturbed with that.
Interviewer:	Okay. That's so sad to hear teacher. Yeah. So, that means to say you need technology equipment, if I if I just correct me if I'm wrong to my understanding. You need technology equipment to support you for your classes. Yeah, so have a smooth class. Yeah. Because if you don't have a smooth class, there will be like, feedback about your performance. Is that right?
Respondent 14:	Correct. And also, the students will complain or give you a negative feedback.
Interviewer:	Okay, I see I see. All right, and will lead to termination if you have a lot of this?
Respondent 14:	Exactly, because it's this lesson is all about online. So you have to prepare, you have to be fully prepared online.
Interviewer:	Okay, I see. All right, I get that now. And well, so what's the most challenging task for you in you know, in online English language teaching,
Respondent 14:	um, technology, troubleshooting, like, sudden error on our, on our software, and at the same time, if you don't have a good computer specs, it could be really big trouble. You know, that would be very challenging. If you are working online, in an English language teaching platform like five, one talk.
Interviewer:	Okay. So why it's challenging for you.
Respondent 14:	It's challenging, because you, as I was saying a while ago, if you if you experience this most of the time, then you cannot have a good or smooth class. You cannot earn because it's like, no, no work, no pay here. I mean, if you don't have students, then definitely you don't have salary. And if you have students, if you've got, for example, if you're fully book today, and then you don't have a good computer specs, you always experienced, you know, problems with your PC or with your laptop and your internet at the same time. So it would give a bad impression to the student and they will not book you anymore.
Interviewer:	In connection to computer problem, do you say or are you a comfortable user of technology or confident explorer?
Respondent 14:	Um Yeah I'm a comfortable user.
Interviewer:	Okay. What do you mean by comfortable user to yourself?
Respondent 14:	It's um. I know how to use a computer and um laptop or smart phone with ease, but you know when there is I ah error on my PC sometimes I panic like a little bit. Then, I ask or send a PM to my friends or our neighbor because he is IT.
Interviewer:	I see. Don't you? Doesn't the company has professional IT?
Respondent 14:	Yeah we have but it is also online and it took takes long time to respond for a concern ticket.
Interviewer:	Okay. I see your point, teacher. And okay. And well, anyway, what are the teaching practices in your professional development programs? Or we say in other words, training, okay, that make you learn effectively,
Respondent 14:	I can say that the TESOL training certification is really really a good help for us teacher online teachers. Why? Because it can as I it, of course, it's it conducted online. And in that blog, black are not really planning that site, the TESOL certification or I mean that TESOL site, there is a test after each topic or unit. So before you can get to the question and answer portion of that, of that, of the test of the topic, you need to learn you need to read carefully so that you could have the ideas on how to answer the questions after
Interviewer:	all right. So there's like, yeah, like an exam?
Respondent 14:	Exactly.
Interviewer:	Okay. So you really have when you do that is all you you need to be focused on it.

Respondent 14:	Yeah. So you have to spend more time for that. Like me, I finish I mean, for example, if I spend time for this when I spend time for this are you finished? One topic? Like 1am already? Oh, yeah. Because we I have to make sure that I you should pass.
Interviewer:	Oh, I see. Yeah. Okay. So but but do you like do you like your training program like TESOL certification to be given online?
Respondent 14:	Um, I guess 5050
Interviewer:	Why, was that 5050?
Respondent 14:	Because um, our TESOL online learning is not suitable for actual teaching. Okay. As far as I know, because I I mean, I I joined by participated in online TESOL training and actual TESOL training. They're in online this whole training some of them some of the readings that I have there where the topic there are not really suitable for online it's for actual,
Interviewer:	okay. Actual. You mean of actual like?
Respondent 14:	like face to face classes, like classroom teachers like that.
Interviewer:	I see. But another What I mean to say like for example, if I want to or an ESL company will give you training? Do you want to do it online? Or how should professional development programs or training given to online teachers?
Respondent 14:	I guess, online online because it's more convenient. By but I have to be honest, it's boring, okay. Because I have to do it by myself alone. It's like self pace.
Interviewer:	Okay. So do you prefer having it in a group? Or
Respondent 14:	if it's a group, that would be better. Because we can share ideas? And at the same time, we don't. It's not boring. And will not, you won't get sleepy.
Interviewer:	I see, teacher, and what are the teaching courses? Or, you know, training programs or training courses that you look forward for your training?
Respondent 14:	Oh, that is a good question. Well, trainings with vocabulary drills or exercise related to content materials, which are fun materials are what I find interesting. Why? Because it makes me teach effectively.
Interviewer:	Okay, so you want this content? It's about the content, right?
Respondent 14:	Yeah. Sorry. Yes. Because I believe there is, you know, some, you know, activities or games for that, you know, which is very helpful for, for for, for the teachers and for the students as well.
Interviewer:	Okay. Right. And there's also from this just additional question, in online English language teaching why it's so important to be patient.
Respondent 14:	As an online English language teacher, you have to be patient, because let's be honest, some, some students are. I mean, they have their very level level zero learners. I mean, they don't have any basic English at all. So you have to be patient and teaching them. And I, on the other hand, you have to be patient as well. Because here in in five, one talk, definitely irises are more Chinese. There are really naughty students. Okay. It's, and also they're also rude students. Like they keep shouting in the class. And also, there are also as they don't like to be corrected, all right, with your grammar, so you have to be patient. And you also have to be creative the same time and how to deal with that.
Interviewer:	Wow, that's really a very good answer. Thank you, teacher. Yeah. Okay. Is there anything else that you'd like to add?
Respondent 14:	Um, none so far.
Interviewer:	Okay. So I think that would be all for today. I don't have any other questions. And yeah, thank you so much, and I wish you have a nice day.
Respondent 14:	Thank you.
Interviewer:	Bye bye.

Answer Summary Per Question

Respondent Number	What skill do you have, that set as an advantage in teaching English conversational fluency online?
1	education degree ko. I find my college education and teaching experiences helpful as an online ESL teacher.
2	time management; communication skills
4	technology skills;a face to face teaching experience; tourism degree
5	teaching experience is really an advantage, you know, teaching Chinese students when it comes to teaching English conversation.
9	teaching experience
11	sociable. So I have that. I can easily socialize with other people and that skill helped me to easily connect with my students when I teach online, and I can make good connection with them. So I think that that is an advantage for me.
14	my teaching experience; that discovery learning and learning by doing - when I discover something that I have some certain skills for example, before I am not so good with conversation, I mean, like, like, like certain, like, what topic I should discuss to the student. By, by because we have in our in teaching adult, we have this free talk lesson. So some, some adults would ask me, like, what, what could be our topic for today? So as a teacher, you should be prepared. Or if ever, you're not really prepared, you can just ask questions to the student and then, and for me, that's learning by doing

Respondent Number	. What is your personality teach, that help you become effective in teaching conversational fluency in online setting?
1	friendly person.
2	-
4	talkative; patient
5	computer management; open minded person, you know, I feel students working, you know, I feel adults, students, working professionals, you know, appreciate if teacher if teachers listen, and sometimes, you know, conversation can lead to out of the blue revelation.
9	prepared and organized
11	I tried to engage my students so that we can really have a good good class and you know, not all online students are interested to learn and not all students are always interested so, as a teacher, I think you have to be I have you have to be funny entertaining to the students; I am sincere so I always I think if you're sincere online the students can also feel that one your sincerity.
14	To help the students engage and be interested in talking at the same time. And also, if you are teaching adult, you have to be creative in asking question. Because to avoid, you know, being a boring teacher in the class, you have to be creative in presenting the topic or question to the learners.

Respondent Number	Are there any new skills you have gained as online teacher teaching conversation?
1	listening. I'm more of listener now. I give the student more chance to talk kesa sa kin.
2	familiar with different levels.
4	understand better how others are speaking
5	computer management.
9	it's more of a using of technology , and I mean, adapting, adapting to technology,
11	using different platforms using different software's because before I didn't know how to help, I didn't know if the software like QQ or class in; teaching skill - I am not an education student before. So I had no foundation and teaching. But in here, I learned how to teach how to teach vocabulary, how to guide the students how to use TPR
14	because of the TESOL training , I it was a very, very helpful course. For online teachers like me. It's like, with this training, it gives additional knowledge to us,

Respondent Number	How you learn it?
1	We were told teach to give the student more chance to speak . Kaya conscious din ako to limit my words. Like nasa teaching material ilang, mga percentage ako magsalita or si student.
2	But for teachers who have been teaching for quite long , I'm sure they were able, like me, like you, you, you know how you know what to do.
4	the frequent classes
5	But working here , you know, it helps me to improve my typing skill, my computer management skill, you know, like, well, let's say for example, before, like, only 10% With knights, like 80 to 90% improvement. All
9	I can switch because I have an experience in face to face
11	, from the training itself; the frequent use, and the frequent class will help you to know what to do
14	because of the TESOL training , I it was a very, very helpful course. For online teachers like me. It's like, with this training, it gives additional knowledge to us,

Respondent Number	What hampers or stops you from becoming an effective online teacher?
1	teaching material.
2	different types of learners and the online setup now ; new setting , it's a, it's, you have to be very mindful of the surroundings, especially the sound noise.
4	it's the environment
5	lack of support . ; the management would not listen to me. If I give suggestion they do, they do not recognize it
9	no topic
11	not interacting ; challenging, because you have to do a lot of motivation, you have to do a lot of activity so that the students will respond or say something
14	they have lack of vocabulary .; to use simple words so that they can understand what you're saying or asking to them.; technology, troubleshooting, like, sudden error on our, on our software, and at the same time, if you don't have a good computer specs, it could be really big trouble. You know, that would be very challenging. If you are working online, in an English language teaching platform like five, one talk.

Respondent Number	What is the most challenging task in online English language teaching?
-------------------	--

1	Rude students.
2	think so I think it's more of your strategy as a teacher, your teaching style, your patients, your personality as a teacher,
4	if if you have a quiet environment, the student will not complain about it, you know, you will not get that negative feedback; the contents are easy that you can just add, besides your teacher, teacher's guide, you can read it before the class if you want ; internet connection
5	no topic to discuss
9	a problem with a time management
11	not enough resources
14	, technology, troubleshooting, like, sudden error on our, on our software, and at the same time, if you don't have a good computer specs, it could be really big trouble. You know, that would be very challenging. If you are working online, in an English language teaching platform

Respondent Number	what are the teaching practices in your professional development programs or training that help you learn effectively?
1	If the facilitator is professional, I can say I learn effectively.
2	Teachers are encouraged to volunteer, they can volunteer if they want and, and we do have this ratings; whether they're introvert extrovert, or ambivert, they really the company will let them Oh, since you are the top two, you have to let this you have to take this workshop. Right? You sit here the top three, so you have to really help the author; every trainings is different different teachers every month different speakers. And it's very interesting to hear your colleagues speak for the first time, especially new teachers.
4	practices that we did in our training, like you know, we have workshop and we have also demonstration,
5	chance to share our insight
9	are games incorporated
11	concrete examples demonstration
14	, there is a test after each topic or unit. So before you can get to the question and answer portion of that, of that, of the test of the topic, you need to learn you need to read carefully so that you could have the ideas on how to answer the questions after

Respondent Number	. How do you want to receive your trainings?
1	online; conferences kami or gathering. May mga learning din ako natutunan doon.
2	monthly workshop; online platform
4	online learning is also good on as a student, but like there, but you will never know what is just boring, you know, to read a lot to read a lot on your own. you don't know if you have the same if it's the same understanding that others that how others get it, and it's self paced. And it's also too long, I feel it's too long. If it's online courses, that's too long. I don't like it.
5	very friendly. You're friendly at the same time. Not authoritative
9	online setup; is there's a seminar and we the teachers make groups and we have activities and we can present it in the in our seminar, so I think that's interesting too.
11	concrete examples; demonstration; trainers should be experienced or or the trainers should have experienced teaching online because how can they understand our situation or how can they fully understand the vet classroom if they have not experienced it by themselves,
14	online because it's more convenient. By but I have to be honest, it's boring, okay. Because I have to do it by myself alone. It's like self pace.

Respondent Number	What teaching courses are you looking forward to in your professional development programs?
1	art of questioning at technology.
2	-
4	well designed topics. Topics that can help me in my can help me in my, my skills and passion as a teacher, like, you know, like understanding by my students, yeah, this kind of courses
5	teaching level zero students, okay
9	the course material, and training contents. Really related to my needs, as online ESL teacher emotional support, and mental support,
11	technology back up, because they teach us about how to use the software, how to use how to use the software, how to teach how to use TPR, and how to encourage students, but there's, I think, lack of content on how we can on on, what are the other things that we can do when when they're like, problems that we cannot control that's out of our control?; some activities related to games that will help the student to remember the lesson
14	, trainings with vocabulary drills or exercise related to content materials, which are fun materials are what I find interesting

Respondent Number	technology skill
1	not afraid to search and try other internet application
2	I'm always interested to learning new things like that if it's necessary. But as much as possible, I don't want to have like changes, keep on learning, you know, every time every month
4	confident explorer because I, I like to search, I look for, I like to search for reviews about certain gadgets. And also, I looked for activities online that I can use to break the ice during the session. I also research about different gadgets like webcam headset, computer specs, which can best help me to deliver the lesson smoothly, especially when glitches happen.
5	To me, it is using a laptop. PC. phone or any gadget, you know. I look for ways or means to solve my present problem like example I have computer problem, I you know, where which button to check or end. I understand, um, you know ping, technology terms I mean. Like ping, bot, other details just basic idea
9	; learn independently
11	For me, I am more confident explorer, because I can I can confidently use different kinds of software. And I am I am able to, to understand different functions of the software. Software buttons or software features. So I think I'm confident Explorer, and yeah, that's it
14	know how to use a computer and um laptop or smart phone with ease, but you know when there is I ah error on my PC sometimes I panic like a little bit

Respondent Number	Other concerns
1	familiar with different levels; the challenge would be for new teachers; So I guess that is the challenge for some teachers, they have to be, they have to do multitask. They do multitasking, since they only have five minutes. Break right after the class, there will be another student 25 minutes. All right.; Both? Because if you are if you have, if you're ineligible, if you have content knowledge, but you are not confident in teaching, that student will not believe you. ;it really boils down to like your passion and your personality and teaching students that like the teaching style, it's how you assess the student.
2	the most important thing they have to master that(company software)

4	
5	
9	
11	the stand of of our government towards online ESL teacher because not everyone is given good compensation. Like we are freelancers and it is difficult to go where to vent out our complains.
14	our TESOL online learning is not suitable for actual teaching. Okay. As far as I know, because I I mean, I I joined by participated in online TESOL training and actual TESOL training. They're in online this whole training some of them some of the readings that I have there where the topic there are not really suitable for online it's for actual,

Appendix 13 Iterative Design

Quality Matters Rubric Checklist*

adapted for Training Program for Online English Language Teachers

	YES	NO	COMMENT
Course Overview and Introduction			
1. Instructions make clear how to get started and where to find various course components.	x x	x x	Include brief introduction about the program, table of contents
2. Learners are introduced to the purpose and structure of the course.	x	x x x	This looks like a trainer's handbook.
3. Communication expectations for online discussions, email, and other forms of interaction are clearly stated.		x x x x	
4. Course and institutional policies with which the learner is expected to comply are clearly stated within the course, or a link to current policies is provided.		x x x x	
5. Minimum technology requirements for the course are clearly stated, and information on how to obtain the technologies is provided.	x	x x x	
6. Computer skills and digital information literacy skills expected of the learner are clearly stated.	x x	x x	Online ESL teachers have a working knowledge of computers. So there's no need to elaborate.
7. Expectations for prerequisite knowledge in the discipline and/or any required competencies are clearly stated.	x x x x		
8. The self-introduction by the instructor is professional and is available online.	x	x x x	The instructor's qualifications should be made very evident. And, no self-introduction.
9. Learners are asked to introduce themselves to the class.	x x x x		
Learning Objectives (Competencies)			
			You can be more specific on what computer problem (example: software or hardware) for Technology User – Expert course Add: At the end of the program, the participants will be able to: Lack ff aspects: measurable time (at the end of the --- -) Not measurable
1. The course learning objectives, or course/program competencies, describe outcomes that are measurable.	x	x x x	
2. The module/unit-level learning objectives or competencies describe outcomes that are measurable and consistent with the course-level objectives or competencies.	x x x	x	consistent with course-level but not measurable consistent but not measurable

4. The relationship between learning objectives or competencies and learning activities is clearly stated.	x x x	x	
5. The learning objectives or competencies are suited to the level of the course.	x x x x		
Assessment and Measurement			
1. The assessments measure the achievement of the stated learning objectives or competencies.	x x	x x	
2. The course grading policy is stated clearly at the beginning of the course.		x x x x	not necessary
3. Specific and descriptive criteria are provided for the evaluation of learners' work, and their connection to the course grading policy is clearly explained.		x x x x	no course grading policy No grading policy
4. The assessments used are sequenced, varied, and suited to the level of the course.	x x x x		It's varied per course.
5. The course provides learners with multiple opportunities to track their learning progress with timely feedback.	x x	x x	no emphasis on timely feedback
Learning Activities and Learner Interaction			
1. The learning activities promote the achievement of the stated learning objectives or competencies.	x x x x		
2. Learning activities provide opportunities for interaction that support active learning.	x x x x		
3. The instructor's plan for interacting with learners during the course is clearly stated.	x	x x x	
4. The requirements for learner interaction are clearly stated.	x x x x		
Learner Support			
1. The course instructions articulate or link to a clear description of the technical support offered and how to obtain it.		x x x x	
2. Course instructions articulate or link to the institution's accessibility policies and services.	x	x x x	
3. Course instructions articulate or link to the institution's academic support services and resources that can help learners succeed in the course.	x	x x x	
4. Course instructions articulate or link to the institution's student services and resources that can help learners succeed.		x x x x	
Others:			
			Mentoring program duties and responsibilities Course titles could be clearer.

* Modified Quality Matters Rubric. For original QM Rubric for Higher Education click here:
<https://www.qualitymatters.org/sites/default/files/PDFs/StandardsfortheQMHighEducationRubric.pdf>

Evaluator 1

Evaluator 2

Evaluator 3

Evaluator 4

Appendix 14 Iterative Development

Quality Matters Rubric Checklist*

adapted for Training Program for Online English Language Teachers

	YES	NO	COMMENT
Course Overview and Introduction			
1. Instructions make clear how to get started and where to find various course components.	X X X X		
2. Learners are introduced to the purpose and structure of the course.	X X	X X	
3. Communication expectations for online discussions, email, and other forms of interaction are clearly stated.	X X X X		
4. Course and institutional policies with which the learner is expected to comply are clearly stated within the course, or a link to current policies is provided.	X X X X		
5. Minimum technology requirements for the course are clearly stated, and information on how to obtain the technologies is provided.	X X X X		
6. Computer skills and digital information literacy skills expected of the learner are clearly stated.	X X X X		
7. Expectations for prerequisite knowledge in the discipline and/or any required competencies are clearly stated.	X X X X		
8. The self-introduction by the instructor is professional and is available online.	X X X X		Be more specific "brief introduction" on what
9. Learners are asked to introduce themselves to the class.	X X X X		
Learning Objectives (Competencies)			
1. The course learning objectives, or course/program competencies, describe outcomes that are measurable.	X X X X		
2. The module/unit-level learning objectives or competencies describe outcomes that are measurable and consistent with the course-level objectives or competencies.	X X X X		
3. Learning objectives or competencies are stated clearly, are written from the learner's perspective, and are prominently located in the course.	X X X X		
4. The relationship between learning objectives or competencies and learning activities is clearly stated.	X X X X		
5. The learning objectives or competencies are suited to the level of the course.	X X X X		
Assessment and Measurement			
1. The assessments measure the achievement of the stated learning objectives or competencies.	X X X X		
2. The course grading policy is stated clearly at the beginning of the course.	X X X X		

3. Specific and descriptive criteria are provided for the evaluation of learners' work, and their connection to the course grading policy is clearly explained.	X X X X		
4. The assessments used are sequenced, varied, and suited to the level of the course.	X X X X		
5. The course provides learners with multiple opportunities to track their learning progress with timely feedback.	X X X X		
Learning Activities and Learner Interaction			
1. The learning activities promote the achievement of the stated learning objectives or competencies.	X X X X		
2. Learning activities provide opportunities for interaction that support active learning.	X X X X		
3. The instructor's plan for interacting with learners during the course is clearly stated.	X X X	X	
4. The requirements for learner interaction are clearly stated.	X X X X		
Learner Support			
1. The course instructions articulate or link to a clear description of the technical support offered and how to obtain it.	X X X X		
2. Course instructions articulate or link to the institution's accessibility policies and services.	X X X X		
3. Course instructions articulate or link to the institution's academic support services and resources that can help learners succeed in the course.	X X X X		
4. Course instructions articulate or link to the institution's student services and resources that can help learners succeed.	X X X X		
Others:			
No assessment indicated for Mentoring program Assessment and course grading policy look better if incorporated under specific course. Reformat for better presentation			

* Modified Quality Matters Rubric. For original QM Rubric for Higher Education click here:
<https://www.qualitymatters.org/sites/default/files/PDFs/StandardsfromtheQMHigherEducationRubric.pdf>

Evaluator 1

Evaluator 2

Evaluator 3

Evaluator 4

Appendix 15
Training Program Blueprint (Beta Version)
Training Needs and Pedagogical Practices
of Online English Language Teachers

This manual is the by-product of the analysis of the training needs and preferred pedagogical practices of online English language teachers in the Philippines. Gathered data were derived from TPACK and Community of Inquiry surveys along with the set of interview questions.

This manual aims to guide trainers and course developers in designing a training program for online English language teachers. It is hoped that with these pointers, course developers will also consider teacher's needs and preferences in relation to their demographic background.

The second section of this manual contains five training courses for Online English Language Teachers. Participants, learning objectives, guidelines, and potential topics are all reflected in the course description. Each course must also follow the general training program guidelines.

This manual is divided into 2 parts.

Part 1. TPACK Needs and Objectives

- TPACK Needs
- Learning Objectives for each TPACK Domain

Part 2. Courses

- General Characteristics of the Course Facilitator
- General Pedagogical Guidelines
- General Learner Support Guideline
- Tailored Courses/Training Program for Online Teachers
 - Course Description
 - Additional Facilitator's Qualification:
 - Course Participants
 - Learning Objectives
 - Possible Topics
 - Course Pointers

Part 1. Summary of the Gathered Data

I. Training Needs

The table below shows the training needs of online English language teachers based on their TPACK rating on each category. The categories are ordered based on their given score.

Priority Number	Overall	Course		Years of Teaching Experience				Age		Technological Skills			
		Education Graduates	Non-Education Graduates	<1 year	1-3 years	4-6 years	>6 years	21-30 y.o.	31-40 y.o.	Confident Explorer	Comfortable User		
1	TK	TK	TCK	CK	TCK	TK	TK	TK	CK	TPACK	TK		
2	TCK	CK	TK	TK	TPACK	TPACK	TCK	TCK	TK	CK	TCK		
3	CK	TCK	TPK	TPK	TK	PK	TPK	TPACK	PK TCK TPACK	PCK TCK TK	CK		
4	TPACK	TPACK	TPACK	TPACK	CK	CK	CK	TPK			TPK	TPACK	TPK
5	TPK	PCK	CK	TCK PK	TPK	TPK	PK	CK			TPACK	TPACK	TPACK
6	PK	TPK	PCK	PK	PK	TCK PK	PK	PK	TPK	TPK	PCK		
7	PK	PK	PK		PK	PK	TPACK	TPACK	PK	PK	PK	PK	

II. Learning Objectives

The table below shows the course objectives and suggested topics for each TPACK category.

TPACK Category	Course Objectives	Probable Topics
Technological Knowledge (TK)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrate knowledge, skills, and concepts related to software and hardware technical problems • Name possible technical difficulties and demands in online language teaching • Select appropriate and prompt techniques in handling basic and elaborate software operation • Appraise available technologies in maximizing its use for language learning • Produce relevant and meaningful reflection to resolve technical difficulties and impact of new technologies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic Hardware Troubleshooting • Software Troubleshooting Techniques • Understanding software functions and tools • Keyboard Shortcuts • Understanding Digital Tools: teaching platforms, content creation apps, webcam software, translator device, virtual whiteboards, etc.
Content Knowledge (CK)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrate good English language grammar • Utilize techniques to build the various language skills of students • Share opinion with facts related to historical and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic and Advanced English Grammar • Language Teaching Techniques and Pedagogy • Varieties and Implications of World Englishes

	<p>current events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster awareness and appreciation for World Englishes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current Events Webpages related to Learner's Context
Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a good command on different teaching methods in handling online class • Demonstrate sensitivity towards student's culture and learning style 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language Teaching Strategies and Techniques • Introduction to Online Language Teaching Environment • Multiple Intelligence • Facilitation Techniques • Understanding Student's Culture, Language and Identity • Understanding English Levels and Student's Proficiency • Lesson Enrichment/Extension Ideas
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate digital resources to increase student's motivation • Examine the benefits and drawbacks of application/software for better classroom management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gamified Interactive Software • Webcam Interactive Tricks • Attendance and Virtual Rewards Management Software • Music and Video Resources in Increasing Motivation and Activating Schema

<p>Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify digital tools beneficial for language learning and teaching • Examine the benefits and drawbacks of application/software for online language learning and teaching • Suggest digital tools for online language learning • Report pertinent and valuable content-related information from the internet • Paraphrase translated text with context-sensitivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web search Keyword Techniques • Amplitude of Information in Different Search Engines • Tips and Tricks in Using Translator for Text Accuracy and Appropriateness • Utilization of Online Language Teaching Tools: YouTube videos/music, interactive visual applications, social networking sites
<p>Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formulate meaningful questions relevant to student's understanding • Demonstrate good diction appropriate to student's language level • Maximize student's participation through facilitation techniques • Adapt traditional teaching practices in teaching content in online setting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art of Questioning • Student's Level and Diction Workshop • Facilitation Techniques • Cultural Learning Style • Anger Management

Part 2. Training Programs and Courses for Online English Language Teachers

Overview

This is the general requirement for all courses within this training program. Each course must follow the recommended standard and particular guidelines.

General Characteristics of the Course Facilitator

A qualified mentor should be professional, knowledgeable and compassionate. Someone who can model professional behavior and act as a role model for the participants in handling online classes. His or her understanding of the subject is demonstrated by his or her ability to convey material clearly, concisely, and in a variety of ways: he or she can customize the curriculum to a diverse student body. In addition, the ideal mentor is sympathetic to the learners' circumstances and enthusiastic about assisting them in their professional development.

General Pedagogical Guidelines:

1. It is important to include a brief introduction of oneself in the training program. Both the instructor and course participants must introduce themselves. This helps an instructor meet the participants, who may be unfamiliar with one another and helps students to build a rapport and camaraderie. For example, during this time the instructor can break the ice by having people introduce themselves and stating who they are personally and professionally. By creating a welcoming atmosphere, learners will be more collaborative to course activities and content, which leads to a spirit of cooperation among them.
2. The training program should use real issues to make it more interesting. This motivates learners to address and grapple with these issues. When a program includes the opportunity for participants to explore problems by themselves, debate their viewpoints and share them with others, learners are more apt to feel that they own the training. For maximum effectiveness, training programs must include opportunities for practical work so that participants can put what they have learned into practice.
3. Each training course can be designed as on-site, online and blended learning depending on the convenience of the course participants. However, necessary technological equipment for each course must be present. All courses are synchronous; therefore, online learning communication should be conducted using the most accessible, user-friendly, and preferred software of the online language school and its course participants.
4. Course participants must have successfully completed the online language school's hiring procedure. With that, they should possess at least the minimum competencies demanded by the organization. Throughout all courses, they should also adhere to the online language school's code of conduct.
5. It is necessary to design assessment for every course. To assess course participants' knowledge, skills, abilities relating to specific course, the following must be observed:

1. Prior to the commencement of the course, course participant must take a pre-test to determine what they already know about the course content. This test is graded only on participation. The students score will not have any impact to his/her final course grade.
 2. During the course, course participant must be assessed using a check your progress activities and embedded assessments.
 3. At the end of each course, course participant must take a post assessment to show growth in knowledge, skills and abilities related to the course target concepts and competencies.
6. Course participants' grade will be formulated on their performance based on the following:
1. Practical performance
 2. Written Test
 3. Reflective Essay
 4. Cooperation

General Learner Support Guideline:

A team dedicated to addressing the problems of course participants around course scheduling, technical assistance, instructional materials, assessment retrieval, and submission bins should be organized.

Five Training Program Courses:

- Technology Knowledge - Amateur Users
- Technology Knowledge – Expert Users
- TPACK Course for Most Disadvantaged Online English Language Teachers
- 1:1 Mentoring Program (Novice & Senior Teachers Collaboration)
- Course Conference of Seasoned Teachers for Seasoned Teachers

Course: Technology Knowledge - Amateur Users

Course Description:

This course is designed for amateur technology users offering a solid foundation of technology skills and strategies to help them be efficient in their day-to-day use. As a hands-on training course, each participant should have access to a computer to gain competence in basic computer use. It is expected that their working knowledge of operating systems, word processing, spreadsheet creation and manipulation, email, presentation software, and an internet browser will be improved. Participants learn in a supportive environment and leave with strategies they can use right away.

Additional Facilitator's Qualification:

An information technology professional who can help with basic computer troubleshooting, software installation and configuration, and keyboard shortcuts and program features.

Course Participants:

Online English language teachers who consider themselves as comfortable users of technology. They are familiar with the basics of computer operation such as encoding and storing data, installing, browsing, and the like; but, have limited knowledge on hardware troubleshooting and software operation techniques.

Learning Objectives:

At the end of the course program, the course participants are expected to:

1. Demonstrate knowledge, skills, and concepts related to software and hardware technical problems
2. Name possible technical difficulties and demands in online language teaching
3. Select appropriate and prompt techniques in handling basic and elaborate software operation

Possible Topics:

1. Basic Hardware Troubleshooting
2. Software Troubleshooting Techniques
3. Understanding software functions and tools
4. Keyboard Shortcuts
5. Understanding Digital Tools: teaching platforms, content creation apps, webcam software, translator device, virtual whiteboards, etc.

Course Pointers:

1. Observation and real-time practice are essential components of every activity.
2. Attendees are required to recall/imagine a challenging situation at work, and then brainstorm and share potential solutions.
3. Efficiency and accuracy are the prime evaluation criteria of the course.
4. Each participant should receive timely feedback about their strengths and weaknesses relative to the course goal.

Course: Technology Knowledge – Expert Users

Course Description:

This course is designed for participants who are confident users of technology. It will present the latest developments in new technologies and discuss their use in language learning. It hopes to enable an individual to install, upgrade and optimize various technologies to aid language learning. It will be technology driven and skills focused, with a particular emphasis on professional communication. A critical examination and evaluation of diverse digital resources is much anticipated in the course.

Additional Facilitator's Qualification:

- An IT expert with a high level of confidence to demonstrate overall competence in teaching and learning of English as a second language using ICT; and/or
- Someone who has experience in designing, creating or managing e-learning platforms for online language learning; and/or
- Someone who is responsible for system planning, software development, programming, site implementation, troubleshooting and data conversion to enhance school's capabilities and operations.

Course Participants:

Online English language teachers who consider themselves as confident explorers of technology. They have good knowledge on data encoding, browsing, installing, troubleshooting and the like. They are not afraid to experiment with new technology.

Learning Objectives:

At the end of the course program, the course participants are expected to:

1. Select appropriate and prompt techniques in handling basic and elaborate software operation
2. Appraise available technologies in maximizing its use for language learning
3. Produce relevant and meaningful reflection to resolve technical difficulties and impact of new technologies.

Possible Topics:

1. Hardware Specifications Evaluation
2. Affordances and Challenges of Different Digital Educational Tools/Softwares
3. Digital Language Learning Tools and their Impact for Learning

Course Pointers:

1. It is recommended to gather a list of digital tools that participants of the course utilize for their work as online English language teachers. A discussion about the benefits and drawbacks of each tool should be presented by the participants themselves.
2. Critical analysis, evaluation and debate of various digital tools are main components of the course.
3. As a joint or individual output, attendees must propose new ideas to enhance online language learning issues.
4. Each participant should receive timely feedback about their strengths and weaknesses relative to the course goal.

Course: TPACK Course for Most Disadvantaged Online English Language Teachers

Course Description:

This course is designed for participants who have limited exposure to online English language teaching and/or technology. It will introduce and cover all TPACK domains (i.e. TK, PK, CK, TPK, TCK, PCK and TPACK). It aims to develop teaching practices that will meet the standards for Newly Qualified Tutors in the platform. This will include a general overview of the course material, basic computer techniques, as well as an explanation of the various teaching methods and the fundamentals of how they all work together in an online language setting.

Course Participants:

Teachers with **all** of the following traits:

- e. Less than 3 years teaching experience
- f. Graduates who did not complete Education-related courses
- a. Between ages 31 and 40 (senior group for this study)
- b. Consider themselves as Comfortable Users of technology (less expert for this study)

Course Objectives:

At the end of the course program, the course participants are expected to:

1. Comprehend theoretical foundation of online language teaching through TPACK framework
2. Demonstrate theoretical knowledge into practice objectively and effectively
3. Foster attitude and skills needed to be as an effective online English language teacher

Course Pointers:

1. Each domain must be introduced one at a time throughout the entire course.
2. The sequence of presentation for each domain begins from single knowledge progressing to combination of domains knowledge (i.e. TK, CK, PK, TCK, TPK, PCK and TPACK).
3. It is recommended to introduce single domain knowledge as follows: TK, CK, then, PK. This is to alleviate teachers' initial concerns about technology. Following that is CK, which provides an overview of the subject area or topic matter that teachers must master. Eventually, CK can be a good tool to reflect on for their PK course afterwards.
4. Each participant should undergo an exit assessment for each domain before taking a new course.
5. Each participant should receive timely feedback about their strengths and weaknesses relative to the course goal.

Course: 1:1 Mentoring Program (Novice & Senior Teachers Collaboration)

Course Description:

This is a mentoring program where novice teachers are partnered with senior teachers within the first three months on the platform. The goal of the program is to enable new teachers to understand the workplace culture and accelerate skills development. Senior teachers should be able to clearly communicate their skills, get a broader viewpoint, and take on more leadership responsibilities. At the end of the program, each pair should submit a written evaluation of their experience.

Course Participants:

Online English language teachers with less than 1 year teaching experience partnered with senior teachers with good credibility in the teaching platform

Mentee (novice teacher)

- express daily difficulties/challenges encountered in the teaching platform
- participate actively in mentoring activities and goal accomplishment
- write a reflection paper about the program
- provides feedback and recommendations for program improvement

Mentor (senior teacher)

- provide weekly tips/guides on managing smooth classes in the platform
- work with the mentee in developing an individual development plan
- write recommendations on which TPACK training is needed for the novice teacher
- write a reflection paper about the program
- provides feedback and recommendations for program improvement

Course Objectives:

At the end of the course program, the course participants are expected to:

1. Help identify skills, knowledge and practices needed to improve craft in online English language teaching
2. Develop good communication engagement and cooperative learning
3. Foster continuous growth regardless of one's career expertise

Course Pointers:

1. This should be facilitated by one of the school's coaching teams.
2. Rules and regulations about the course should be established by the coaching team.
3. An orientation about mentor's and mentee's roles should be provided prior the commencement of the course. Mentors and mentees should be given an orientation for their responsibilities during the program.
4. Course participants should convene and discuss about the program by the end of the course. A reflective essay should be submitted by all course participants.

Course: Course Conference of Seasoned Teachers for Seasoned Teachers

Additional Facilitator's Qualification:

An online English language teacher who has been teaching for more than 6 years; has a proven track record; preferably holds a bachelor's degree in Education; and has participated in the majority of the school's in-service training programs.

Course Participants:

Online English language teachers who have been teaching in the platform for more than 6 years regardless of other demographic factors

Course Description:

This course is designed for teachers who have been teaching for more than 6 years in the online English language teaching industry. The purpose of this course is to continuously keep the teachers abreast about new trends in the field of technology for education and on how to integrate those in teaching that could further improve the quality and quantity of learning a student would have. Each participant must provide a presentation on his or her strongest competence, gained from professional experiences and knowledge.

Course Objectives:

At the end of the course program, the course participants are expected to:

1. Develop their metacognition skills as online English language teachers by recalling professional experiences
2. Enhance communication skills by making a short presentation and discussing it with other seasoned teachers in the field
3. Foster good collaboration among online English language teachers

Course Pointers:

1. This course should be structured like a conference for experienced online English language teachers, where they must decide as a group what knowledge or skill they want to impart with one another during the course. They could suggest content that has already been practiced or that could be used in the future as a solution to the current difficulty that teachers are experiencing on the platform.
2. Each participant (or group of participants) must share any insight or skill (related to the decided focus knowledge of the group) that will benefit everyone.
3. There should be an open forum among online English language teachers about the presented topic.
4. All of the skills or insights offered should be summed up in a single report contributed by all of the course participants.